

**STRATEGIC CHALLENGES AND THE WAY FORWARD: A CASE OF
NEPAL AIRLINES CORPORATION**

A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of
Scotland for the award of Doctoral in Business Administration

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Declaration

I hereby assert this is my own work that has not been presented in any university or any other body. This thesis is submitted to University of the West of Scotland for the partial fulfilment of the requirements for degree of Doctorate in Business administration (DBA).

I also declare that intellectual content of this work is of my own efforts except where stated has been adequately referenced.

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Abstract

With the advancement in technology and increasing innovations, the aviation industry has become far more efficient in the past few decades, contributing significantly towards the rapid globalisation. With the increasing popularity of air travel, the number of service providers has also increased significantly, making the aviation industry as one of the most competitive industries. Following the increased competition, questions regarding the sustainability and survival of many airline companies are arising and this has led to the need for identifying ways of sustaining traditional airline companies. An extensive review of the literature has suggested that, although several studies are conducted to identify the strategic challenges faced by airline companies across the world, no prior study was conducted in identifying the challenges and critical success factors of Nepal Airlines Corporation (NAC). NAC, which was once the best airline in South Asia, is now facing existential challenges with debt surging year by year. Therefore, this study aims to investigate NAC identify the strategic challenges faced by the organisation as well as its critical success factors in order to bridge the knowledge gap as well as to offer insights to the practitioners.

This study adopted the interpretivist-inductive approach by utilising semi-structured interviews for collecting the research data. A total of 47 interviews were conducted with the employees of NAC (the CEO, department directors, and general employees), customers, ticketing agents, and an expert in the Nepalese aviation industry. Purposive and snowball sampling techniques were used for recruiting the research participants. The collected data were analysed using manual thematic analysis.

This research identified NAC's various political challenges, namely increased corruption due to the political appointment system, employees' political affiliations and extreme unionism leading to the lack of collaboration across departments, instability of the government, and outdated government public procurement act for airlines and operational challenges such as the lack of sufficient fleet, spare parts and ground handling equipment, the lack of effective research and development practices, the lack of coordination with TIA and lengthy and ineffective employee recruitment process. This study also highlighted various critical success factors of, namely effective fleet management, effective management of people, effective planning and development, great organisational culture, and minimal external interference in the decision-making process. The findings of this research make significant contributions to the body of knowledge by bridging the knowledge gap that previously existed.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Meanings
CAAN	Civil Aviation Authority of Nepal
CIAA	Commission for the Investigation of Abuse of Authority
EU	European Union
IATA	International Air Transport Association
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organisation
NAI	Nepal Aviation Industry
NG	Nepal Government
NAC	Nepal Airlines Corporation
TIA	Tribhuwan International Airport

1. Introduction

1.1. Background of the Research

As the living condition of the people across the globe is gradually improving, the landscape of the aviation industry is also transforming with more and more people travelling by air. The number of air journeys is expected to continue rising in the next decade with the number reaching 7.8 billion in 2036 (IATA, 2017) from 3.1 billion in 2016 (Uniting Aviation, 2018). With increased innovations in the aviation industry and the rapidly rising market demand, the number of airlines across the world is also increasing, making the airline industry highly competitive. The aviation industry, which is one of the key drivers of the globalisation, makes significant contributions to the global economy by providing employment to over 62.7 million people (Uniting Aviation, 2018) and contributing \$2.7 trillion to the world economy.

With the growth of the airline industry and the emergence of new airline companies, the airline industry is has become highly profit-oriented. Until the late 1970s, the industry was highly regulated with little concerns in regard to competition and needs for organisational strategies for enhancing profitability (Kangis and O'Reilly, 2003). However, that quickly changed in 1978 when United States Airlines Deregulation Act came in whose primary purpose was to remove control from the government over fares, market-entry, and routes from commercial airlines (McKenzie, 1991). After deregulation, various low costs airlines entered the market and the competition intensified (Chan, 2000). The aviation industry is one of the fastest-growing industries with exceptionally complex business models that face numerous challenges in the industry as well as in its surrounding provisions (Belobaba et al., 2009).

In 2014, the annual revenue of the airline industry increased to \$746 billion from \$369 billion in 2004, which was mainly driven by low-cost carriers. However, the profit margin of the sector was relatively small at 2.6% (IATA, 2014). The key partners like airports, aircraft manufactures made great profits; however, the industry itself is struggling. It was due to the complex nature of the business, lack of sustainable competitive advantage, weakness to exogenous events, geopolitics, and the price pressures (Clayton and Hiltz, 2015). The airline industry faces a lot of strategic challenges over some time to meet or exceed customer

expectations. Airlines industry is facing challenges where customer expectation and needs are rising at a higher pace (Abdelghany and Abdelghany, 2016). Furthermore, fluctuations in the fuel price are also impacting airlines' operational costs as a rise in fuel price increases operation costs (Bilotkach et al., 2015). The perception of a customer segment has been increasingly negative towards airline companies due to their environmental impacts such as noise pollutions and air pollutions (Taneja, 2017).

The aircraft manufacturing companies such as Boeing and Airbus always have been committed towards product innovation, pressurising airlines companies to upgrade their systems, which requires huge investments (Johnson et al., 2008). The supplier power in airlines industry is high due to the existence of just a few aircraft manufactures and the consequent for the regular update for technological advancement adds additional strength to the suppliers (IATA, 2012). There are several internal and external environment factors that airlines companies are exposed to that create rapidly changing business models. Brand reputation is one of the competitive strengths that helps organisations to remain market leaders; however, the brand reputation of the airline industry is fragile and vulnerable (Grant, 2008). Strategic alliances another challenge that airlines companies face in the global market where airlines that form strategic alliances can be highly competitive than the others.

Effective organisational strategy plays a crucial role in the success of an organisation (Barney, 1997; Wit and Meyer, 1998; Henry, 2008) and aviation organisation are no exceptions. Organisational strategies have been defined in multiple ways by multiple scholars, some of them focus on the relationship between missions and visions of the organisation whereas other focus on the need of the firm to cope with peripheral environmental issues through the application of internal resources and capabilities (Hambrick and Fredrickson, 2001). The environment in which airline companies operate is consists of various interrelated factors and consideration of each of them is crucial in order to develop business strategies that can lead to organisational success. The strategic competency of airlines depends on both the internal and external environmental factors that have impacts on the ability of the organisation (Johnson et al., 2005). The strategic analysis helps an organisation to gather relevant and sufficient information for strategy formulation and implementation (Campbell et al., 2002). Strategic analysis is a vital task that should be carried out before any strategy formulation or

implementation as many strategies fail due to formulation and implementation not being informed by an effective strategic analysis of internal and external environmental factors.

A review of the literature indicated multiple ways of strategic analysis that leads to gaining competitive strength. Although many studies over the past decade were conducted in gaining a competitive edge through strategic analysis (i.e., Park 2003; Graham 2004; Albers et al., 2005; Jarach 2005; William, 2006), only a handful of studies are conducted in the aviation sector. Although the tools for strategic analysis used for the internal and the external environment of the organisation is same, the outcome of the analysis may differ from an organisation to another. This difference may also occur in the same kind of organisation that operate in different markets. Following the increased competition, deregulation, and development in technology, there is a greater need to understand the competitive power an airline service provider prior to forming any organisation strategy. It is challenging for airlines companies to maintain their competitive advantage for a sustainable period as the airlines market is exceptionally volatile. Therefore, there is always a need to understand the strategic challenges faced by the organisation on a consistent basis.

A strategic analysis of the aviation industry helps to gather relevant and sufficient information that is required for strategy formulation and strategy implementation (Campbell et al., 2002). Most of the strategies fail because organisation formulate and implement strategy without proper analysis of the internal and the external environment, organisational goals, and the competitive environment. This research is being conducted in Nepal Airlines Corporation (NAC). The primary aim of this study is to make is strategic recommendations for enhancing the overall documentation performance. In doing so, this study focuses on identifying the challenges faced by the organisation as well as the critical success factors. Ahis study also conducts a strategic analysis of NAC by identifying factors related to both internal and external environments. Analysis of the organiser environments can be done through SWOT and PESTLE analysis (Oxford University, 2007).

Numerous Empirical studies have been conducted to assess the challenges faced by various strategic challenges faced by different organisations across the world. Bitelmal (2010) conducted empirical research on strategic challenges that airports face in gaining competitive advantages on Dubai airport and concluded that competitiveness of an airport depends on general condition, strategic direction, competitive situation, and the resources acquirement.

Likewise, Yusoff (2008) conducted a study on strategic management practises in the local authority of Malaysia and concluded that dilemmas and conflict are two important constructs illuminating cultures and tradition that have secure links to contest and political nature of the strategy-formulation process. Correspondingly, Misiura (2016) also investigated enterprise risk management, structure, and practise in the airline industry that concluded that both technical and intuitional factors configure the management system and the organisational risk management structure.

Despite being one of the fastest-growing industry in the world, the business environment of the airline industry is uniquely complex where airlines itself struggles to make profits; however, its key partners like aircraft manufacture and airports make tidy profits (Belobaba et al., 2009). The complex nature of business includes weakness of the aviation industry and the challenges faced to exogenous events such as volcanic eruptions, the spread of infectious disease, significant degree of guideline and constant pressure to drop the price without any effects on operational efficiency and safety, geopolitical situations, evolving technology (Future of the airline industry, 2017; Zhang 2017; Clayton and Hiltz, 2015). The rapidly changing needs of the customers and high customer expectation are also some of the challenges faced by the airline industry (Ford and Despeisse 2016; Abdelghany and Abdelghany 2016). Jet Fuel is one of the major operating costs in the aviation industry and vacillations in the fuel price has impacted the operation cost of the airline industry (Bilotkach et al., 2015).

There are various other strategic challenges faced by airline industry such as radical and incremental product innovation from manufactures (Naikuni, 2009) and the regular technological updates and product innovations from manufactures, adding pressure to airline companies to upgrade their system (IATA 2012; Johnson et al., 2009). Airlines industry is constantly exposed to the fast-changing business environment and unstable brand reputation (Vanoosterhout et al., 2006). In order to overcome the various strategic challenges, different airline companies strategically collaborate with each other forming strategic alliances and it has been on of the most powerful trends that swept global business in last 100 years (Peker, 2003). According to Richard (2006), airlines must be effective in four general areas, namely attracting customers, managing its fleet, managing its people, and managing its finance in order to sustain in the current competitive global environment.

As the living standard of Nepalese people is gradually improving, the culture of air travel is becoming gradually more popular among middle-class people. The market for aviation companies is rapidly rising and so is the competition with the emergence of both national and international carriers. Despite the increase in the popularity of the industry, an extensive review of the literature indicated that the amount of research done in the area is very little. There are some studies conducted precisely in NAC; however, they either only focus on a certain aspect of the organisation or they are not in-depth. For example, a case study research was done in NAC where only SWOT analytical tool was used and no primary data was collected (Yadav, 2016). Similarly, another empirical research by Joshi et al. (2015) focused on understanding the present scenario of NAC without using any analytical tools or primary data. Moreover, a study was done on influencing factors of organisational performance in NAC using a mixed-method approach where primary data was collected through only fifteen in-depth interviews with government and NAC executives (Gyanwali and Walsh, 2019). No previous studies focusing precisely on strategic challenges faced by NAC was found in the literature.

This research aims to fill the knowledge vacuum and to provide recommendations to the practitioners by identifying the strategic challenges faced by NAC as well as the critical success factors of the organisation. In this research, and a wider range of strategic analysis tools will be deployed in order to have a better understanding of the organisational environments. Literature evidence suggests that one of the key reasons behind the failure of NAC is the lack of strategic planning. It is expected that this research will identify various interesting insights about NAC and provide ways for enhancing organisational performance, eventually bridging the knowledge gap that presently exists.

1.2. Problem Statement

NAC, the national flag carrier of Nepal, was once known as the best airline in entire South Asia. During 1989, NAC generated \$54.3 million revenue with an operating profit of \$ 17 million. It was the country's largest employer with 2,200 employees and the largest foreign currency earner with bringing roughly \$ 15 million a year from abroad. However, the future of the organisation changed swiftly as almost three decades later, NAC is making millions of rupees loss daily. In 2019, the annual loss of NAC stood at NPR 1.5 billion (approx. \$13 million) with the debt reaching a critical level of NPR 37 billion (approx. \$317 million)

(Prasain, 2019). Despite multiple government bailouts, the organisation is still facing an existential crisis with its future being highly uncertain.

Despite the challenges the organisation is facing, an extensive review of the literature suggested that no priory study was conducted to identify the ways for enhancing the performance of NAC. Some of the prior studies done within the organisation either only focused on a certain organisational aspect or was based on mere secondary data available on the internet. Besides, no prior study conducted a comprehensive analysis of the organisation's strategic position as well as the strategic challenges faced by it, leaving knowledge voids in the literature. The lack of research has prevented the management of the organisation from having an actual understanding of the challenges the organisation is facing, leading to many of the decisions made being ineffective and sometimes inappropriate. This study, therefore, is being conducted to fill the knowledge gap that currently exists in the literature as well as to provide evidence-based recommendations to the practitioners for enhancing the sustainability and the performance of NAC.

1.3. Aim and Objectives of the research

1.3.1. The Aim of the Research

The foregoing sections of this research highlighted the importance of strategic analysis for the success of an organisation. The earlier section also discussed the number of prior studies conducted in NAC being very low, leading to the strategic decisions of NAC not being evidence-based. This study, therefore, aims to bridge the current knowledge gap as well as to provide strategic recommendations to NAC for enhancing its organisational performance. Therefore, the following research aim has been formulated.

The aim of this research is to offer strategic recommendations to Nepal Airlines Corporations for enhancing its organisational performance upon empirically studying its current strategic position, strategic challenges, and critical success factors.

1.3.2. Research Objectives

In order to achieve the research aim stated above, the following research objectives have been developed:

- Objective 1: To critically review the literature related to strategic analysis, challenges faced by the aviation industry, and the critical success factors of an airline company.

- Objective 2: To conduct a strategic analysis of Nepal Airlines Corporation for identifying both internal and external environmental factors that their impacts on the organisation.

- Objective 3: To identify the strategic challenges faced by Nepal Airlines Corporation.

- Objective 4: To reveal the critical success factors of Nepal Airlines Corporation based on the views of various organisational stakeholders.

- Objective 5: To make strategic recommendations for enhancing the overall performance of Nepal Airlines Corporation based on the research findings.

1.3.3. Research Questions

In order to achieve the above research objectives, the following research questions are designed:

- a. What are the common tools and techniques for conducting the strategic analysis of an organisation?
- b. What are the key internal and external environmental factors of Nepal Airlines Corporation and how they impact its organisational performance?
- c. What are the key strategic challenges faced by Nepal Airlines Corporation?
- d. What are the critical success factors of Nepal Airlines Corporation?
- e. What kind of strategic changes can result in Nepal Airlines Corporation's enhanced organisational performance and sustainability?

1.4. Justification for the research

As presented in the earlier sections of this chapter, this study is designed to make strategic recommendations for NAC for enhancing his organisational performance and profitability. In order to do so, in this study, the environmental factors that impact the operations of NAC will be identified, the challenges faced by NAC will be assessed, and the critical success factors of NAC will be evaluated.

The first and only national flag carrier of Nepal, NAC, was established in July 1958 as Royal Nepal Airlines Cooperation (RNAC). The headquarter of the organisation is located in Sundhara, Kathmandu, Nepal with the main base being Tribhuvan International Airport. It currently operates in over 25 destinations domestically and five destinations internationally, operating fleet of 11 aircraft. After the liberalisation of the airline industry, RNAC was renamed as NAC. The first aircraft of NAC was Douglas DC-3. Which served many domestic routes and a handful of international destinations. NAC acquired its first Boeing 727 aircraft in 1972. It received Hawker Siddle Hs-748 in 1970, Twin Otter in 1971, Boeing 727 in 1972. Between 1988 to 1989, NAC reported revenue of \$54.3 million with an operating profit of \$17 million. It was the country's largest employer with 2,200 employees and the largest foreign currency earner with bringing roughly \$ 15 million a year from abroad.

Over half a century later, once globally renown and a very profitable organisation was found on its knees, struggling to stay afloat. In 2013, NAC halted its service during the peak season stating that they did not have planes to fly. During the same year, NAC also lost its long-running contract with TIA as it failed in successfully completing its contractual obligation of effective ground handling. Despite the fall of NAC, the aviation sector continued to grow with the improving living standard of Nepalese people as well as the increasing globalisation. This led to the emergence of various private airlines such as Buddha Airlines, Yeti Airlines, and Himalayan Airlines. These new entrants have now taken a significant proportion of Nepalese aviation market reducing the market share of NAC into a fraction of what it used to be.

NAC has experienced a complete ruin with debt piling over year by year despite receiving significant grants from the government of Nepal. The organisation has repeatedly taken loans for buying new aircraft; however, this does not appear to have helped the organisation in overcoming the losses. Despite its great history and past glory, NAC is now rated as one of the

worst airlines in the world, ranking among 22 airlines that have been awarded two stars by the UK based Skytrax in annual world airlines rating (The Himalayan, 2015). European Union (EU) has banned NAC from flying in its airspace since December 5, 2013 (My Republican, 2016). Since then, NAC is not allowed to operate in any European Union countries neither any airlines registered in Nepal are allowed to fly in Europe. Due to this, NAC is making millions of rupees losses daily.

The Skytrax rating of NAC is more focused on the services rather than safety. NAC is criticised for its low-quality performance, inadequate and unreliable standard of product, poor front-line staff service for cabin services, and poor home-based airport environment. NAC has heavily suffered from lack of transparency, corruption, political interference, due to which it was once reduced to the fleet of two operational planes and five international destination in 2014 from 21 international destinations and the fleet of 19 aircraft in 1980 (Econ-it, 2015). NAC has not been able to hire pilots and other employees to fulfil their vacant jobs due to less competitive financial package and uncertainty revolving the future of the organisation. Once, NAC had announced the vacancy for two junior pilots for domestic routes, but it did not a single application (Nepali Times, 2010). NAC's market share in Nepal has been much taken by other private budget airlines (Himalayan Times, 2016). They have capitalised on the weaknesses of the NAC. Similarly, on international routes where NAC stopped flying, the market is now controlled by other international carriers.

Despite significant technological advancement in the aviation industry, NAC has been unable to incorporate them on a consistent basis. This has impacted the safety standards of NAC and it was ranked one of the least safe airlines (Mail Online, 2015). Besides, NAC has faced its worst-ever flight punctuality crisis where it had to halt its flight for international destinations due to the lack of aircraft (The Himalayan, 2016). Among the total eight aircraft, three of them fly on international routes, three on domestic routes with rest being grounded. This is a usual scenario of NAC, leading to frequent flight cancellations. Poor organisational management and the lack of coordination across different departments has been one of the key reasons behind this. Due to such ineffective utilisation of resources, NAC has been making millions of rupees loss daily. In 2019, the annual loss of NAC stood at NPR 1.5 billion with the debt reaching a critical level of NPR 37 billion (Prasain, 2019).

Despite extremely concerning organisational performance, only a handful of research is conducted on NAC and how the organisation can be made more profitable. Few studies conducted on the organisation are either based on secondary data or incomprehensive. Precisely from the strategic perspective, no prior comprehensive study was conducted leaving a knowledge void in the literature. As the organisational debt is mounting year by year, its future is becoming increasingly uncertain. Therefore, it is considered relevant to conduct this study as it will not only bridge the knowledge gap but also uncover insights that can be crucial in making strategic recommendations to the NAC for enhancing its sustainability and overall organisational performance.

1.5. Brief Descriptions of the Research Method

This exploratory research follows interpretivist philosophy for answering the research question as it seeks to uncover new constructs or invent new theoretical perspectives (Currall and Towler, 2003). This research adopts the inductive approach for theory creation by taking a holistic approach. The case study is selected as the research strategy in this study as it allows in-depth analysis into topic or phenomena with real-life settings, leading to rich, empirical descriptions, and the development of the theory (Dubois and Gadde, 2002; Ridder et al., 2004; Yin, 2014). This research utilises the qualitative research method to explore subjects, themes, and categories for exploring and describing the research phenomena (Brewer, 2007). The qualitative research was considered further relevant for achieving the research objectives and the field of the study is not highly developed due to the lack of prior studies.

This research deployed a qualitative data collection instrument – in-depth and semi-structured interview – for primary data collection. In order to collect the research data, NAC employees (CEO, directors, and general employees), customers, ticketing agents, and an expert from the Nepalese aviation industry were interviewed. A pilot study consisting of three respondents was conducted before the main data collection process to ensure the relevant and required data can be collected. Following the pilot study, minor modifications were made in the interview questions. The main research data was collected from 47 respondents using purposive and snowball sampling techniques under the non-probability sampling method. For ensuring the reliability and validity of the data, the transcribed interview was sent to the respondents for verification. Comprehensive discussion and justifications of the selected research methods,

sample size, and the steps taken for data analysis are elaborated in chapter three and four of the thesis.

1.6. Outline of the Thesis

This study consists of six chapters and the outline of each chapter is detailed below:

TABLE 1-1: OUTLINE OF THE THESIS

Chapters	Descriptions
Chapter 1	This chapter reviewed the background of the research, highlighted the research problem, aim, objectives, and questions. It also provided justifications for the study, a brief discussion of the methodology chosen, and the scope and limitations of the research.
Chapter 2	This chapter deals with the theoretical aspect of the research by reviewing various strategy theories, elements of strategy theory, strategy formulation, strategy analysis, the importance of strategy analysis, various analytical tools available for strategic analysis, and implementation of the strategy. The different strategic analytical tools are described and how they can be used to analyse an organisation within the aviation industry is discussed. Besides, this chapter also reviews prior studies related to the global aviation industry and the critical success factors of the aviation industry. Finally, this chapter presents a contextual review of NAC and its strategic challenges.
Chapter 3	This chapter deals with the methodology aspect of the research by discussing and justifying the selected research philosophy for the research after critically evaluating all key research philosophies. It also deals with the selected research approach, research design, data collection methods, data analysis techniques, sampling techniques and sample size of this study. Besides, this chapter also provides insight into the challenges that researcher faced during the data collection process and steps that were taken to mitigate them.
Chapter 4	This chapter deals with the analysis of the research findings. The primary data collected for the research is analysed and themes are developed for answering the research objectives. The key themes include the environmental factors of

	NAC, the strategic challenges faced by NAC, and the critical success factors of NAC.
Chapter 5	This chapter discusses the findings of the research by locating them in a wider context. The strengths and weaknesses of the findings are evaluated in this chapter whilst highlighting the contributions they make to the literature.
Chapter 6	This concluding chapter revisits the research process as well as the findings and discusses how each research objectives were achieved. This chapter also clearly outlines the theoretical, methodological, and practical contributions to the research findings. Besides, recommendations to NAC and its stakeholders is also highlighted. Finally, this chapter acknowledges the possible limitations of the research findings and makes recommendations for further studies for extending the current research.

1.7. Scope and Limitations of the Study

This research is being conducted on NAC. It reviews the strategic aspect of the organisation by studying its strategic position, strategic challenges, and critical success factors. In order to analyse the strategic position, internal and external organisational factors will be analysed using PESTLE and SWOT analysis. The purposed study is limited to NAC and the findings may be irrelevant to other airline companies. Key limitations of this study are addressed below.

Lack of Generalisation: This study is undertaken only in the single case study of NAC. Therefore, the findings of this research might not be useful for any other airlines as the internal and external environmental factors differ from one organisation to another. Besides, the way in which organisations operate in developing countries can be different from developed countries. This can result in the findings being less generalisable.

Small Sample Size: This is interpretive research. Given that interpretive research tends to have a smaller sample size, the reliability and the replicability of the findings can be limited.

Exclusion of Competitive Analysis: After carefully considering the time and resource limitations, no analysis of the NAC's competitive status was conducted in this study. This may lead to the strategic analysis not being highly robust.

1.8. Conclusions

The aviation industry faces various strategic challenges due to constancy changing business environment. These changes are caused by the emergence of low-cost airlines, growing strategic alliance between airlines, and other geopolitical factors that impact on the operation and financial position of airlines. In the context of NAC, despite being in operation for more than 62 years, the organisation is still struggling with the debt increasing year by year. The future of the organisation is now in question as it does not have sufficient fleet to fly neither financial power to buy them, instead it is relying on government grants and loans. The literature suggests that the primary reasons behind the failure of NAC include political interferences, corruption, and mismanagement.

This research was initiated to identify the critical success factors of NAC and to make strategic recommendations to the organisation for enhancing its organisational sustainability and profitability. In order to conduct the research in a systematic manner, this chapter dealt with the background of the study, discussed the research problem, outlined research aim, objectives, and questions, provided justifications for the research, presented a brief description of the methods, and outlined the structure of the thesis. The subsequent chapter now deals with the literature review aspect of the thesis.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

This chapter presents a review of the existing literature related to business strategy and strategic analysis. In this chapter, business strategies and their importance to the business is discussed in detail. Besides, tools for strategic analysis are reviewed and their suitability to this research is evaluated. This chapter also reviews the global and the Nepalese aviation industries, challenges faced by them, and their critical success factors. For accessing the relevant literature, various peer-reviewed journals, government websites, electronic databases, and relevant books were reviewed. The figure below presents the structure of this chapter.

FIGURE 2-1: STRUCTURE OF CHAPTER TWO

2.2. Business Strategy

The concept of strategy is considered as essential for the success of organisations that has been preferred by managers who consider detailed plans as irrelevant (McGhan,2004) however there is no straight forward, simple and step by step definition for strategy (Wit and Meyer, 1999; Henry, 2008; Barney, 1997). There is various definition provide by different scholars, business and consultant on strategy (Hambrick and Fredrickson, 2001) some of them focus on the relationship between strategy and targets of firms while other focus in the needs of firms to cope with external environmental issues through utilization of their internal resources and abilities. A strategy is about key issues for the future and vital for the survival of an organisation.

2.2.1. Defining Strategy

The word “Strategy” is believed to be originated from the Greek word “Strategos” which means “the art of general” with military roots (Galibraith and Nathanson, 1978, p.3). There are various definitions of strategy and still, there is not only one definition to follow. The traditional definition defines strategy as the concept of the strategy to a firm’s mission, objectives and tactics (Barney, 1997). In another term, Strategy is about finding the way in which it enables an organisation to compete, defining its missions and identifying the tactics that are needed to achieve its objectives.

According to Porter (1996), a strategy is about accomplishing competitive advantage through being unlike, delivering distinctive value-added to customers, having a clear and intact view of how to position uniquely in the relevant industry. Strategy can be successful if it is fit among organisational activities that complement each other and can deliver value to customer and organisation. There is an agreement that strategy is concerned with the match between organisational capabilities and its external environment however disagree on how it can be done.

Likewise, Kay (2000) argues that strategy is about using various tools carefully to analyse to understand the influence a company position in the market and will be a mistake to consider that strategy is about planning or visioning as it is hard to predict or control future. Similarly, Gary Hamel (2000) argues that strategy is about radical change and creating a new vision for the organisation where it becomes leaders than followers. Furthermore, Grant (2002) and Rowe

et al. (1993) agrees that strategy can be seen as creating opportunities by building on organisation resources and competencies. The table below now presents the key definitions of strategy provided by various strategy theorists.

TABLE 2-1: DEFINITIONS IS STRATEGY

Sources	Definition
<i>Chandler (1962, p. 21)</i>	<i>“The determination of the long-run goals and objectives of an enterprise and the adoption of courses of action and the allocation of resources necessary for carrying goals”</i>
<i>Benjamin and John (1980, p. 28)</i>	<i>“The framework which guides the choices that determine the nature and direction of an organisation”</i>
<i>Bryson (1996, p. 36)</i>	<i>“ A pattern of purposes, policies, programme, actions, decisions, or resources allocation that defines what an organisation is, what it does and why it does it”</i>
<i>Porter (1996, p. 64).</i>	<i>“Competitive strategy is about being different. It means deliberately, choosing a different set of activities to deliver a unique mix of value”</i>
<i>Galbraith and Nathanson (1978, p.3)</i>	<i>“Strategy means a specific action, usually but not always accompanied by the development of resources, to achieve an objective decided upon in strategic planning”</i>

According to Henry Mintzberg (1994), Strategy has several useful meanings and indicates that it is a plan, pattern, a position and perspective that can be a ploy, manoeuvre intended to outwit a competitor. All these strategy definitions incorporate important elements of strategy definition however strategy would best to considered long term direction of an organisation that would include both deliberate, logical strategy and more incremental, emergent patterns of strategy (Johnson et al., 2015). It would also include both strategies that emphasis difference, competition and strategies that recognise the roles of cooperation and even imitation. This strategy definition includes three elements long term, strategic direction and organisation (Wit and Meyer, 2014).

2.2.1.1. Long Term Strategy

A strategy is measured over years and developed for the long term. The concept of long term in strategy is vital that is emphasised by the “three horizons” framework. The “ three horizons”

framework consists of three genera of activity that suggest that organisation should think of themselves as comprising three types of business or activity, defined by their horizons in terms of years (Wit and Meyer,2014).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Wit, B.D. and Meyer, R. (2014). *Strategy synthesis: Resolving Strategy Paradoxes to create competitive Advantages*. London, New York: International Thomson Business.

FIGURE 2-2: THREE HORIZONS

Source: Wit and Meyer (2014)

In horizon 1, Organisation should concentrate, defend and expand its core business activities but anticipate that in long term it is likely to go flat or decline in organisation profit or value. In horizon 2, it emphasis organisation in beholding new market, emerging business market, and various genus of activities to generate a new source of profit. Whereas in horizon 3, it is all about risky research and development projects which are nothing for sure (Wit and Meyer, 2014). For example, any pharmaceutical company carrying research and development work for new drugs might take many years that might delay the profit of the organisation. In this horizon, the profit (or whatever else organisation value) might differ depending on the organisation. The basic of three horizons it helps the organisation to focus on short term to long term. A strategy involves pushing horizons 1 as far as possible, at the same time beholding to horizons 2 and 3 (Wit and Meyer, 2014).

2.2.1.2. Strategic direction

Strategic direction typically set according to long term objectives of the organisation but sometimes it emerges as a coherent pattern over time. Strategies follow some kind of long-direction or trajectory (Wit and Meyer, 2014). Strategic direction is the actions taken to achieve goals of the organisation strategy and is asses through vision, mission and objectives of the

organisation. The mission is what managers consider as the purpose of their organisations and what they would like to achieve in the future. It is often written down in the form of a mission statement and, unlike objectives and tactics, it does not change over time (Henry, 2008). Objectives are targets for a firm in which they set out what the firm desires to accomplish within a given timeframe, and they are typically focused on market growth, market share, increasing profits and cash flow (Oxford University, 2007). The particular actions undertaken by an organisation to implement its strategy are considered as ‘Tactics’ (Barney, 1997).

The procedure of bringing a strategy together is regarded as strategic management (Barney 1997, Henry 2008). Therefore, strategic management is about deciding a firm’s mission and objectives, analysing a firm’s situation and formulating and implementing a business plan. A strategy is the foundation of a unique and valuable position involving a different set of activities. A company will have competitive advantages and can outperform its rival if it can preserve its differences.

2.2.1.3. Organisation

An organisation consists of complex relationships both internally and externally. There are various types of stakeholder internally and externally. Internal organisation is filled with people from various background with a more or less reasonable view of what should be done (Wit and Meyer, 2014). Externally, organisation are surrounded by various types of stakeholder like customer, alliances, partners, supplier, regulators and investors. A strategy is crucially concerned with both internal and external factors of an organisation. It is crucial for the organisation to maintain the important relationship. The strategy typically involves managing people, relationship, resources, subject over many years. So, it is sometimes referred to as “strategic management”. Good strategies are about practicalities management as well as the analysing strategies.

2.2.2. Importance of Strategy

According to Lewis (2008), strategies support organisation to be more proactive than reactive in shaping its own future and they are crucial tools for organisation success. It is vital to initiate and implement actions that can help an organisation to control its destiny (Fadeyi et al., 2015; Maduenyi et al., 2015; Adegbuyi et al., 2015). Similarly, Thompson, Strickland and gamble (2007) argue that there are two primary reasons for strategies being important to organisations. Firstly, management needs to proactively craft on how the business of the organisation will be

conducted. It further helps well-thought strategy to do business, ways to evaluate the plan to capture customers, gain competitive advantage, improve the financial position and intact better within an organisation to improve performance. Secondly, the organisations that are strategy focused tend to have a distinct business plan and are more likely to have strong bottom-line performance. Effective strategy formulation and implementation or execution align with the vision of the organisation are likely to have a positive impact on the overall growth of the organisation.

Strategies should allow organisations to use internal resources and capabilities either to profit from opportunities or to respond to threats in the external environment (Barney 1997; Wit and Meyer 1998; Wharton School 1997; Henry 2008). A strategy is about formulating the way in which the organisation wants to compete in the market-defining its mission, identifying tactics in order to achieve its objectives (Barney 1979; Steiner and Miner 1977). An organisation with a clear strategy is likely to have outstanding performance through the achievement of competitive advantage (Porter, 1985). In simple term, a strategy is a documented plan on how the organisation will achieve the goals it has set out, analyse competitive environment, internal and external environment. It will then help to identify sustainable competitive advantage that will help to sustain the organisation in the market. Even though to sustain competitive advantage is extremely difficult as competitors always want to duplicate, imitate and surpass the competitive advantage of the organisation. Therefore, the competitive advantage is always temporary (Schnaars, 1994). Understanding of various elements of business strategies is crucial to forming effective business strategies.

2.3. Formulation of Business Strategies

According to Hofer and Schendel (1978, p.11), Strategy formulation is the process of deciding the basic mission of the organisation, the objectives that it seeks to achieve and using major strategies and policies to governing the use of organisation resources and capabilities to achieve its objectives. The strategy formulation is often concerned with decision and actions mechanism in the organisation specified in the decision-making process (Jofre, 2011). This stage is subjective action as it often relies on perception, the experience of top leaders or managers and knowledge. The formulation of strategy in a complex and large organisation has a different level of focus and scope with respect to function and organisation can exist in three levels (Jofre, 2011). The three levels of strategy are highly interdependent and integrated and they are Cooperate level, Business level and Operational level (Wit and Meyer, 2014).

2.3.1. Corporate level strategies

A corporate-level strategy is concerned with the overall scope of the organisation. It is concerned about how value can be added to the constitute business or organisation as a whole. This kind of strategy is at the high level of function and structure of the organisation which is regarded broad decision about the scope, direction and position of the organisation in long term (Jofre, 2011). It is often associated with organisation values and mission with top layer strategic planning and developed in much more significant depth (Johnson and Scholes, 2020).

It is crucial as it defines all other decisions that are made in the organisation along the line. It includes various strategic issues such as diversity of products or services, geographical scope, acquisition of a new business. It also helps to understand how resources are allocated with various elements of the organisation (Wit and Meyer, 2014). It is crucial to be clear about the corporate level strategy that is the basis of other strategic decisions like Vertical integration, horizontal integration, strategic alliances, merger and acquisition. The example of a corporate level strategy is Vice Media diversifying from the organisational magazine into retail, Publishing and Video.

2.3.2. Business level strategies

The strategy in the business level is broadly focused on competition and the main objectives are to develop and sustain competitiveness in the business it has decided to participate (Jofre, 2011). This type of strategy is often referred to as “Competitive Strategy” that is concerned on how any individual business should compete in the market. A business-level strategy is particularly concerned with within the organisation itself or unit of business and strategic issues like innovation, response to competitor’s moves, and appropriate scale. It is also concern with how value can be provided in any particular individual business or within a business unit (Wit and Meyer, 2014).

The strategic point of view the main objectives is to sustain competitive advantage on a long period of time as much as possible. According to Porter (1998), such competitiveness can be excel by the means of strategic position based on the advantage achieve either by cost and difference. Cost advantage can be achieved by providing the same benefits as competitors but in lower price, whereas differentiation advantage can be achieved when the benefits of the

products or service exceed those provided by its competitors. Another perspective to achieve competitive advantage is through resource-based view where the resource or assets (tangible or non-tangible) and capabilities to compete are strategically used and managed to achieve competitive advantage (Barney et al., 2001). The resources must be valuable, rare, inimitable and organised to gain competitive advantage. Many organisations today formulate their business-level strategy combining resource base view and positioning to gain competitive advantage (Grant, 2008b).

In this context, an organisation can formulate a business-level strategy by managing resources and capabilities to position itself in cost and differentiation advantage. The cost and differentiation strategies can formulate the scope in the narrow or wide market (Porter, 1998). The combination of cost, differentiation and scope is defined as a generic strategy of an organisation and the main aim of this strategy is to create value (Jofre, 2011; Porter, 1998). Porter (1998) expediently explains value creation as a quantifiable group of activities named as the value chain. The value chain consists of primary activities and supporting activities. Primary activities consist of inbound logistics, operation, outbound logistics marketing and sales respectively whereas supporting activities consist of administrative infrastructure, human resources management, technology and procurement respectively. Porter (1985) argues that primary and supporting activities do have three types of activities: direct, indirect and quality assurance that play a different role on competitive advantage. Direct activities involve creating value for the customer, indirect activities allow direct activities to take place, and quality assurance ensures the quality of other activities is asserted.

An organisation can gain a competitive advantage when it has the capability to edge out its competitors when competing for customers (Wit and Meyer, 2014). The discussions above state that an organisation wants to gain sustainable competitive advantage through resource base view, value chain and position in the market. An organisation can gain a competitive advantage that is sustainable if it cannot be derivative, replaced or battered by the actions of rivals and does not vanish from the developments in the environment (Porter, 1980). Therefore, it means that sustainability depends on two vital factors: competitive defendability and environment consonance (Wit and Meyer, 2014).

Competitive defendability means the competitive advantage is easier to defend than others due to various factors like difficult to imitate or competitors find impossible to attack. Organisation

competitive advantage is sustainable due to organisation ability to stay ahead of its competitors, outpace them in the race to stay ahead (Stalk, Evans and Shulman, 1992; Gilbert and Strebel, 1989). Therefore, building distinct business model will help an organisation that will fend off competitions and Organisation should remain true to its fundamental strengths, especially when it comes to unique resources and activities that it has built up over a prolonged period of time.

On Other hand, the constant flux in customer needs and wants, development in the market, change in government regulations, innovative technologies and change in distributions channels will all threaten the competitive advantage of the organisation and will weaken the organisation's position and undermine the fit between the organisation's competitive advantage and environment (Rumelt, 1980). Therefore, environment consonance requires an organisation to continuously adapt to the demands of the business model and new opportunities in the market.

2.3.3. Operational strategies

Operational strategies are concerned with how corporate level and business level strategy are delivered effectively in terms of people, process and resources. In most successful business strategies depend to a large extent on decisions that are taken or activity that occur at the operational level (Wit and Meyer, 2014). The formulation of operational strategies focuses on short-term activities at a functional level to support and implement business and corporate level strategy. Even though, each functional unit within an organisation has certain freedom over strategic choices however operational strategies must align with general long term strategy of the organisation (Slack and Lewis, 2011).

There are three aspects in this level such as short term characteristics of objectives, the specificity of scope and the involvement of operational managers in this level describe the formulation of the strategy (Jofre, 2011). In large organisation operational level strategy commonly organised according to the major functional department such as finance, research and development, human resources, operational, commercial and marketing. In the operational level, there is coordination and alignment of the decision-making process, communication and control system of all function or operation within an organisation (Wit and Meyer, 2014). Operational strategy at this level defines the balance between available and needed resources

and capabilities determine for example the strategic choice for outsourcing activities (James, 2011).

Strategies are often formed as a set of alternatives and while choosing strategy organisation consider both expectations and facts about the internal environment, external environment, competitive environment and position of the organisation (Jofre, 2011). A strategy should be simple, easy to implement and evaluate and should not conflict with the mission and goals of the organisation. A strategy should be able to solve the issue of organisation permanently; however, if it solves or not, it should not create any issue with the implementation of the strategy. The strategy formulation happens in three levels in any large organisation. It is vital to link all those three formulation strategies together (Cooperate, Business, and Operational) for successful implementation of business strategy. All these three strategies need to be aligned with each other. The demands of integrating level define an important characteristic of strategy (Wit and Meyer, 2014). This research is focused on the analysis of strategic challenges and position of NAC, therefore the process of strategic analysis and strategic analysis tools are presented below.

2.4. Strategic Analysis of an Organisation

The purpose of strategic analysis is to gather information about the organisation as without sufficient and relevant information it is difficult to formulate and implement the strategy (Campbell et al., 2002). Strategic analysis is the vital advance work that should be done properly to effectively formulate and implement strategies. Strategies mainly fail due formulating and implementing strategies without proper analysis of the internal and external environment, lack of careful analysis of its goals and lack of careful analysis of its competitive market (Candido and Santos, 2019). Strategic analysis is the process of understanding and investigating the current situation of the organisation (Fleisher and Bensoussan, 2003). The main purpose of strategic analysis is to do environmental scan both internal and external of the organisation and understand the competitive environment of the organisation (CIMA, 2007).

Strategic analysis requires the use of analytical tools to rationalise the complexities of the interaction between the internal environment and external environment (Grant, 2008). There are various tools that can be used to analyze the organisation internal, external and competitive environment (Ramanujam et al., 1986). The tools that can be used to analyse the internal environment and external environment are resource base view, value chain analysis, PESTEL,

SWOT, Five forces (CIMA, 2007). The external environment is classified into two categories: micro and macro – also known as the general environment and competitive environment respectively (Henry, 2008). The general environment analytical tool is PESTEL, whereas competitive environment can be analysed with five forces.

The analysis of the general environment takes into account the changes that happen outside the organisation that will have an impact on an organisation. Whereas, the competitive analysis looks especially to its competitors on the industry and how they might impact the organisation (Gunn and Williams, 2007). The analytical tools to analyze the internal environment of the organisation are resource base view, value chain analysis. Similarly, another analytical tool SWOT is used for analysing both the internal and external environment where strength and weakness are internal and opportunity and threat are external (Oxford University, 2007). The main attributes of business environment analysis are to identify and evaluate relevant data for strategy formulation, to analysis internal and external environment and employee range of analytical methods in the analysis (CIMA, 2007).

The business environment is classified into two environments: internal and external environment. The internal environment is relevant within the organisation and investigates the resources and capabilities that will help to create or identify sustainable competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). The analytical tools that can be used to analyse the internal environment are resource base and value chain analysis. The external environment of the organisation is divided into two categories: general environment - which is also known as the macro-environment and competitive environment - which is known as the micro-environment (Henry, 2008). The analytical tool used to analyse the general environment is PESTEL whereas the competitive environment is analysed by Five forces. Similarly, another analytical tool SWOT analyses the strength and weakness which is internal and opportunities and threat which is external (Oxford University, 2007).

This study will strategically analysis the airline industry as a whole. Firstly, the external environment of the airline industry where the general environment will be analysed through PESTLE. Secondly, it will then use SWOT to analyse strength and weakness which are internal and opportunities and threats which are external factors of the airline industry.

2.4.1. Analysis of the external environment

The external macro factors are beyond the control of an organisation that influence organizational decision making, affects its performance and strategies however it might not directly influence it (Franke and John, 2011). PESTLE is a strategic business analytical tool that helps to understand the external influence on the organisation (Rastogi and Trivedi, 2016). Airlines industry is impacted by several macro factors to a greater extent than most of the other industries (Heracleous et al., 2009). Furthermore, Sze et al. (2015) argue that understanding the macro environment is vital to the survival of airline companies as it impacts on airlines performance.

2.4.1.1. PESTLE Analysis

PESTLE is a strategic analytical tool that helps to evaluate the impact of Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, and Environmental factors. Below each factor is discussed.

- **Political**

Political factors can have a direct and huge impact on airlines industry even though political factors general vary within different nations. Various political factors such as security threat, strict visa policy, border control, and so on have impacts on Air travels (IATA, 2011). Political influences in making the free market to competitors in the aviation industry in the last few decades have opened up the market to competitors in the aviation industry in the past few decades (Freathy, 2004). Airlines industry has always been affected by political influences in various ways like in term of operation, ownership and in fact, there are still many airlines in the world that are partly or fully owned by the state (Mhlanga and Steyn, 2017).

Government around the world has understood the importance of airlines industry that has on economic growth so has many governments have invested heavily airlines and expanding and building new airports (Bastola, 2017). There are various political factors that affect the airline industry such as trade protection and open borders, geopolitical instability, corruption, the strength of governance, anti-corruption decisions, shifting border boundaries and sovereignty, government ownership of airspace and critical infrastructure (Rivers, 2015)

The various political interventions that may enhance or hinder the operation of air transport are the political factors that affect airlines transportation (Heracleous et al., 2009). Political

factors have a momentous impact on the operating business environment of airlines industry (Barrett, 2006; Doganis, 2001; Taneja, 2010; Shepherd, 2012) and some particular market are regulated by the political atmosphere (Pratap, 2016). According to Doganis (2001) due to political interference state airlines tend to be characterised by elements of over politicisations, substantial losses, lack of clear development strategy, bureaucratic management and overstaffing. Similarly, Mananavire (2016) agrees that political interference has a significant impact on the performance of the airline industry.

- **Economic**

Economic factors influence the airline industry and vice versa (IATA, 2016). Political factors influences in the way firm want to invest and economic factors in the region are directly related to the amount of the demand the firm can expect to face and how well the firm can expect to during specific time period (Grant, 2008). There are various economic factors that would impact the airline industry like unemployment, economic growth business cycles, inflation, interest rates, money supplies, disposable income, business cycles (Johnson, 1999). Economic factors play an important role in the airline industry where it important influences. Airline companies have seen several ups and downs in recent years like the recession in 2009 where poor performing airlines went busted and saw a rise in low budget airlines (Pratap, 2016).

According to Davis (2013), the airline industry is subject to changes in the world economy as it is not immune to economic pressures like unemployment, inflation, interest rate, disposable income and has to adjust time to time as per changing economic conditions (Demydyuk, 2011; Cederholm, 2014; McCann, 2015). The airline industry is contributing to the economic growth of the globe by enabling the flow of the goods, people, capital, technology, ideas and falling transport cost (IATA, 2016).

According to IATA (2017) the potential economic factors that can have an impact on the airline industry are global income inequality, strength and volatility of the global economy, price of oil, level of integration along air industry supply chain, shift to a knowledge-based economy, privatization of infrastructure, the concentration of wealth into a "barbell economy", unionization of labour and regional independence, open data and radical transparency, changing nature of work and competition for talent. Economic factors have a major influence in the airline industry and vice versa (IATA, 2016; Pratap, 2016). Economic factor in the region

is directly related to the amount of the demand the organisation can expect to face and how well the organisation can expect to do during a specific time period (Grant, 2002).

- **Social**

Social factors are those factors that included demographic and changing in cultures (Johnson et al., 2015). The culture of going holidays has increase around the world where more and more people are using airlines to travel. Tourism has become more diverse and large customer market (Shankman, 2014). Globalisation and various social factors like attitude, belief and values have helped to increase the number of people using the airline industry. Low budget airlines have changed the perception of the people and have made accessible to larger public around the globe where airlines were seen as an expensive cost and not available for low and middle-class earners.

According to IATA (2017), list of potential social factors that will have an impact or change the airline industry includes terrorism, urbanization and the growth of megacities, passenger identity and fraud, ageing global population, growth of middle-income population in China and the Asia Pacific region, new modes of consumption, tensions between data privacy and surveillance, global population growth is driven by Asia and Africa, shifting ethnic, political and religious identity, disability, fitness, and health.

Airlines create social value as any other business does that points out social factors affect the attitude of consumers towards air transport (Pratap, 2016) which explains relationship relationships between society and the industry (Chandrappa, 2014; Heracleous et al., 2009). Social factors are those factors that will have an impact or change in airlines industries included demographic and changing in cultures (Johnson et al., 2015; IATA, 2017). The culture of going holidays has increase around the world where more and more people are using airlines to travel and tourism has become more diverse and large customer market (Shankman, 2014).

- **Technological**

Technological factors are one of the pivotal factors that has been shaping the economy and the environment that firms are operating. Development in various technological factor has led to old technology being replaced with new ones and making technological environment highly dynamic that ultimately creates new market and opportunities (Kotler and Armstrong, 2005).

Technological factors are also used to create a competitive advantage for various organisation. A technological breakthrough in the various field will provide opportunities as well as brings a threat to the existing organisation (Thompson and Martin, 2010).

Technological plays a pivotal role in the airline industry. Technology has been important in various aspects of the airline industry in terms of safety, speed and convenience. For example, airlines status can be tracked online nowadays, booking online tickets and even air traffic are managed. The incremental and radical change in technology has helped the airline industry as well as it faces the dilemma of change that is required in various aspects of the airline industry. There are various examples of technological development that has disrupted the industry like the takeaway industry had been disrupted by just eat, the traditional taxi industry has been disrupted by various application and online-based taxi services.

According to IATA(2017), the potential technological factors that will have an impact on airlines industry are cybersecurity expanding human potential, robotics and automation, 3D printing and new manufacturing techniques, virtual and augmented reality, internet of things, alternative fuels and energy sources, new aircraft designs, alternative modes of rapid transit and geospatial technology. Technology in aviation industry means speed, convenience, safety and the importance of trichology could be understood from substantial use of technology in the aviation industry (Porter and Kramer, 2011).

The role of technology is crucial in the airline industry whether it is on passenger safety, modern aircraft, air traffics, online payments, and online booking system (Truxal, 2013). Technology enables airlines prompt access to customers to book tickets online, online check-in system saving the cost of airlines companies (Hartman and Boscoianu, 2015). Technology has the ability to reach a large number of customers (Porter and Kramer, 2015) that provides competitive advantages in this highly turbulent industry (Davies, 2013). It also helps airlines in the wide dissemination of advertisement (Georgieva, 2016) however airlines company that is statured with technology struggles for a competitive advantage over its competitors.

- **Legal**

Legal factors are those factors that are related to the legal environment in which industries and individual firms have to operate. There are various factors like conventions, legislation, agreements in which all organisations operate (Grant, 2008). The various types of legislation

in which firm operates have an impact on firms strategies that can make one strategy more effective and can make other strategies less effective. There are various types of legislation that has an impact on the strategies of the organisation for examples in the UK are anti-age discrimination laws, minimum wages, corporate social responsibility, are the few examples that affect strategies and activities of the organisation (Arnold and Reynolds, 2003). The main aim of such legislation of legal factors is to make fairer competition and make the organisations operate under social benefits rather than just originations gain.

There are various organisation and agreements in the aviation industry that governs and advocates the aviation industry. The organisation like the International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO), Civil Aeronautics Board, International Air transportation (IATA) are some of those organisation that monitors, advocates and regulates airlines industry. Legal factors significantly impact the performance of the airline industry (Roche, 2011; Mulder, 2011) where air transport is regulated by several laws and regulations (Georigieva, 2016).

Legal factors are those factors that are related with the legal environment in which industries and individual firms have to operate and there various factors like conventions, legislation, and agreements in which all organisations operate (Grant, 2008). There are various types of legislation that has an impact on the organisation for example minimum wages, corporate social responsibility, are the few examples that affect strategies and activities of the organisation (Arnold and Reynolds, 2003). There are various organisations that monitor, advocate and regulate airline industry; for instance, the International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO), Civil Aeronautics Board, International Air transportation association (IATA).

- **Environmental**

Environmental factors are those factors that are related to environmental issues like pollution, waste, recycling and climate change. Environmental factors can add additional cost to the organisation or firm but it even might provide an opportunity for new business like electric cars (Tesla), recycling phone business. Environmental factors have been the most important issues in today's world where people do not just want basic requirement of life rather they desire to achieve the highest standard of living and quality of life. People around the world have a major concern of environmental issues like pollution, waste, recycling, climate change and worry about natural resources are growing (Upham, 2003). Thus, this kind of concern about environmental issues has forced the organisation and government to have environmental

laws, co-operate social responsibility and be more environmental focus rather than just profit-making organisation or firm.

Airlines industry does contribute to climate change and global dimming (Forsyth, 2011) due to the heat, noise particular and gases being eliminated from aircraft. Not, only aircraft but other forms of transportation that uses fuel does contribute to climate change (Cederholm, 2014). The carbon footprint of airlines which is estimated by some researcher to be one of the most dramatic impacts on global warming with a total contribution of approximately 6% of greenhouse gases to the atmosphere (Bakic, 2008). Such environmental factors are driving changes in the airline industry (Delfmann et al., 2005). Such environmental factors are driving changes in the airline industry. The rapid growth in the airline industry in recent years have contributed to the increase in pollution despite emission reduction and more fuel-efficient aircrafts production (Anderson and Bows, 2008)

However, PESTEL, like any other business tool, also has limitations and implementing this tools requires deeper consideration for each of the factors as it may change suddenly and are usually unpredictable (Henry, 2008). Collecting relevant data from the enormous data that has been collected from the external environment can be costly and time-consuming. As there are an enormous amount of data that will be collected from PESTLE analysis so there is a chance of losing sight on critical aspects. Even though it is a great business tool that is widely used to analyse macro-environment (Oxford University, 2007).

2.4.1.2. Potters five forces

According to Porter (1980, p35), the involvement of suppliers, competitors, customers, substitutes and new entrants affects the operations of the organisation. It is vital to understand the competitive pressure to determine the industry attractiveness (Thompson and Martin, 2005). Porters (1980) argues that state of the competition of the industry depends upon the five competitive forces and they are bargaining power of customer, bargaining power of supplier. Analysing all the five forces of porters it helps the organisation to gain insight and complete picture of what influences the profitability of the organisation, changing trends and would help to exploit them. Various authors (Barney, 1997; Oster, 1994; Wharton School, 1997; Grant, 2008; McGahan, 2004) have assessed that five forces model is a vital and the most influential tool in analysing the competitive environment.

Porter's five forces provide practical guidance with a framework that helps to understand a deeper view of its implication in strategy today (Porter, 2008). Porter's five forces help strategists to understand and cope with its competitors. It helps to analyse the organisation underlying structure in the term of five forces. It helps to analyse competitive forces of organisation, underlying causes and reveals the roots of industry's current profitability while providing a framework for anticipating and influencing over a period of time (Kotler and Armstrong, 2006). The framework suggests that the higher the strength of each forces the lower possibility of the profit (Demydyuk, 2011)

It is vital for an organisation to understand its competitive concern to a strategy that defines the company's position. It is equally important to understand industry structure that will help to have essential to an effective strategic position. Analysis organisation through porter's five forces helps to understand organisation structure, competitive forces and helps to build a strategy to an organisation that helps the organisation to be competitive in the market (Thompson and Martin, 2005). It is also vital for an organisation to understand, research, watch its established rivals and it is equally important to scan its competitive environment as well as watch beyond its direct rivals. Therefore, this strategic analytical tool proves to vital tool for analysis operating environment of airlines industry.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Porter, M.E. (1980) *Competitive Strategy: Techniques for Analysing Industries and Competitors*. New York; London: Free Press; Collier Macmillan.

FIGURE 2-3: POTTER'S FIVE FORCES

Source: Porter (1980)

- **Rivalry among existing competitors**

Porter (1980) argues that as any industry seeks to improve its position and financial performance are likely to increase their rivalry. In some industries, most of the market share is covered by few big businesses in which rest of the small business act like followers to them however if there are many equally balanced organisation in the same industry with almost same resources, it is argued the rivalry is intense (Bitelmal, 2010). In the case of the airline industry, the deregulation and budget airlines have led to price war increasing the rivalry among existing competitors (Moiseiwitsch, 2014). The rivalry within the existing competitors significantly impacts the performance of the airline industry (Stonehouse and Campbell, 2004; Thompson and Martin, 2005). Therefore, the rivalry is high among the existing competitors in the airline industry.

- **Threat of Entry**

There is always threat in any organisation the differences is it might be high on some and low on some. The new entry in any industry brings new capacity, desire to gain market share that puts pressure on the prices and market (Porter, 1980). Any industry that is more accessible and profitable is likely to attract more competitors, new entrants that would lead to the intense level of competition (Wharton school, 1997) which would lead forcing the price down with declining profit. The threat level of entry in any industry depends on entry barrier where in some industry the capital costs are high, maintenance costs are high that would discourage any potential entrants and lower the profit prospect (Bitelmal, 2010).

In the context of the airline industry, the threat of entry is low as it is mainly due to the huge capital requirement (Rahman et al., 2015; Bryson, 2012). The airline industry is already saturated and one of the most expensive industry to operate that requires skilled human resources, technical knowhow and companies can gain from economies of scales so operating on a large level is considered as profitable (Pratap, 2018). It will be difficult for new entrants to compete with existing established airlines companies (Hitt et al., 2010).

- **Pressure from Substitutes**

Porter's (1980) identifies that if a product and services can be replaced by another product and services from a different industry it is known as substitutes. For example, high-speed trains are

substitutes for the airline industry. Porter's (1980) argues that some of the substitute's product and services are competitors as they impact the profitability of the industry. The way to identify substitute's products and services as competitors is by examining and analysis if the substitutes function in the same way. According to Wharton school (1997), there are two ways to view substitutes: one from the demand side in which it looks ways to satisfy the customer and another from the supply side with the ability to serve the customers.

The threat of substitutes is low to rising in the airline industry as it outperforms other industry when it comes to cost and convenient (Walters 2010; Pratap 2018). Similarly, Clark (2011) agrees that the airline industry does have competitive advantages of cost and convenient from its substitutes. However, the airline industry does have exit barriers and it does have various direct and indirect rivals or substitutes. For example, high-speed trains are the substitutes for short airlines journey only.

- **Bargaining Power of the Buyers**

Buyers can be an individual or company that purchase a product and services from seller firm in the market. Powerful suppliers have much more power in the market where they can influence the price as well as the quality level (Oster, 1994). In the airline industry, the bargaining power of customers is high. Customers are price-sensitive when it comes to travel as it is a meaningful share of discretising spending (IATA, 2013). There is low or no switching cost at all that gives the buyers more power to switch airlines anytime. The advancement of technology has given the power to buyers as they can buy tickets online or through intermediates which has the option of various airlines companies, no switching cost, therefore, do not have to stick with one airline (Rahman et al., 2015; Pratap, 2018)

- **Bargaining Power of the Suppliers**

Suppliers are all those companies that provide components parts to firm and may possess significant power if those parts are final products and if there are few to produce them (Porter 1980; Flouris and Oswald, 2006). Suppliers can be powerful when resources of the substitutes are low and if they have unique resources. In the airline industry, the bargaining power of supplier is high (IATA, 2013).

There is a limited and very small number of specialising firms that provide airport services like handling, cleaning, catering which do not provide various options to airlines industry. The company that makes both aircraft and engine are concentrated oligopolies. In most of the airports, the airline industry does have powerful labour which controls the operational network. There are also various airports around the world that are local monopolies with significant power. The demand for aircraft is very high as there are lots of airlines companies however there is only two main aircraft manufactures Airbus and Boeing that makes the power of supplier high (Rahman et al., 2015)

Porter five force is considered as one of the most powerful and useful tools analysis competitive environment; however, it does have some weakness and limitations. Porter five forces do not take consideration of various factors like technological change, government and regulatory intervention and volatility in market demand (Wharton, 1997; Grant 2008; Oster 1984).

2.4.1.3. Analysis of Opportunities and Threats

SWOT analysis is a strategic analytical tool that is used to analyse the internal and external environment of an organisation. It is a simple, effective and powerful tool for sizing up an organisation resources capabilities and its deficiencies, market opportunities and external threats (Thompson et al., 2017). SWOT analysis has four components namely strength, weakness, opportunities and threat. Strength and weakness are internal organisation factors whereas opportunities and threat are external environmental factors. SWOT analytical tool is a significant tool that is used to evaluation of organisation plan, business activity, and business project and strategy formulation. Below, discussions on the external factors are made.

- **Opportunities**

Opportunity is an external environmental factor that helps an organisation take advantage of its strength to overcome or neutralise weakness and threats (Harrison and St. John, 2004). Opportunity is a convenient situation of time that helps the organisation to achieve its goals. Few examples of opportunities in airlines industry are the use of technology, market expansion, better customer and supplier relationship.

- **Threats**

Threats are the external environmental factors of an organisation that make it impossible or difficult to reach organisational goals. The changes that happen in an environment bring threats to an organisation that might bring difficulties for an organisation in maintaining its existing advantages over its competitors. The threats of the airline industry are customer trust, quality service and negative image of reliability and punctuality (Gaibre and Shakya, 2017). The price of jet fuel is also one of the threats of the airline industry (Prasain, 2019). The threats of the airline industry are unstable government, increasing operational costs, growing competitions and lower profitability (Yadav, 2016).

According to Feurer and Chaharbaghi (1995), strategies of an organisation can be defined by the strength and weakness of the organisation. Similarly, Johnson et al. (2005) agree that strategic capabilities of the organisation depend upon the strength and weakness of the organisation and if the strength is superior to its competitors it can become a competitive advantage. Airlines can use strategy to take advantage of opportunities to avoid threats and at the same time can use opportunities to minimize weakness (O'Connell, 2007).

2.4.2. Analysis of the Internal Environment

2.4.2.1. *Analysis of Strengths and Weaknesses*

This section now discusses the internal factors of SWOT, namely strengths and weaknesses.

- **Strengths**

Strength of an organisation is known when the internal analysis of the organisation is carried out and in the organisational level is refer to favourable, positive and creative physiognomies that involve resources and capabilities in which organisation can gain the advantage over its competitors (Thompson and Strickland, 1989). Strength is something that gives organisation competitive advantage over its competitors and strength may exist in various aspects such as market leader, financial resources, buyer and supplier relationship (Pearce and Robinson, 1991). According to Flouris and Oswald (2006), the source of strength in the airline industry is strong financial positions, employee, brand loyalty, quality products, international operations, good operating procedure, strong promotion practices, strong brand name, strong knowledgeable management and suppliers and customer relationship.

- **Weaknesses**

Weakness is an internal aspect of the organisation that refers to incompetent resources and capabilities of an organisation comparing its competitors. It means that an organisation is less effective and efficient compared to its competitors (Thompson and Strickland, 1989). Weakness in an organisation means resources and capabilities are limited or deficiency that impacts the efficiency and effectiveness of the organisation (Pearce and Robinson, 1991). An organisation must know and understand its weakness in order to improve efficiency and effectiveness. The weaknesses of the airline industry are lack of new advance technology, no strategic direction, high inventory cost, old resources, lack of leadership and vision, no product recognition and lack of research and development (Flouris and Oswald,2006).

2.4.2.2. *The Resource-Based View*

An organisation needs resources to carry out activities and produce goods and services. An organisation resourced based are all those activities that add value to the organisation. Some authors prefer the term “assets” to emphasise that the resources belong to the firm (Itami, 1987; Dierickx and cool, 1989). There is various research done under the resource-based view of the firm that has shown the importance of resource for success and even the existence of the organisation (Wernerflet, 1984; Penrose 1959; Barney 1991). There is no one general established classification of organisation resources that has yet emerged in the field of strategic management.

According to Barney (1997) firms resources can be classified into four categories: Financial capital, Human Capital, Physical Capital and Organisational Capital. Grant (2008) argues that resources can be classified into Tangible and Intangible resources, Tangible resources are those resources that are easiest to identify similar to those that have been identified by Barney (1997) as Finical and Physical resources whereas resources such as the firm’s reputation, cultural assets and technology are regarded as intangible (Grant,2008). Intangible resources can be considered as considered more significance than tangible resources mainly because they can be a major source of sustainable competitive advantages (Johnson, 1989; Grant, 2008; Oster, 1994).

Financial Capital is all the money that is required by the airline industry to carry out its strategies (Barney, 1997). Financial capital can come from entrepreneur, equity holder, retained profit, bondholder and banks. There is a huge investment required in Airlines development projects where financing can be seen as an area of concern (Doganis, 1992; Winston, 1991; Wells and young, 2004; Forgyth, 2005; De Nevville and Odani, 2003; Graham, 2003). On the other hand, the physical capital of organisations includes organisational geographical location, plant, technology, raw materials, equipment etc.

Human capital includes experience, training, skills, relationship, intelligence, and employees within an organisation (Barney, 1997). It is vital for an organisation to get its employee to involve in necessary knowledge and training programme and keep them up to date with new information and technology required as it would be decisive in employee effectiveness (Grant, 2008; Barney, 1997). An organisation should rely on its employee attributes, motivation, potential and learning capacity rather than qualification and experiences. Various research in the area of strategic management has concluded that organisational leader and managers do have a direct and great impact on the firm's internal performance (Barney, 1997).

- **Conducting a Resource-Based View Analysis**

Resources that have been discussed above may be shared common on other firms of the industry so the resource-based view theory requires to fulfil four requirements form the source of sustainable competitive advantage, it must be valuable, Rare, Inimitable and organised (VIRO) (Barney and Clark, 2007; Barney 1997) that ultimately impact the performance of an organisation (Peteraf, 1993). The VIRO framework is structured in a series of four questions to examine whether resources meet the four categories of competitive advantage. The structured series of four questions, as highlighted by Barney (1997), are presented below:

- a. Valuable: Do resources and capabilities increase the value offer o customer and enable the firm to respond to environmental threat and opportunities?
- b. Rare: How many other organisation possess similar resources and capabilities?
- c. Inimitable: Do organisation without resources and capacity face a cost disadvantage in obtaining it compared to the firm that possesses already?
- d. Organisation: Is the organisation capable to exploit and maximize the valuable, rare, inimitable and organised resources to achieve sustainable competitive advantage?

If an organisation has the ability to leverage the resources into competitive advantage than it refers as value for the organisation (Fahy, 2001). Resources are 'Valuable' when it creates value for the organisation and customer that could be done by increasing differentiation or decreasing the cost of production. The resources can also be considered as valuable if it helps the organisation to exploit an opportunity and meet external threat (Barney and Clark, 2007).

The second characteristic of VRIO resource-based view is 'Rare'. It means that valuable resources are not widely obtained by other competitors. The resources that are only acquired by few firms can be referred to as rare. If resources are common that is widely acquired by many organisation it is highly unlikely that it would be the source of any competitive advantage (Barney and Clark, 2007).

The third characteristic that firms could find the source of competitive advantage is 'Imitability'. Value and Rare resources cannot only be a source of a competitive advantage unless it is inimitable (Barney and Clark, 2007). If resources are easily replaceable or subsisted than it cannot be a source of competitive advantage. Intangible resources such as culture, reputation, and Brand Image are a few examples of resources that are hard to imitate so they are inimitable.

The last characteristic of VRIO resources based view is 'Organised'. Value, Rare and inimitable can be a source of competitive advantage if the firm is organised to exploit their potential (Barney and Clark, 2007). An organisation should organise its process, management systems, policies, culture and organisational structure to fulfil realize the potential of all its resources and capabilities the only it can achieve suitable competitive advantage.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Barney, J. (1997) *Gaining and sustaining competitive Advantages*. Reading Mass: Addison Wesley Pub.co

FIGURE 2-4: THE VRIO FRAMEWORK

Source: Barney (1997)

The biggest limitation of the resources based analysis is that it fails to address the unpredictability change that suddenly occurs in the external environment which could change the value of resources making competitive advantage less sustainable (Barney, 1997).

2.4.2.3. Value Chain Analysis

A value chain is an integrated set of value creation process leading to the supply of product or services. An organisation needs value chain in place to be able to actually sale what it wants to produce or provide and it is vital whether it is supplying or producing. All these value-adding activities need to link together and coordinated, this business model is referred to as “Value Chain” (Porter, 1985). Value chain analysis helps organisations to understand which activity helps an organisation create value that would ultimately be organisation competitive advantage. Value chain differs from organisation to organisation even though it might be in the same industry. For example; McDonalds and Burger King might employ the same value chain model but their value-adding activity would differ.

An organisation having a distinct value chain often provide a basis for competitive advantage. It helps the organisation to do things better, cheaper, faster, nicer or more tailored than its competitors that would ultimately help to offer its customer a unique value proposition (Wit

and Meyer, 2015). Developing value chain is strategically important as developing new products or services. Even though value chain can differ quite significantly but there are some attempts made to develop a general taxonomy of value-adding activity that could be used as an analytical framework (Norman and Ramirez, 1993; Day, 1990). Porter's value chain model is by far the most influential framework (Wit and Meyer, 2015) which distinguishes primary and supporting activities of the organisation.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Porter, M.E. (1985) *Competitive Advantage: Creating and sustaining superior performance*. New York: The Free press

FIGURE 2-5: THE GENERIC VALUE CHAIN

Source: Porter (1985)

Primary activities are directly apprehensive with the creation or delivery of a product or service. Whereas, supporting activities facilitates the primary activities that would help to improve the efficiency or effectiveness of primary activities. The generic category of primary activities as identified and describe by porter (1985) are:

- **Inbound logistics:** These are the activities that are associated with receiving, storing, and distributing inputs including material handling, inventory control, warehousing, vehicle scheduling and return to suppliers.

- **Operations:** These are those activities that transform input into final products including machining, packing, equipment maintenance, assembling, testing printing and facility operation.
- **Outbound Logistics:** These are the activity that is associated with collect, store, material handling and distribution of the product and selling to a customer of the buyers.
- **Marketing and sales:** These are the activities that help customer or buyer aware of where the product and service could be purchases including advertising, pricing, salesforce, promotion, quoting, channel selections, channel relations,
- **Services:** Activity that is associated to maintain or enhance the value of products and services such as installation, training, repair, product adjustment and part supply.

Porter (1985) urges that for service industry the specific activities might be different but still can be divided into these five categories. In order to carry out primary activities effectively or efficiently supporting activities are required.

- **Procurement:** Activities that are associated with the purchasing of inputs to facilitate all other activities including vendor selection, negotiating, and contracts.
- **Technology Development:** All the value activities of the organisation have technology involved in various value activities such as product development, product design, and raw material improvement.
- **Human resource management:** Activities that are associated with the management of the personal organisation including recruitments, rewards, development, training and management within an organisation.
- **Infrastructure:** It consists of all the activity that supports the entire value chain including planning, Finance, accounts, legal, government affairs and quality management.

Few Specialise value activities will not be a source of uniqueness of the value chain neither it would be the source of competitive advantage rather extraordinary configuration of the entire value chain. An extraordinary configuration multiple the distinctness of a particular value chain, while often raising the barrier to imitation (Porter 1996, Amt and Zatt, 2014). Potter (1985) argues that primary and supporting activities do have three types of activities direct, indirect and quality assurance that plays a different role on competitive advantage. Direct

activities involve creating value for the customer, the indirect activity allows direct activity to take place and quality assurance ensures the quality of other activity is asserted.

In an attempt to apply the concept of value chain analysis in the airline industry, Tretheway and Markvida (2013) suggest that value chain analysis can be divided into two segments: upstream and downstream. In upstream, it consists of aircraft manufacture, aviation infrastructure like airports, aviation communication centre, and Air navigation, service provider, leasing firms, financial capital source, fuelling firms, catering, ground services and insurance providers. On the other hand, downstream activities consist of travel agents, Global distribution system, computerised reservation system, cargo integrators, airlifts with trucks and customer service.

FIGURE 2-6: AIRLINES INDUSTRY VALUE CHAIN

Source: Surenderan (2010)

A limitation of value chain analysis is the availability of data such as a change in cost structure, capital investment and market price may not be available for long term strategic plan. The value chain has also been criticised for not adequately capturing the value creation logic of service industry (Stabell and Fjeldstad, 1998) where it isolates customer from operation process

that would not be applicable in the service industry like banking, hospitals, telecommunications (Gabriel, 2006).

2.4.3. Implementation of Business strategies

There are three steps in the strategy process where it starts with environmental appraisals, formulation of strategy and implementation of the strategy (Jofre, 2011). In environmental appraisal, it involves internal and external environmental analysis. The internal analysis includes the evaluation of organisation goals, mission and objectives of the organisation whereas the external environment includes the analysis of the general and competitive environment. Similarly, the second step of the strategy process is strategy formulation where it is formulated in three different levels cooperate, business and functional level (Wit and Meyer, 2014). Cooperate level is the highest level of strategy formulation on an organisation where the strategy is formed for direction, position and organisation in the long term. The common examples in this level are vertical integration, horizontal integration and alliance and collaboration (Wit and Meyer, 2014).

Similarly, the formulation of business-level strategies main objectives is to develop and sustain competitiveness in all the lines of business that the organisation has participated. The organisation formulate strategy in this level through positioning, resource-based view and value chain analysis (Grant 2008b; Barney et al., 2001). Finally, functional level strategies are formulated to focus on short term activities and to support and implement cooperate and business level strategies. The formulation of these types of strategies are organised across the major departments of the organisation with the coordination, alignment, communication in the decision-making process (Jofre, 2011). Strategies are often formulated as a set of alternative therefore formulation process rarely concludes with one strategy. The last and final stage of the strategy process is strategy implantation.

At the end of the formulation stage, the organisation decided which strategy fits the organisation and the execution of strategy in the organisation is implementation (Jofre, 2011). Implementation of the strategy is determents of success and failure of the organisation that is extremely apprehension with the formulation, function and structure of the organisation. However, despite such importance implementation is least studied and documented stage in the strategy process (Hitt et al., 2006). The formulation and implementation, in general, are

placed in the same level of strategy process as if it is a continuous process while evidence and logic suggest that although it is highly entangled they are two very different phases.

According to Paul Stonich (1982), strategy formulation and strategy implantation are distinguished by suggesting formulation is about where the organisation is today and where it should be tomorrow whereas implantation is about how to get the company from where it is today to where it should be tomorrow. According to Eccles (1994), strategy implementation is the action or intentions that help to move an organisation along with the route of its goal, fulfilling its mission and helps to achieve its vision. The implementation of strategy incisions through various fields of social science including organisational theory, organisational development and strategic management however they all do not agree (Jofre, 2011). There are nine key strategy implementation models and all of them have their own functions, advantages and disadvantages (BAM, 2013). An empirical study was done on the nine different strategy implementation model with considering three criteria, model's components, research design and validity/ reliability and found Inverted Pyramid framework by MacLennan (2011) and Kaplan and Norton (2008) appropriate model compare to rest of the models (BAM,2013).

Andrew MacLennan (2011) is the most recent model for strategy implantation that is based on longitudinal case studies of two organisation therefore the research has embedded limitations in external validity. MacLennan's Inverted Pyramid framework (2011) findings are much more limited comparing Kaplan and Norton's research (2008) findings that have utilised a group of 12 companies but it is more reliable due to employing longitudinal case study instead of the focus group. MacLennan (2011) model consist of thirteen tasks that are divided into two-phase which is a step by step process with a logically sequent set of task. Phase 1 of MacLennan (2011) comprises three tasks (overall objective, strategic choices, and critical activities), would transform the organisation's general objectives into sequences of activities. Phase 2 of MacLennan (2011) comprises of ten tasks (processes, projects, resource allocation, organisation structure, interface management, roles & responsibilities, performance criteria, capacity, commitment, and capability), would build an alliance among organisational strategies and obtainable systems (MacLennan, 2011, pp. 59-65).

According to MacLennan (2011, p. 58) sequence of the tasks for managers follow: set general objectives; creating strategic variations to support the achievement of the objectives; describing critical activities by breaking down the strategic choices; separating temporary critical activities (projects) from continuous ones (processes); designing an appropriate organisation

structure; allocating resources to the projects and processes; managing interfaces between SBUs; assigning roles and responsibilities; defining performance criteria; creating required commitment, capacity and capability; detecting possible strategic risks as well as performance measures; and finally conducting internal and external environmental analysis that MacLennan put it as the last task but it should be done as the very first activity (Alexander, 1985; Herold, 1972). This research focus on the aviation industry and the strategic analysis will be done in the context of the airline industry.

2.5. The Global Airline Industry

2.5.1. Introduction/ landscape

The global airline industry has played a vital role in the development of global economy and serving virtually every county in the world. The airline industry has major contributions in the economic aspects both from its own operations and related industries. In 1950, the growth of the global airline industry enable by major technological innovation and development of wide-body aircraft in 1970 (Belobaba et al., 2009). After deregulation, the airline industry is facing various major issues around the globe with cost efficiency, operating profitability, competition and competitive behaviour (Oum et al., 2010). However, increased competition after deregulation forced airlines companies to restlessly improve their productive efficiency and optimize their network and pricing strategy (Fethi et al., 2000). The airline companies that were less efficient were either bankrupts or merged with new business models and innovation evolving (Button 1998; InterVISTAS, 2006).

The growth of the airline industry around the globe is expected to be 5 per cent approximately every year until 2038 with the current condition (ATAG, 2008). In 2008, the global airline industry consists of 2000 airlines operating with 23,000 commercial aircrafts providing service to 3700 airports around the world (ATAG 2008; IATA 2008). According to IATA (2019), the global passenger is expected to rise from 4.34 billion in 2018 to 4.59 billion in 2019. In 2017, air transport was the major employer around the world with 65.5 million jobs globally with a contribution to production, encourage investment and innovation (ATAG, 2018). The global airline industry operates in a highly turbulent environment where supply and demand side has gone through some drastic change (Keynes, 2009). The airline industry operates in a complex

business environment where it is subject to the rapid change from competitors, suppliers, customer expectations and government regulation. (Bissessor and Alamdari, 1998).

2.5.2. Key Players

According to IATA (2019), the top five airlines in 2019 in the world by total scheduled passenger's kilometre flown are mention in the table below. The biggest and successful airlines companies have tailor-made structure, proper business plan, investment in technological advancement and collaboration with airlines companies (Verbouska, 2018). The vital focus of successful airlines companies is to maintain a young fleet, improve customer experience and have well-defined price targeting strategy.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at IATA (31 July, 2019) *More connectivity improved efficiency 2018 airlines industry statistics released*

Source: IATA (2019)

2.5.3. Challenges Faced by the Airline Industry

The global aviation industry faces various challenges that directly affect the operation of the airline industry (Belobaba et al., 2015). Due to deregulation, there is huge competition in the airline industry and airline companies have to focus on cooperating strategies so that airlines companies can have long term sustainability (Borenstein and Rose, 2014). The airline industry operates in a global environment where a multitude of exogenous factors are colliding at once presents numerous challenges like geopolitical threats, the rising interest rates, the rise in oil price and increasing labour costs (KPMG, 2019).

The airline industry is vulnerable to external factors such as political, economic as for commercial aviation sector political stability and sustainable economic growth are vital for

sustainable growth of the airline industry. The supply chain is another challenge that aviation industry is facing due to limited manufacturer of aircraft with record new number of aircrafts delivery where it will be extremely difficult ensure timely delivery while maintaining high quality whilst keeping the costs controlled. The airline industry has seen various changes in last 20 years with the rise in low budget airlines, challenges faced by the outbreak of disease or pandemic, geopolitical situation, evolving technology and airlines industry expects more turbulence in future (Future of the airline industry, 2017; Zhang, 2017).

The fast-changing needs of the customer requirements and high customer expectation is also one of the challenges faced by the airline industry (Ford and Despeisse, 2016; Abdelghany and Abdelghany, 2016). Jet Fuel is one of the major operational cost in the aviation industry and vacillations in the fuel price have impacted the operational costs of the industry (Bilotkach et al., 2015). The fast-changing needs, requirement and expectations of customers is a challenge that the airline industry is facing at the moment (Ford and Despeisse, 2016). There is continuous growth in airlines companies and aircraft that has increased air traffic, causing an impact on the airline industry (Oster et al., 2013). Deregulation in the airline industry and entry of low budget airlines have increased the level of competition and there is a lack of cultural loyalty and retention in airlines industry (Hu et al., 2013).

The aircraft manufactures like Airbus and Boeing are always dedicated to producing modern aircraft and engine through investment in research and development (Johnson et al., 2008) where airlines companies face challenging needs to upgrade their system that requires huge investment. Airlines industry also faces challenges with its fragile brand reputation where bad reputation and negative publicity can immediately drive down to meltdown (Daramaju et al., 2007). Similarly, the advancement of the internet that allows accessing tickets online and increasing competition has allowed customers to buy tickets at the best price making them powerful (Truxal 2013; Hartman and Boscoianu, 2015; Porter and Kramer, 2015).

Furthermore, a strategic alliance which allows loyalty programmes and code sharing while delivering quality products and services have led to stiff competitions (Byles, 2007). The increasing costs of labour, insurance, fuel and security measures have also increased the operations costs of the airline industry (Keynes, 2009). Therefore, identifying critical success factors of the airline industry is vital to overcome the strategic challenges faced by the industry.

2.5.4. Critical success factors of the Aviation Industry

The critical success factors of any organisation represent as elements of competitive strength in examining the relevant strength of the organisation compare to its competitors. According to Bullen and Rockart (1981), critical success factors depends on the limited number of areas where the satisfactory result will ensure the competitive performance of the organisation and there are few areas where the thing must go right in order to flourish in the market and achieve organisational goals. The critical success factor of the industry lies with an optimum match between environmental conditions and business characteristics.

The business must align its strategy, skills, resources and capabilities with the surrounding environment that possess certain fundamental requirements, limitations threat and opportunities in order to achieve critical success factors (Rockart, 1979). According to Rockart (1979), critical success factors can be distinguished from five sources like the industry, competitive strategy and industry position, environmental factors, Temporal factors and managerial position. Therefore, critical success factors can be both internal and external environmental factors where the organisation might have control over it or do not have control over it and monitor it (Munro and wheeler, 1980; Ferguson and Dickinson, 1982; Boynton and Zmud, 1984).

An organisation must manage several tasks successfully in order to be a successful airline company. Not doing well in one or two or more areas do not mean failure however it appears to make success elusive. According to Richard (2006), the study that was done with eight United States airlines found that airlines must be effective in four general areas namely attracting customers, managing its fleet, managing its people and managing its finance to have successful critical factors for the airline industry. There are numerous strategies implemented by various airlines that will ensure their market position and market share however there are few specific key success factors that will ensure the successfulness of an airline company. The few of key success factors of airlines industry are as follows.

2.5.4.1. *Organisational structure*

The organisational structure has been effective management tools that focus on the relationship that defines the way work is done by clear structuring positioning, authority,

responsibilities, power and communication from human resources. The structure of an organisation is vital to be successful in the service business. The structure of an organisation provides a clear chart that allows organising all the functional units of airlines to operate in one clear chain of command and focus on its strategies building competitive advantage (Byles, 2007). It will be easier for the organisation to pick a tailor-made structure that will fit with organisation operations. The best structure will help to maximize the efficiency of the organisation and break the barriers between hierarchies and people (Harogopal, 2006). The horizontal structure is for value chain process, functional structure focuses on functional excellence and divisional structure focus on market place responsiveness (Spector, 2007). The organisational structure is a key success factor of an airline company as it unifies the organisational structure and how it caters the market.

2.5.4.2. Collaboration with Airlines companies

The airline industry, like any other industry, is always looking ways to expand its market it serves, reduce its costs, improve its revenue, and enhance its customer services and one of the way doing is through collaboration. According to Airline Business magazine survey in 1994, there were 280 strategic alliance where 136 airlines were involved (Burton and Hanlon, 1994) which was an increase by 500 alliance agreements in 2006 involving 120 passenger airlines (Airlines Business, 2006). There are various benefits of collaboration between the airline industry like it allows airlines baggage and passenger between different carrier and connection around any city in the world. The collaborations in the airline industry are marketing agreement and alliance.

- **Marketing Agreement**

Marketing agreement is an independent entity with a marketing alliance and it consists of three types of collaboration in airlines industry namely Interline/Pro rate agreements, pooling agreements and code-sharing agreements. The agreement that is done between airlines concerning sale, endorsement, baggage and acceptance of the tickets so that passengers can transfer from one airline to another to reach passengers final destination is known as interline/pro-rate agreements (Iatrou, 2004). It is further divided into Non-allied interline agreements and allied interline agreements (Ito and Lee, 2004). The connecting ticketing of two airlines that is not part of the alliance is known as non-allied interline agreement whereas

the connecting of ticketing between two airlines that are not part of the alliance is known as allied interline agreements.

Pooling agreements is a unique arrangement between two or more airlines in which they share the cost of operating and the revenue that it generates (Burton and Hanlon, 1994). Pooling agreement is usually conducted between the airlines that operate in the same route where the arrangement is made for similar ticket pricing that reduces the competitions. Pooling agreement is still active in some Asian, African and Middle Eastern airlines company however it has been replaced by code-sharing agreement and block space agreement (Doganis, 2005). Code-sharing is the most common collaboration between airlines industry where airlines permit another airline to use its designator code on a flight or two airlines share designator code (ICAO, 1997). In simple terms, it means the agreement between airlines companies that allows to sell and market their partner's seats as their own seats.

- **Alliances**

The member of strategic alliances shares their activities and resources among them to strengthen the competitive position in the market. According to Oum et al. (1996), the airlines that are not a member of any alliance will be marginalised and develop as a niche player in the local market. Similarly, Li (2000) agrees and argues that airlines that do not belong to any alliance will have severe disadvantages. There are three types of alliances in the airline industry namely strategic alliance, equity partners and airlines franchise.

The share of resources and activities between two or more organisation to pursue strategy is known as a strategic alliance (Johnson et al., 2005). Alliance has been one of the most powerful tools in business in the last 100 years (Pekar, 2003). Strategic alliance and collaboration have also become a way to bypass bilateral convections that prevents them from flying certain countries or owing foreign airlines. Such strategic alliances give flexibility to organisations, unlike merger or acquisition. Flexibility is what required in a turbulent and uncertain market. Collaboration with a number of global partners can dismiss reliance on one particular region. The process of one airline (franchisee) getting the rights of intellectual property, know-how and service which comes with it from another airline (Franchisor) for return of fee is known as airline franchise (Denton and Dennis, 2000). This kind of agreement means that franchisee and franchisor cannot compete head to head and it also generates revenue streams and provides opportunities to be part of big airlines company (Button, 1991; Iatrou, 2004).

2.5.4.3. *Organisational culture*

Culture is fundamental sets of assumptions, value and ways the things are done in an organisation that has been accepted by most of its members (Laudon and Laudon, 2007). The common organisational culture can unify its employee and their actions towards achieving organisational goal. The previous empirical research done in south-west airlines finds that excellent corporate culture motivated employee and cultivated attitude that steered towards teamwork with employee commitment and cost-consciousness translated into operational excellence and growth in profitability (Dess et al., 2008; Daramaju et al., 2007; Bunz and Maes, 1998). The history and culture of an organization may contribute to its strategic capabilities, but may also give rise to strategic implication as its strategy develops incrementally on the basis of influence and failing to keep pace with a changing environment (Johnson et al., 2008).

2.5.4.4. *Planning and Development*

The business environment in which airlines operates is complex and very unstable which is both subjects to emergent and planned change therefore planning is a vital management tool to help forecast and build exigency plans (Golightly, 1967). Olumuyiwa et al., (2012) identifies that effective planning determines the success or otherwise of any organisation and impacts the organisation productivity. Similarly, Ufartiene (2014) stated that planning is related to organisation development and employee development that could help to expand and survive business in a competitive market. An organisation that implement effective research and development practices offers a tremendous advantage for an organisation that questions its process and productivity, encourage organisation flexibility, ability to integrate new concepts and process that will allow organisation adapt itself in an effective way in the environmental changes (Freel, 2000).

2.5.5. Common Strategies Used in the Aviation Industry

Airlines industry was regulated for a long period of time and there was no need to be a concern for competitors neither for strategy (Kangis and O'Reilly, 2003). It was not until the 1970's competition in the airline industry was almost non-existence as the barrier for entry and exit was high and competition almost non- existence. However, that changes quickly when the US

airline deregulation act came in as there were new entrants that change the status quo and gave some competitive structure (Williams, 1994). After deregulation, the new entrants of low-cost airlines that were largely driven by low costs non-union labour and the widely available of second-hand aircraft entered high volume point to point market (Chan, 2000). However, established carriers capitalised on their size and responded with full innovative strategies. During this period there was various strategic development happen like Frequent flyer programme (FFP), computer reservation system (CRS) and adoption of most important strategic development was the hub and spoke network which allowed airlines to reduce the numbers of aircraft required still being able to provide universal coverage through their networks. Due to the development of these strategies many new entrants were destroyed (Chan, 2000).

The airline industry has become a global orientation and so has its competitions. Airlines industry wants to maintain its position in the market and gain competitive strength to maintain their competitive advantage. Apart from Frequent flyer programme (FFP), Computer Reservation System (CSR), hub and spoke network other strategic orientation is also developed in the airline industry like strategic alliance, vertical integration and horizontal integration. However, as the airline industry is not fully deregulated all around the world and there are still national flag carriers merger and acquisition are still strategic issues that are faced by the airline industry.

2.5.5.1. Competitive strategies

Porter (1985) address that there are many ways in which organisations can get the best out of competitive advantages. He argues that an organisation can structurally lower its competitors or can have products or services that are different from competitors or products that are so valued by customers so that it can charge higher prices. Porter urged firm can choose from any three generic strategies namely cost leadership, differentiation and focus to gain competitive advantages. If firms fail to apply any of this strategy they will be stuck in the middle. He also urges that it is possible for an organisation to adopt more than one strategy at a time; however, it is not possible to follow all generic strategies at the same time.

The airline industry, being a service sector, is prone and open to changes that are highly flexible in demand, competition and has dense or uncertainty (Glisson et al., 1996). As changes occur,

the structure, functions and operation position of airlines are examined as a restructuring period and the changes are based on markets and globalization. The industry also faces numerous challenges to enter new market therefore, competitive strategies are vital to determine the positing of airlines companies.

- **Cost Leadership**

The first generic strategy of porter is about becoming the lowest-cost organisation in the area of activity. Potter (1985) urges that to become that, an organisation needs the highest attention in cost control to become a low-cost organisation. It has also been stated that becoming a low-cost organisation, it helps to defend against its powerful supplier, competitors, powerful buyers, new entrants and substitutes. The four key components that help an organisation to become the cost leader are low input cost, the economics of scale, experience, and product/process design (Johnson et al, 2015). Potter (1985) urges two requirements for cost-based strategies: firstly, it should be lowest than its competitors and secondly, cost should not be in total disregard for quality.

Airlines that pursue cost leadership are often termed as low costs or no-frills airlines that pursue to outperform its competitors by providing service at high labour and capital productivity. In cost leadership, strategy standardization is often considered as the main attribute to the success (Treacy and Wiersema, 1995) and high market share where the economics of scale can grasp. The airlines that pursue this strategy achieves low cost by un-complex point to point turnaround in high volume routes, quick turnaround times, operated by few or one types of aircraft and customer being less sensitive to service-based characteristics (Stoll, 2004).

- **Differentiation**

Differentiation strategies help the organisation to become a unique organisation than their competitors that are sufficiently valued by customers which helps them to charge a premium price. The differentiation varies between markets like in the car industry the differentiation may vary from safety, style, fuel efficiency or even luxury likewise in clothing industry it may vary from location, fashion or even store size. There are various dimensions that are valued by the customer which makes it possible to have different types of differentiation strategy in markets. While adopting differentiation strategies an organisation need to consider two key aspects. Firstly, it has to identify its strategic customer on whose needs the differentiation is based and secondly to identify key competitor even on a particular niche market.

The airlines that adopt differentiation strategy are usually established, sizeable and has worldwide networks that are built upon the possession of critical mass at hubs or dominate position in particular geographical market (Stoll, 2004). According to Farkes et al. (1997), the sophisticated in the networks and hub management is not easily imitable or replicable and that could prove as a sustainable source of competitive advantage. Therefore, it will be a major barrier for small and medium airlines companies to challenge and compete with major established airlines (Holloway, 1998). Airlines that use differentiation strategy usually focus on to build a strong brand with a special focus on attributes such as quality and services (Chen, 2000). The airlines that are generally in this segment are those airlines that are part of the major international alliance and have a close connection or financial stakes at other international companies.

- **Focus Strategies**

Focus strategies come on two variants cost focus and differentiation focus for the underlying source of competitive advantages. Potters urges that organisation either can follow cost focus or differentiation focus to meet the needs of that customer that would ultimately help to gain competitive advantage. This strategy allows an organisation to become proficient in a particular market (Flouris and Oswald, 2006) that would give the organisation a competitive edge.

The focus strategy in the airline industry is directed towards serving the needs of limited customers group of market segment and is a target for a different sector of niche opportunities that exist (Berardino, 1998). According to Stoll (2004), niches in air transportation are either geographical defined, services related or to be confined for cost advantages. So, the airlines that adopt focus strategy are able to gain competitive strength through serving the needs of chosen segments and focusing their activities and efforts on it. However, there are various approaches in focus strategies and in order to gain competitive advantage organisation need to focus on one distinct approach that caters one specific segment. For example, a typical example of service-related niche strategy is to serve business class people. Similarly, the typical example of the geographical airline includes Air Mauritius where it focuses on its own island as it will not be profitable for long haul airlines.

- **Growth Strategies**

The three generic strategies of competitive advantage have been discussed above while this section will focus on Matrix growth strategies that were developed by Ansoff to analysis the different direction a firm can follow for their growth. Ansoff (1965) argues that organisation can follow four different strategy Market penetration, Market Development, Product Development and Diversification to achieve strategic growth as shown in the figure below.

FIGURE 2-7: THE ANSOFF MATRIX

Source: Ansoff (1956)

Market penetration strategy suggests increasing organisation market share by its own existing products and services (Johnson et.al, 2015). If an organisation is simple or undiversified the most obvious strategy is to penetrate its current market with its existing products. Market penetration does not require an organisation to go to a new market or uncharted territory rather than it builds on established strategic capabilities. However, the organisation might face difficulty seeking greater market penetration from its competitors, legal constraints and economic constraints.

Product development focuses on the development of new product or modification of products and services. When an organisation decides to introduce new products and services to its existing customer the firm is said to pursue product development strategy. An organisation can target existing customer with its new product and services using a similar production process and distribution channels. The ability to develop new or modified product and services is

crucial in a rapidly changing market where consumer behaviour is changing with shorter product and service life cycle. Product development can be a risky and expensive activity that could require high investment and willingness to learn about new products (Henry, 2008).

Market development can be attractive if product development is risky and expensive as being potentially cheaper and quicker to execute. An organisation can achieve market development by introducing an existing product or service in a new market. A new market often refers to a new geographical location or new customer market (Flours and Oswald, 2005). Market development does have higher risk as being relatively new in the market. Airlines industry can achieve market development by flying on different location geographically.

2.5.6. Strategic Alliances and Collaborations

Strategic alliances are becoming crucial business models and management strategies that represent a cooperate and complementary approach in achieving market reach that would help in cost reduction, increase customer loyalty and supplement operating capability (Stickler, 2005). Strategic alliances have reshaped competitive strategy through globalization yet activities like an exchange of information and services, sharing and co-development of technology and services takes place where it has help in cost reduction and economics of scale. Strategic alliances are crucial particularly in developing countries as they help carriers to increase their competitiveness against large carriers of developing countries. Furthermore, it also increases the bargaining power or airlines industry in operational levels like fuel price, aircraft maintenance and airport charges. Strategic alliance takes place when a firm chooses to collaborate with one or more other firms in order to achieve its objectives.

Barriers against merger and acquisition are also the factors that encourage strategic alliance. In recent years, the aviation industry has involved in a horizontal relationship with the aim of developing a mutually advantageous agreement that strengths market share (Dana, 2000). The airlines that are operating internationally the question is not whether to join or not join alliance group rather it is with whom and to what extend (Kleymann and Seristo, 2001). Strategic alliance and collaboration have also become a way to bypass bilateral convections that prevents them from flying certain countries or owing foreign airlines (Groenewege, 1999).

Strategic alliances give flexibility to organisations unlike merger or acquisition. Flexibility is what required in a turbulent and uncertain market. Collaboration with a number of global partners can dismiss reliance on one particular region (Agusdinata and Deklein, 2001). Code sharing, integral computer reservation are few milestones that have been achieved through strategic alliances in the airline industry. The code-sharing is a form of sharing its codes with more flights where it can access carriers to display and sell each other seats and provide the customer with a wide range of services. Strategic alliances between airlines and airport industry can provide a sustainable competitive advantage for both allied partners as both involve in a vertical relationship with the same target of providing products and services to the customer.

Strategic alliances have been major strategic management tools where collaboration in the UK is encouraged under a framework called constructive engagement which was developed by CAA that helps discuss issues such as traffic projectors, capacity requirements and investment projects (CAA, 2005). Strategic alliance in the aviation industry started as a code-sharing agreement but has now developed into a global alliance with huge networks (Vasigh et al, 2008). Strategic alliances have high status and increased power in terms of networks that provide aviation industry competitive advantages. It helps airline companies to partner with high-performance cooperations, provides better loyalty programme to customers, achieves cost-saving programme through sharing of sales and flight maintenance systems.

There are three possible levels of strategic alliance in airlines industry that is ordinary, tactical and strategic (Fan et al., 2001). At the ordinary level, if a carrier does not frequently travel to given destinations then it may choose to outsource products and services like handling the general sale, airport functions to another carrier or handling agents. In the tactical level, the organisation usually cross-sells each other or carries marketing its code on governance structure. Cooperation between different carries in this level is usually limited where carries are still classified as independent. In the strategic level, airlines alliances are characterized by joint, dedicated marketing entities for network-wide cooperation. It helps to provide partners with mutual benefits that are generated through voluntary agreements involving sharing, exchanging or co-development of products, technologies or services (Gulati, 1998).

The previous empirical study that was done on strategic alliance in Turkish airlines found that there are two factors at the macro level and four factors at the micro-level to be important to succeed in strategic airlines alliance (Semercioz and Kocer, 2004). This study investigates

antecedents of the success and failure in strategic alliances which was implemented by Airlines Company as a response to globalization and liberal government policies. Turkish Airlines partnership with Qualiflyer group consists of Swiss air, Sabena, TAP, AOM, Air Europe and Cross Air until it collapsed in 2001.

The two macro-level factors that were affecting Turkish airlines were political and economic differences and international regulation. When Turkish airlines joint Qualiflyer group it was on the verge of privatization (Borsa Market, 1999) as government own 51% of the company (TPA, 2002). The relationship with Turkish airlines with Qualiflyer group was affected for two reasons first as Turkish airlines on the process of privatization general manager Bulayirli declared that join project development with Qualiflyer would be on hold as any commercial agreements would be bidding for the company's future. Second, the inflexible nature of the state was decreasing Turkish Airlines ability to participate in group projects as the most business-related decisions were subject to be approved by the TPA and even state planning organisation (SPO). The micro-level factor that affected Turkish airlines relationship with Qualiflyer group were compatible objectives, analysis of prospective partners, management relationship with alliances and level of cooperation.

This study concludes that liberation of the airline industry allowed carriers to reach wider areas in the world and airlines with a larger fleet and finical resources were more likely to benefit. Therefore, strategic alliances became an important source of synergy for airlines in the developing countries as it would increase its competitiveness against larger carriers. Strategic alliances' successes are the result of the consequences of the interdependencies between macro and micro factors. In the context of the Turkish Airline, the cooperation with Qualiflyer group was limited due to political and economic differences. Incomplete privatization as macro factor affected alliances success through its influence on the micro-level factor that became a source of uncertainty that their partner did not appreciate and it became barriers against the managerial flexibility required to complete integration that caused lack of cooperation since bidding would decrease Turkish Airlines' attraction to non Qualiflyer carriers. Turkish Airlines did not achieve its objectives with Qualiflyer group because of macro and micro factors mention above. However, due to strategic alliances, it enhanced its brand value through association with a well-known European brand. It also gained experiences of strategic alliance which would help in their future strategic alliance strategies.

However, the success of the strategic alliances and collaboration primary depends on a clear understanding of the expectation of each party and align with the right partners with compatible goals. There are various factors that might affect strategic alliance performance like economic and political differences, compatible objectives. This study concluded that in order to achieve maximum benefit from alliance strategy, prospective partners should evaluate its strategic objectives in the partner selection process and monitor when there is a change in those objectives after they established those alliance relationship. Cost is another factor that should be considered in the partner selection process as it might require a larger investment in systems such as technology. Companies should consider all different cost attributes while forming strategic alliances from joining to leave an alliance group.

In order to survive in competitive markets, airline companies must build strategic competitiveness that will become the competitive strength of the organisation and help to build critical success factors. The success of an airline company depends on how quickly it can respond to the changes and adapt to the changing environment rather than if it is able to strategically respond or not. This research is focused on strategic challenges of NAC therefore a strategic analysis of NAC is presented below.

2.6. Nepalese Aviation Industry

The aviation industry has played a tremendous role in the economic growth of Nepal and has provided opportunities for global connectivity, tourism, and global trade (Dangol, 2018). Nepal Government has kept tourism its upmost priorities of economic growth of Nepal and Nepal aviation industry has provided great exposure in bring tourism, foreign supplies, opportunities for social and cultural exchange and help during a humanitarian crisis (Nepal Government, 2010). The establishment of aviation industry date back in 1958 A.D. were aviation was not accessible to the public. However, due to technological advancement, globalisation and various other factors air transport has become just another mode of transport.

According to IATA (2018), the Nepalese aviation industry has a major impact on the economy of Nepal in the aspects of creating jobs where 455,000 were supported by air transportation including people arriving from the air and USD 1.1 billion was contributed which 3.7 % of country's GDP. According to IATA (2018), the air transport is expected to grow by 165% by

2038 A.D. under current trend meaning around 784,400 jobs will be created and USD 2.9 billion of G.D.P will be added. In 2018, Tribhuwan International Airport posts the growth of 12 percentage of passengers comparing to 2017 (Prasain, 2019).

The Nepalese aviation industry's domestic market has been dominated by budget private airlines namely Buddha Airlines, Yeti Airlines, Tara Airs, Summit Airlines, Saurya Airlines, Sita Airlines, and Nepal Airlines which are all cost-effective airlines (Skyline, 2017). In 2018, the domestic share of the private airline companies was 97.22% (Prasain, 2019). Similarly, the international market is also dominated by private airlines or airlines from other international countries with a market share of 89.67% in 2018 (Prasain, 2019). Air transportation in Nepal has been developing and there is a growth of airlines operating from different countries in the globe.

Nepal has bilateral agreements with 36 different countries; however, 22 of them do not have direct flights to and from Nepal (CAAN, 2013). According to the Ministry of Tourism and Civil Aviation (MOTCA), in 2013, about 75 per cent of international tourists arrived through air transportation (MOTCA, 2013). Due to poor road transportation system and lack of other means of transport, air transport provides key services to domestic passengers and tourists. Nepal has 56 airports in total and among them, one is an international airport and the rest of them are domestic airports (CAAN, 2014).

2.6.1. Nepal Airlines Corporation

Nepal Airlines Corporation is the first national carrier of Nepal that was established in July 1958 as Royal Nepal Airlines Cooperation (RNAC). Its headquarter is located in Sundara, Kathmandu, Nepal with the main hub being Tribhuwan International Airport (Joshi et al., 2015). It currently operates with the fleet of eleven aircraft in over 25 destinations nationally and five destinations internationally (Nepal Airlines cooperation, 2016). NAC owns 2 Airbus A330, 2 Airbus A320 for international destination and it has 6 Chinese and 1 twin otter aircraft for the domestic market that are airworthy (Prasain, 2019).

After the liberalization of the airline industry, Royal Nepal Airlines Corporation (RNAC) name was changed to Nepal Airlines Corporation (NAC). The first aircraft was Douglas DC-3 that

was used to serve domestic routes and a handful of India destinations. NAC acquired its first aircraft 727s in 1972 (Joshi et al., 2015). It acquired Hawker Siddeley HS-748 in 1970, Twin Otter in 1971, Boeing 727 in 1972. In 1988 to 1989 NAC reported revenue of \$54.3 million with an operating profit of \$ 17 million. NAC was country largest employer with 2,200 employees and largest foreign currency earner with bringing \$ 15 million roughly a year from abroad (Civil Aviation Authority of Nepal, 2013; Nepal government 2010). NAC in its heyday in 1980 was one of the leading airlines with 10 international and 38 domestic destinations with the company having a fleet of 19 aircraft, including 8 twin otter, three Boeing 727 and two 757 (Prasain, 2019). The table below presents the history of NAC's fleet.

TABLE 2-3: THE HISTORY OF NAC'S FLEET

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at Nepal Airlines. (2020) *Brief History*. Available online: <https://www.nepalairlines.com.np/home/histories>

Source: Nepal airlines (2020)

NAC came to terrible situations by mid-2010 with once profitable airlines has been scuppered completely (Prasain, 2019). Similarly, in 2013, NAC halted its service during festival time stating that they did not have any plane to fly. The private airline companies like Buddha Airlines, Yeti Airlines that has not long been established has been leading the domestic market

of NAC (Econ-ity, 2015; Bastola, 2017). NAC has virtually nothing left in recent years despite being granted a loan to buy new aircraft. However, it seems like buying new aircraft would not only solve the problem they have and would not overcome the losses (The Kathmandu Post, 2017).

Even though NAC has been operating its activity domestically and internationally, it has been disorganised, has political interferences and has less aircraft than it had before (Shrestha, 2011). The political system of Nepal is so volatile that there is no safe environment for airlines operation. On the other hand, NAC is facing its own problems with quality service, the growth of other airlines company is another problem. The government is unstable and there is no transparency in the organisation and it has lead NAC into a complete mess. In 2014, NAC decided of revitalising the ailing airlines with 10 years plan drawn up proposing to procure five narrow-body and four wide-body aircraft for long haul routes like USA, Europe and Australia (Prasain, 2019) NAC made a three-year improvement plan in 2015 provisioned of purchasing new aircraft, international market expansion, revisions and update of policies, improve online ticketing system, improve internal management, improve the financial system, removing NAC from EU blacklist and implementation of effective control and planning system (Subedi, 2016).

2.6.1.1. Organisational Vision, Mission and Objectives

The vision, mission and objectives of Nepal airlines are presented below (NAC, 2010).

Vision

- To become a leading airlines company in Nepal.

Mission

- To provide world-class air service with competitive price in both the domestic and international sectors.

Objectives

- To increase market share, market expansion, fleet expansion and regain a leading position in both the domestic and international markets.
- To recognized as reliable and punctual national flag carrier in both the domestic and international markets.
- To remain open to innovative ideas that can enhance service standards and overall performance of the organisation.

- To focus on the attraction of three vital resources investment, aircraft and human resources and make them as productive so the competitive strength can be maintained among with competitors.
- To ensure the resources and capabilities can provide sustainable competitive advantage so that there is a reasonable return for stakeholders.

2.6.1.2. *Company Structure*

The main in charge of NAC is the Executive Chairman who reports to the board and the government officials of Nepal. The departments are divided into two categories: administration and technical (NAC, 2010). The administration division consist of five departments namely Human resources department, commercial department, finance department, cooperate department, and general services and property management department and the directors of this department reports to deputy managing director of administration. Similarly, the technical division consists of five departments, namely customer service department, ground support department, operational department, engineering maintenance department and continuing airworthiness management department and the directors of this department report to deputy managing director of technical (Yadav, 2016). The figure below presents the organisational structure and hierarchy of NAC.

TABLE 2-4: NAC ORGANISATIONAL STRUCTURE

Source: Yadav (2016)

Operational department of the organisation is responsible for crew management and flight operation as per the plan prepared by the commercial department. The commercial department is responsible for all marketing and sales-related activities, exploration of the market and promotion, managing agents, managing schedule and non-schedule flights and does make pricing decisions. The financial department is responsible for planning, controlling and monitoring financial activities such as budgeting, cash flow, financial transaction process and negotiating with banks. The engineering department is responsible for the maintenance of aircraft and maintenance plan aspects such as procurement and storage of engineering equipment, maintenance and order of spare parts and make aircrafts ready for timely flights. Human resources department is responsible for recruitment, transfer and promotion of employees as well as the welfare issues of employees. All the fixed assets of NAC is maintained and purchased by general service and property management. Continuing airworthiness management department ensures that NAC complies with civil aviation authority of Nepal (CAAN) quality and safety standards in flights. Cooperate department is responsible for business planning, publication, legal aspects of NAC. The ground handling activities are looked after by ground handling department. The customer services department looks after the query and issues of the customers. Finally, the internal audit department ensure that there is not any irregularity in any of the activities of NAC such as any financial transactions.

NAC adopts generic focus strategy at present as it operates as a niche operator focusing on tourists, rural areas and Nepalese diaspora travelling and living abroad for various purposes (Gyanwali and Walsh, 2020). NAC targets a similar market segment in international destinations as well. In the domestic market, it operates in remote areas, mountains tourist areas where other airlines normally do not operate due to poor infrastructure of airports and lack of volume.

2.6.2. Strategic review of Nepal Airlines Corporation

2.6.2.1. *PESTLE Analysis of Nepal Airlines Corporation*

The table below (Table 2-4) presents the PESTLE analysis of NAC.

TABLE 2-5: PESTLE ANALYSIS OF NAC

Factors	Impacts on NAC
Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of transparency, corruption, political interference and political appointment (Econ-ity, 2015). • Political Instability of the Government impacting the business plan and operations of NAC (Bastola, 2017). • Political appointment of lack of experiences, skill and knowledgeable people in key decision making place leading to corruption and a huge loss to NAC (Gyanwali and Walsh, 2020). • Political interference and involvement in purchase, leasing aircrafts leading huge financial losses (Gyanwali and Walsh, 2020) and politicians making NAC as their money-making organisation for parties and themselves (Prasain, 2019).
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The growth in the economy of Nepal reaching 7.1 per cent in FY2019 due to growth in the service sector, growth in agriculture, higher remittance inflow, growth in tourism, growth in retail trade, growth in real estate, growth in transport and restaurant services (Nepal Development Update, 2019) • Growth in domestic passenger traffic that was increased by 11.96 per cent to 3.18 million in 2019 where it was 1.37 million a decade ago (Prasain, 2020) • Air transportation is cheaper and affordable by middle-class people (Prasain, 2020). • NAC has a loan with an interest rate of 10.5 per cent fixed per annum that has been secured from two government organisation namely Citizen Investment Trust (CIT) and Employee provident fund (EPF) to buy two-wide-body Airbus (The Kathmandu Post, 2017). • Increasing the losses of NAC, interest rates where equity and loan are very high and the cumulative loss has soared and the current loan of NAC is Rs. 40 billion (Poudel, 2019).
Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The rising numbers of Nepalese people travelling abroad for employment, higher education, tourism and religious purpose have contributed to the use of growth of air transportation domestically and internationally (Mann Paryo, 2019). • The tourism boom in Nepal has contributed to the growth of air transportation (CAPA, 2018) and managed to bring more than 1 million tourists in 2017 (Biju, 2018).
Technological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of modern and technological advance aircraft that has negatively impact reliability, punctuality and safety of NAC ultimately contributing huge financial losses where NAC has decided to ground all the Chinese-made aircraft (Bastola, 2017; Gyanwali and Walsh, 2020; Prasain, 2020).
Legal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public procurement act that NAC has to follow whilst purchasing aircraft (CAPA, 2019)

Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growth number of airlines companies has increased the probability of environmental pollution in Nepal (Karki, 2017). • Challenging geographical locations of airports in Nepal with the main hub in the middle of the city (Upreti, 2016).
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2.6.2.2. SWOT Analysis of Nepal Airlines Corporation

The table below presents a SWOT analysis of NAC.

TABLE 2-6: SWOT ANALYSIS OF NAC

Factors	Impacts on NAC
Strength	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong financial backing from government and the strong brand itself representing national flag carrier (Yadav, 2016) • NAC operates in 8 international cities (within 6 countries) and 25 domestic destinations (Gyanwali and Walsh, 2020) • Experiences Airlines company operating for more than 62 years with being on the best airlines companies in south Asia in past (Prasain, 2019) • NAC generates Rs. 4 billion from ground handling services from Tribhuvan international airport (Prasain, 2019) and has total assets worth of Rs. 54.17 billion (Magar, 2020).
Weakness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political appointment and interferences causing huge financial losses, operational issues and impact in the business plan(Gyanwali and Walsh, 2020) • NAC has old aircraft and lack of pilots to fly its domestic Chinese aircraft which are high on insurance, high maintenance costs that are not safe and reliable (Prasain, 2020) • Lack of coordination among the department of NAC and poor employee relationship (Yadav, 2016) • Rated as one of the worst airlines companies among 22 airlines by Skytrax that focus on services (The Himalayan, 2015) • Less employee empowerment culture and old manpower (Gaibre and Shakya, 2017) • NAC does not have sufficient aircraft where it does have 4 international aircraft and two domestic aircraft that are airworthiness (Prasain, 2019) • Lack of long term planning and poor handling of resources (Yadav, 2016) • Mismanagement at NAC (Prasain, 2019)
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The growing projects like air transport enhancement, Gautam Buddha International airport, Pokhara Regional International airport and Nijgadh International airport are the ray of opportunities that can contribute to the growth of NAC (Bastola, 2017). • The purchase of two 274 seaters A 330-200 wide-body and two A320-200 narrow-body aircraft from Airbus for international destinations provide an

	<p>opportunity for market expansion, growth in the market that will contribute in the growth of revenue (The Himalayan Times 2018; Gaibre and Shakya 2018)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The rising income of Nepalese people, growth in domestic and international tourism and opportunities to form alliances with other international airlines companies (Yadav, 2016) • In the financial year 2019, economic growth of Nepal was 7.1 per cent due to growth in the service sector, growth in agriculture, higher remittance inflow, growth in tourism, growth in retail trade, growth in real estate, growth in transport and restaurant services which will provide opportunities for NAC growth (Nepal Development update, 2019). • The increasing growth of domestic traffic which increased by 11.96 per cent to 3.18 million where it was 1.37 million decades ago will provide opportunities in the growth of the domestic market (Prasain, 2020).
Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NAC lacks customer trust, quality service and negative image of reliability and punctuality (Gaibre and Shakya, 2017) • Nepali Aviation industry (Including NAC) has been blacklisted by the European Commission to enter European skies for safety concerns (Pokhrel, 2020). • One international airport causing traffic congestion increasing operational costs and impacting the effectiveness of aircrafts operations (Karki, 2017). • The increasing interest rates and mounting debts that stands at Rs. 37 billion from various institutions (The Kathmandu Post, 2020) • Increase in the price of jet fuel (Prasain, 2019)

2.6.2.3. Porter's Five Forces Analysis of Nepal Airlines Corporation

The figure below presents Porter's Five Forces analysis of NAC.

TABLE 2-7: PORTER'S FIVE FORCES ANALYSIS OF NAC

Factors	Impacts on NAC
Rivalry among existing competitors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The competition in Nepal aviation international market has been intensified with 27 foreign international companies operating and dominating 90 per cent of the international market (CAPA, 2018). • There is fierce competition among airlines companies in Nepal with the 97 per cent of the domestic market captured by private airlines companies like Buddha, Yeti, Shree, Saurya, Tara, Smirk and summit airlines (Prasain, 2020)
Threat of Entry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The threat of entry is low in the airline industry as it is mainly due to the huge capital requirement (Rahman et al., 2015).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The airline industry is already statured and one of the most expensive industry to operate that requires skilled human resources, technical knowhow and companies can gain from economies of scales so operating on a large level is considered as profitable (Pratap, 2018). • The international big companies have recently started to operate from Nepal like Turkish Airways (Rai, 2018)
Pressure from substitutes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The only substitutes option for air transport in Nepal is road transportation which does not impact international destination. The domestic destination is also not impacted much due to cheap air tickets, poor road conditions. (Prasain, 2020) • The pressure of substitutes in the airline industry is low due to lower ticketing prices available, convenient, time convenient (Pratap, 2018).
Bargaining power of Buyers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The bargaining power of the customer is high due to huge competition in Nepal airlines market with various domestic and international airlines operating in Nepal • The advancement of technology has given the power to buyers as they can buy tickets online or through intermediates which has the option of various airlines companies, no switching cost, therefore, do not have to stick with one airline (Rahman et al., 2015; Pratap, 2018).
Bargaining power of suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The demand for aircraft is very high as there are lots of airlines companies however there is only two main aircraft manufactures Airbus and Boeing that makes the power of supplier high (Rahman et al., 2015) • The monopoly of Nepal oil corporation charges the highest cost of jet fuels comparing to other countries (Prasain, 2019).

2.6.3. Challenges Faced By Nepal Airlines Corporation

The key challenges being faced by NAC are discussed below:

2.6.3.1. Banned from flying to Europe leading to Bad reputation

NAC has been rated one of the worst airlines among 22 airlines that have been awarded two-star by the UK based Skytrax in annual world airlines rating (The Himalayan, 2015). Skytrax rating is more focus on services not on safety stated that Nepal Airlines provided low-quality performance, poor and unreliable standard of product, poor front line staff service for cabin services, poor home-based airport environment. According to Skytrax customer reviews indicated that it has failed on several other factors like in-flight entertainment, seat comfort, staff service, food, beverage, etc. (Prasain, 2019).

In 2013, the European Commission blacklisted and banned Nepali airlines from entering the European skies after the International Civil Aviation organisation raised significant safety concerns of Nepal aviation (Pokhrel, 2020). Since then, NAC has not been allowed to fly to the 28-nations bloc of European Union countries (My Republican, 2016). The European Commission has raised concerns regarding the fatal crash as Nepal had been reporting a spate of air crashes over the years (Prasain, 2020). The European commission major demands were a revision of Civil Aviation polices and splitting the Civil Aviation Authority of Nepal into operational and regulatory bodies (South Asia monitor, 2020). has been effort made By Nepal Aviation regulator where it hired an expert with the International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO) for one year as per its plan to delist Nepal Airlines from the blacklist and send the required documents but it all effort went on Vain where European Union decided to continue to ban (Pokhrel, 2018). Nepal airlines came bottom of the safety reports and when it comes to safety NAC does not have a good reputation (Mail online, 2015).

2.6.3.2. Lack of transparency, corruption, political interference

NAC has heavily suffered from lack of transparency, corruption, political interference where it has come down to a fleet of two operational planes and five international destinations in 2014 from doing 21 international destinations and fleet of 19 planes in 1980 (Econ-ity,2015). The decline of Nepal airlines started along with the introduction of multiparty democracy where prime ministers made NAC a cash cow for themselves and their party (People’s Review, 2016). Girija Prasad Koirala, then the prime minister of Nepal, decided to dispose of flying condition Boeing 727 aircraft and lease aircraft for a short period of time under the influence of commission agents rather than buying new aircraft.

The management of NAC has been shaken up every time there has been a change in the government of Nepal. According to an aviation consultant, NAC has also been warned that its organisation was running like managing food cooperation (Nepali Times, 2015). NAC has been run as third government cooperation where there is not expertise management and lack of transparent decision making (Nepali Times, 2016). Due to the polarization of political alignment in staff union cause poor coordination within the departments of Nepal Airlines and irresponsibility among some employees (Gyanwali and Walsh, 2020).

2.6.3.3. *No strategies for hiring and retaining talented employees*

NAC has not been able to hire pilots and other employees to fulfil their vacant jobs due to less competitive financial package and uncertain within NAC. NAC had once announced the vacancy of 2 junior pilots to fly within domestic routes but did not receive a single response (Nepali Times, 2010). NAC lack of good salary schemes, guaranteed hours, and the lack of competitive packages, which led to this situation. The technical manpower like pilots, operational engineers, and aircraft maintenance engineers leave once they acquire some experience due to improper management, low salary scale, no proper evaluation of contribution and talent (Joshi et al., 2015).

2.6.3.4. *Lack of leadership and aviation expert to run airlines*

NAC is well known for not having leaders in its organisation. Leaders without vision, ambition, and clear strategies are running NAC in recent years. A recent example of lack of leadership and aviation in NAC is the plan to buy a wide-body aircraft (Online Khabar, 2016). Nepal airlines made public about their three years plan where it would buy two wide-body aircraft. This plan was halt initially after its two own narrow-body aircraft failed to operate in full capacity.

2.6.3.5. *Expensive Aviation Fuels*

The state-owned oil monopoly of Nepal Oil Corporation makes a fortnightly profit of more than Rs. 200 million on aviation fuel charging NAC USD1 per litre for aviation fuel at TIA comparing to \$0.46 per litre and \$0.55 per litre in Delhi (Prasain, 2019). The fuel cost of NAC is accounted for 30 per cent of operational cost and is engaged in unfair competition with foreign airlines that get subsidised. The feasibility of route and ticketing price is also determined by fuel price (Ojha, 2019).

2.6.3.6. *High competition and the lack of fleet*

NAC's market share in Nepal has been much taken by other private Nepal's budget Airlines (Himalayan Times, 2016). They have capitalised on the weakness of the NAC. Same on other international routes where NAC does not fly any more international airlines so has other international airlines have taken then market share of them. NAC is very weak in terms of technology and comfort where it is hard for it to compete with any other airlines.

In the context of NAC, it only has a handful of aircraft due to lack of ownership feeling from the government (Gyanwali and Walsh, 2020) where it has two twin otter for the domestic market and two wide-body and two narrow-body for the international market (Ch-aviation, 2020). Furthermore, NAC does not have the required funds to purchase aircraft and has to rely on government and lenders. However, the main issue with the fleet of Nepal airlines is not only lack of sufficient aircraft rather it is effective to use and proper operation of them (Prasain, 2019). NAC has not been able to fly the required amount of the hours in the sky that is required to make any profit from two wide-body, two narrow-body and it has grounded all of its six Chinese domestic aircraft (The Kathmandu Post, 2020).

All these factors have contributed to the lack of market share in both domestic (2.78 percentage) and international market share (11.3 percentage), reliability and punctuality issue in NAC (Prasain, 2019). Secondly, the funds required for the purchase NAC will be difficult as the debt of NAC currently at it a critical level that has a loan from various institutions that stands at Rs. 37 billion with an annual interest payment of Rs. 3.66 billion and an interest rate of 10.5 percentage approximately (The Kathmandu Post, 2017). The recent pandemic has also force NAC to seek government bailout of Rs. 20 billion (The Kathmandu Post, 2020) and NAC is seeking Rs.4 billion to purchase new aircraft for its beleaguered domestic fleets (Ch-aviation, 2020).

2.6.3.7. The Lack of Sufficient International Airports

Tribhuvan International Airport (TIA) is the only getaway in and for Nepal. When it comes to the airport, it includes a different array of facilities, rules and regulation. However, the situation and the condition of one and only Airport of Nepal is different. It is considered to be one of the worst airports in the world based on security, facility, cleanliness, service and comfort (The Himalayan, 2016). It has only one runway that has also been developing potholes and cracks time and again. It was constructed in 1967 with a target to support some 196 tons of flight but has been landing around 300 tons in recent years.

The commission for the Investigation of Abuse of Authority (CIAA) found out in 2013 that due to poor facilities and weakness at the only international airport of Nepal TIA it has not been able to cope with existing air traffic and extension of air services. It has made air service risky in Nepal. Due to attenuation in the intuitional capacity of NIC, its competitive capacity is in decline. NIC was in finical crisis when other private firms were earning profits. It

concluded that if the existing challenges and problem of corruption is not addressed on time than there was danger of cooperation going in liquidation (CIAA, 2013).

There has been a problem with parking congestion at the airport. An aircraft, when it arrives at the airport, has to hover around for a while due to traffic congestion. Customers, on the other hand, have complained about baggage clearing area where they have to wait up to an hour to get their baggage from the conveyor belt. All these factors affect the competitiveness of NAC as TIA being home-based airport for the airlines.

2.6.3.8. *Poor Management*

NAC has faced its worst-ever flight schedule crisis where it had to halt its flight for international destination lack of planes (The Himalayan, 2016). Among eight aircrafts three were flying on international routes, three on domestic routes were grounded at the same time, one of the planes had technical issues and send it to Singapore for repair other had been grounded after bird strike. It took a few days to resume service as the spare parts that have been ordered would take a couple of days to arrive. The poor management and lack of coordination within the department have lead NAC in such serious and shame situation. Due to this Nepal airlines has been making millions of rupees loss daily.

2.7. Conceptual Framework

Based on the discussions presented in the forgoing sections of this chapter, a research conceptual framework is developed. The figure below presents the conceptual framework of this research.

FIGURE 2-8: RESEARCH CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Source: The Author

Upon an extensive review of the literature, multiple tools for conducting a strategic analysis of an organisation were identified. As presented in the figure above, some of the most common tools used for conducting a strategic analysis of an airline company include SWOT, PESTLE, resource-based view and value chain analysis. These strategic analysis tools assist in gathering relevant information about organisations prior to formulating and implementing effective business strategies (Campbell et al., 2002; CIMA 2007; Henry, 2008; Grant, 2008; Ramanujam et al., 1986). Particularly in the context of the aviation industry, having a good understanding of both internal and external business environments is essential in order to be able to outline factors that are critical for the success of an airline company. Strategies developed without giving considerations to internal and external organisational factors tend to fail (Candido and Santos, 2019).

Effective utilisation of strategic analysis tools can help to reveal critical success factors - considerations of which is essential for attaining increased profitability, performance, and sustainability. Prior studies identified various critical success factors related to the aviation industry. They include organisational structure (Byles 2007; Herogopal 2007; Spector, 2007), collaboration with other airlines companies (Burton and Hanlon 1994; Airlines Business, 2006), organisational culture (Laudon and Laudon, 2007; Johnson et al., 2008), and planning and development (Golightly, 1967; Olumuyiwa et al., 2012; Freel, 2000). Careful considerations of these factors during strategy formulation processes can result in enhanced organisations performance, improved sustainability, and ultimately increased revenue collections and profitability.

2.8. Conclusions

The aviation industry is not only extremely competitive but it is also highly fragile as a small change in the industry can significantly impact the profitability and sustainability of airline companies. The review of the literature indicated that effective business strategies and their adequate implementation are essential for any airline company to survive. Although there are numerous studies conducted in the airline industry (i.e., Graham, 2004; Park, 2003; Jarach, 2005; William, 2006; Albers et al., 2005), the number of studies that particularly focused on the strategic aspects of airline companies is limited.

Prior studies highlighted various tools for strategic analysis such as SWOT, Five forces, PESTLE, value chain analysis, resource-based view, positioning, and business model for assessing the factors impacting both the external and the internal environments of an organisation. This chapter reviewed all key tools for strategic analysis by evaluating their strengths and weaknesses while applying to the airline industry. This chapter also dealt with strategy formulation and implementation aspects by pinpointing different approaches in which business strategies can be developed and successfully implemented.

As this research precisely focuses on NAC, an extensive review of the literature related to the global aviation industry and NAC was conducted. The review identified a handful of empirical studies conducted in NAC; however, they were incomprehensive and lacked the necessary depth for strategy formulation. For example, a case study research was done in NAC where only SWOT analytical tool was used and no primary data was collected (i.e., Yadav, 2016).

Similarly, another research by Joshi et al. (2015) reviewed the present scenario of NAC, but it also relied on the secondary data. Another study by Gyanwali and Walsh (2019) focused on influencing factors of organisational performance using mixed methods where primary data was collected through fifteen in-depth interviews. Gyanwali and Walsh (2019) did not focus on the strategic aspects of the organisation. The review of the literature highlighted numerous knowledge gaps regarding strategic positioning and challenges of NAC. Below are the key knowledge gap being addressed by this research.

- The lack of prior studies involving the strategic challenges faced by Nepal Airlines Corporation.
- The lack of prior studies focused on identifying the critical success factors of Nepal Airlines Corporation.

This research, therefore, aims to fill the current knowledge vacuum by investigating the strategic challenges faced by NAC as well as its critical success factors. The findings of this research will not only bridge the knowledge gap but will also make contributions to the practitioners by pinpointing ways in which the sustainability of the organisation can be enhanced. The following chapter now deals with the methodological aspects of this research.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to identify the most suitable philosophical stance for this research after carefully reviewing and comparing different research philosophies. After identifying the most suitable philosophy for the research, the relevant research approach, research design, relevant tools and techniques for data collection analysis are critically reviewed. Based on the review of the literature, a research design is developed in this chapter. This chapter also deals with the chosen sampling technique for this research, research ethics, and limitations of the selected research methods. The figure below presents the structure of this chapter.

FIGURE 3-1: STRUCTURE OF CHAPTER THREE

3.2. Philosophy of the Research

According to Saunders et al. (2016), research philosophy refers to a system of belief and assumption about the development of knowledge. Prior to discussing various research philosophies, the section below discusses different philosophical assumptions.

3.2.1. Philosophical Assumptions

Philosophical assumptions are made both consciously or unconsciously at every stage of the research (Burrell and Morgan, 1979). These assumptions shape how we understand the research question, the method we use, and how we interpret our findings (Crotty, 1998). A well thought out set of assumption will establish a creditable research philosophy which will underpin methodical choice, research strategy, data collection techniques, and analysis procedure. This will help to design a coherent research project in which all the elements will fit together. According to Johnson and Clark (2006), business and management researcher should be aware of the philosophical commitment they make through our choice of research strategy since this will have a significant impact on what we do and how we understand on what we are investing on. There are three key assumptions, namely ontology, epistemology, and axiology that support to distinguish research philosophy (Saunders et al., 2016).

3.2.1.1. *Ontological Assumptions*

This philosophical assumption is concerned about the nature of the reality, in particular, whether the objective reality exists and is authentic (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Bryman, 2012; Denzin and Lincoln, 2000). The ontological assumption shapes the way we see and study research objects. Research objects, in this case, are organisations, managers, individual working people, organisational events, and artefacts. Therefore, our ontology determines how we see the world of business and management shapes what to research for the research project (Saunders et al, 2012).

3.2.1.2. *Epistemological Assumptions*

Epistemology concerns supposition about knowledge, what constitutes acceptable, valid and legitimate knowledge, and how to communicate it with the others (Burrell and Morgan, 1979).

Business and management are multidisciplinary contexts so it has a different kind of knowledge ranging from numerical data to textual and visual data, from facts to interpretation like narratives and stories all can be considered as legitimate. However, different business and management research adopt different epistemologies in their research including project based on archival research and autobiographical accounts (Marti and Fernandez, 2013), fictional literature (De Cock and Land, 2006) and narratives (Gabriel et al., 2013). The variety of epistemologies gives a greater choice of method(s) however it is vital to understand the importance of different epistemological assumptions in relation to methods, their strengths, and limitations in subsequent research findings.

3.2.1.3. *Axiological Assumptions*

This philosophical assumption denotes to the role of ethics and value in the process of the research. It integrates how researchers deal with the value of our own and the participant. These values are guiding reasons for all human actions (Heron, 1996). A researcher demonstrates axiological skills being able to articulate human values whilst making judgements during the research process. For example, choosing one topic rather than other shows the topic that is highly valued by the researcher.

3.2.2. Subjectivism and Objectivism

The business and management research philosophies are scattered along with a multidimensional set of continua (Niglas, 2010) between two opposing extremes objectivism and subjectivism. Objectivism incorporates the assumption of the natural sciences by embracing realism where it considers social entities to be like physical entities of the natural world. It believes interpretations and experiences of social actors do not influence the existence of social world rather it believes that there is only one true social reality experienced by all social actors. The social world is made up of solid, granular, and relatively unchanging things including a major social structure where individuals are born (Burrell and Morgan, 1979).

On the other hand, a subjectivism considers that social reality is made from perceptions and actions of people. It incorporates assumptions of the arts and humanities where it considers that order and structure of social phenomena we study are created by both researcher and social actors through the use of conceptual categories, languages, consequent actions, and

perceptions. Each individual's experience and perception of reality is different thus it is sensible to talk about multiple reality rather than a single reality (Burrell and Morgan, 1979). Subjectivism believes that reality is constructed through social interaction in which social actors create partially shared meanings and realities. The subjectivist researchers are interested in a different opinion, narratives, stories that can help to account for various social realities of various social actors. The table below summaries the continua and two extremes in relation to the three types of philosophical assumption discussed in chapter 3.2.1.

TABLE 3-1: PHILOSOPHICAL ASSUMPTION AS A MULTIDIMENSIONAL SET OF CONTINUA

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3.2.3. Research Philosophies

In the domain of business and management research, there are three major research philosophies. They include Positivism, Interpretivism, and Pragmatism (Saunders et.al, 2012; Wilson, 2014). Below, each of them is discussed.

3.2.3.1. *Positivism*

Positivism refers to the philosophical stance of natural scientists and entails work with an observable social reality to produce law-like generalisations (Saunders et.al, 2012). The focus of positivism is strictly focused on scientific empiricist methods designed to yield pure data and the facts that are not influenced by human interpretation. Positivist research starts with reviewing existing theories and developing hypotheses that are subsequently tested statistically. Positivist researchers remain neutral and detached from the research itself in order to avoid influence and possible biases (Crotty, 1998). Positivist studies are highly structured and facilitate replication (Gill and Johnson, 2010). A positivist researcher collects quantifiable data that are measurable in numbers. Although positivist research has various advantages such as replication and generalisation of the findings, it is often criticised for being unable to extract rich in-depth information (Saunders et.al, 2012). Besides, positivist researchers treat respondents as repositories of facts and give little considerations towards their individual feelings and emotions (Holstein and Gubrium, 2011).

3.2.3.2. *Interpretivism*

Unlike positivism, interpretivism believes that human beings are different from physical phenomena as they create meanings (Saunders et.al, 2012). This philosophy argues that social science cannot be studied in a similar way as natural sciences. Interpretivist researchers believe that as different human beings react differently in different circumstances, different social realities exist (Gill and Johnson, 2010). Therefore, they argue that all people involved in research should be looked from different perspectives rather than universally – which is the positivist belief.

The main purpose of an interpretivist researcher is to create new, richer understanding, and interpretations of the social world and contexts (Bell, 2018). For a business management researcher, it means looking organisation through the perspective of each individual such as CEO, supervisor, board of directors, managers, cleaners, and customers as they tend to have different perspectives and different experiences. Interpretivist researcher tries to take account of this intricacy by collecting what is meaningful to their research participants (Collis and Hussey, 2014). There are different strands of interpretivism that emphasise on how to conduct this practice. For example, phenomenologists focus on participants' lived experiences,

hermeneuticists focus on the study of cultural artefacts such as texts, stories, symbols, images, and symbolic interactionists focus on observation and analysis of the social interactions such as meetings, conversation, and teamwork (Crotty, 1998).

Generally, interpretivist researchers emphasise the importance of language, culture, and history in shaping the interpretations and experiences of the organisational and social works (Crotty, 1998). The focus of an interpretivist researcher is on complexity, richness, and multiple interpretations. However, and interpretive researcher are can be highly involved in emotional aspects of the research and thus greatly influence the interpretation of the findings, leading to the researcher bias. Besides, the findings of interpretive research cannot be generalised as they tend to be based on a small sample size (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

3.2.3.3. *Pragmatism*

As aforementioned, both positivist and interpretive researchers strictly follow the principles of the philosophy and take either an objective or subjective stance. Pragmatic researchers, however, do not focus highly on taking a particular approach, rather they focus on answering the phenomenon by adopting a different set of approaches wherever necessary (Saunders et.al, 2016). Research problems initially originate a study under this philosophy and researchers follow approaches that are beneficial in achieving the pre-established research objectives.

A pragmatic researcher strives to reconcile both objectivism and subjectivism, facts and values, different contextualized experiences, accurate and rigours knowledge. They do these by considering theories, ideas, concepts and hypothesis in order to solve an existing problem. Pragmatic research starts with a problem, instigated by doubts and a sense of something went wrong (Elkjaer and Simpson, 2011). During pragmatic research, researchers focus on utilising the tools offered by both positivist and interpretivist philosophies and they tend to remain reality-oriented by constantly focusing on the research problem. Pragmatic researchers believe that there are multiple ways of interpreting the world and no single method or point of view can give the entire picture as there are multiple realities. However, it does not mean that pragmatist researchers always use multiple methods rather they use the methods that are reliable, well-founded, creditable, and relevant (Kelemen and Rumens, 2008). Nonetheless, given that pragmatic studies require the higher intervention of the researcher, success pragmatic research is highly dependent on the capabilities of the researcher.

3.2.3.4. *Philosophy selected for the research and justification*

This study adopts the interpretivist philosophy as the nature of this study is humanistic and subjective as it is interested in understanding the dynamics of organisational strategies and the challenges faced by NAC. As previously discussed in earlier chapters, the aviation industry of Nepal is one of the least researched areas. With very little prior studies in the research context, developing hypotheses and testing them would not be the most suitable approach. Rather, an interpretive study that focuses on identifying new insights is more relevant. This study focuses on understanding the perceptions and experiences of the employees, agents, customers, and experts of the Nepalese aviation industry, which can be best achieved through an interpretive study.

Interpretive studies are generally elaborative, and they tend to focus on deeper issues. This research focuses on identifying the challenges faced by NAC as well as to assess the critical success factors of the organisation. The respondents of the study will involve senior management members of the organisation and it is concluded that using an interpretive approach will allow the researcher to extract highly rich data from where challenges faced by NAC can be understood in greater detail. Given that a very few numbers of studies are previously conducted on NAC, a positivist approach is deemed unsuitable for answering the research objectives.

3.3. Research Approach

Whilst conducting research, researchers that adhere to different philosophies tend to follow different approaches. Positivist researchers follow a reductionist approach where they gradually reduce less relevant information in order to produce a theory whilst interpretivist researchers generally take a holistic approach by considering a large number of variables. The first approach is known as a deductive approach whilst the latter is known as an inductive approach. Below, both approaches are briefly described.

3.3.1. Deductive Approach

The deductive approach is associated with the positivist research philosophy and is often referred to as a scientific research approach (Saunders et.al, 2012). This research approach

involves answering the research question by breaking the research problem into multiple hypotheses and answering the research questions by whether accepting or rejecting the developed hypotheses (Wilson, 2014). Under this approach, researchers generally conduct a systematic literature review in order to have a wider grasp of the research domain and thus to deduce hypotheses that are based on available empirical evidence.

Although this kind of approach is highly popular in the domain of natural science as well as the medical science due to the generalizability and replicability of the findings, this is sometimes criticized as inappropriate for answering social science questions. This is primarily due to this approach not providing flexibility to incorporate new insights during the process of data collection and analysis (Saunders et.al, 2012). Besides, this approach is also criticised for preventing researchers from collecting in-depth information.

3.3.2. Inductive approach

The inductive approach is followed by interpretive researchers and it is highly used in the field of social science. During this approach, researchers take a holistic approach and consider a wide range of factors and variables for developing theory. This approach is found very effective in the areas where little previous studies have been conducted and there is no need for generalising the findings to a wider context (Saunders et.al, 2012). Through this approach, the interpretive researchers can extract a rich set of data by giving careful considerations to the emotions and feelings of the actors such as respondents and researchers. This approach, however, is criticised for higher respondent bias which eventually leads to the findings being unreliable Wilson (2014). Nonetheless, if a researcher is very competent, these elements of biases can be significantly reduced (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

For the purpose of this research, after giving careful considerations to the nature of the research question and the philosophy is selected for the research, an inductive approach is considered as the suitable approach for theory creation. This is because this research involves understanding the perceptions of various organisational actors such as senior management members, general employees, customers, agents, and experts. Furthermore, the research context (NAC) is one of the least investigated areas which will prevent the researcher from forming adequate hypotheses based on the existing literature evidence.

3.4. Research Design and Strategy

3.4.1. The selected research design for the study and justifications

Research design is a comprehensive blueprint for collecting, measuring, and analysing the research data in order to achieve the research objectives (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). An effective research design consists of information related to sources of data collection, data analysis techniques, and strategies to deal with ethical concerns (Saunders et.al, 2012). There are three key research designs, namely quantitative research design, qualitative research design, and mixed methods research design.

Quantitative Research design is usually associated with positivism and it uses highly structured data collection techniques (Saunders et.al, 2012). It is normally associated with the deductive approach mainly focusing on testing hypotheses and theories. Qualitative research design is usually associated with experimental and survey research where data are collected through the use of questionnaires, structured interviews, or structured observations.

Qualitative research design, on the other hand, is usually associate with Interpretivism philosophy (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). In this design, the researcher needs to make sense of the subjective and socially constructed meanings and interpret the phenomena that are being studied. These kind studies are often referred to as naturalistic research as the researcher needs to operate in natural settings or research context in order to establish trust, participation, access to meanings and in-depth understanding. Quantitative research design is usually associated with the inductive approach where a naturalist and emergent research design is used to build a theory or to develop a richer theoretical perspective. However, some qualitative research designs use the deductive approach to test the existing theory using deductive procedure (Yin, 2014). Qualitative research design is associated with various strategies including action research, case study research, ethnography, grounded theory, and narrative research.

Finally, mixed methods design combines both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques and analytical procedures. It might use deductive, inductive, and abductive approach for theory development (Tashakkari and Teddle, 2010). Mixed method research design is a combination of various ways of quantitative and qualitative techniques that range from simple, concurrent forms to more complex and sequential forms. The ways in which

qualitative and quantitative methods can be combined have led to many variations of mixed-method research design.

As previously discussed, this research follows an interpretivist-inductive approach for answering the research objectives. Therefore, a decision was made to follow the qualitative research design for this research. This was due to the phenomena in this research are difficult to quantify; in such circumstances, it is preferred to use qualitative research design (Lancaster, 2005). The qualitative approach helps to explore subjects, themes, and categories rather than mere statistical results. The qualitative technique allows collecting data in the form of ideas and opinions of people. It helps to explore and describe issues in death rather than merely testing an existing theory (Brewer, 2007). The use of a qualitative method will help the researcher to better understand the strategic positioning of the NAC, challenges faced by it, and its critical success factors in great depth. Thus, the qualitative research design was deemed most suitable for the purpose of this research.

3.4.2. Research Strategy

A research strategy is a plan of action for achieving the goal of a study. It is a methodical link between philosophy and subsequent choice of method to collect and analyse data (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). The key importance of research strategies is that it enables researchers to achieve a reasonable level of coherence throughout their research, eventually enabling them to answer research questions.

Selection of a suitable research strategy depends on the nature of the research question itself. In the domain of social science, positivist researchers primarily use survey strategy by utilising questionnaire instruments whereas interpretivist researchers use various other strategies such as case study, ethnography, action research, grounded theory and narrative inquiry along with Surveys consisting of instruments such as semi-structured and unstructured interviews, focus group discussions, and observations. This research precisely focuses on understanding the strategic practises and challenges faced by NAC by critically investigating the case of NAC. Yin (2014) states that a case study research is suitable for such kind of investigation. Therefore, a decision was made to adopt the case study strategy in this research.

3.4.2.1. Case Study Research

A case study research is an in-depth inquiry into a topic or phenomena within real-life settings leading to rich, empirical descriptions and development of the theory (Dubois and Gadde 2002; Ridder et al.2004; Yin 2014). The “case” in case study research refers to various entities like a person, an organisation, a change process, an event, and many other types of case subjects. The vital factor in defining case study research is to choose the case study that is being studied and determine the boundaries of the study (Flyvberg, 2011). Once defined, the case study sets out to understand the interactions between the subject of the case and its context (Eisenhardt, 1989; Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2007). According to Yin (2014), understanding the context is vital in case study research.

The case study strategy helps to design in-depth inquiry which helps to understand and identify what and why a phenomenon is occurring. To achieve such insights, case study research draws on qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-methods approaches, to fully understand the dynamics of the case. Although the case study research has been widely used for a long period of time in business and management research, it sometimes has been criticised by for its inability to produce generalisable, reliable, and theoretical contributions to knowledge (Flyvberg, 2011).

The case study research method is often used to study a single organisation in order to recognise the factors involved in specific aspects or behaviours (Ghauri and Gronhaug, 2005). A case study provides a detailed understanding of the particular phenomena, experience, events, or situation that is being studied (Brewer, 2002). The case study is considered as a suitable research strategy when there is insufficient knowledge to establish hypotheses or lack of theorisation. Case study research often involves case comparison; however, a single but comprehensive case study can be as effective as multiple case studies (Yin,1994). The use of single case study will be appropriate in this research in order to reflect the exploratory nature of the research as well as to address the difficulties in developing hypothesis based on prior empirical evidence due to the lack of sufficient literature evidence.

In this research, a single case study is used for answering the research question. A case study research strategy is considered appropriate when researcher inductively describes, explores, and explains the phenomena being examined in real-life settings with the aim of adding or developing new aspects of the existing theory in a particular area of the research (Yin, 2003).

The earlier chapters reviewed the current situation of NAC (the case of the study), revealing a significant knowledge gap due to lack of research. Although NAC is going through a problematic period, it is not clear why this situation emerged. Therefore, choosing NAC will provide opportunities to the researcher to closely analyse the factors that have been impacting the growth of NAC.

3.5. Data Collection

Any research must select an appropriate data collection method as it is the source of information. There are two different sources primary and secondary data collection while undertaking any research. An empirical study must combine both data collection sources to explore certain phenomena, answer research questions, and solve the issue of the research (Lancaster, 2005).

Primary data, for exploratory research, requires data collection from either qualitative or quantitative methods or from both (Lancaster, 2005). In this study, the case study strategy is used and qualitative methods are chosen instead of quantitative methods. The phenomena of this research are difficult to quantify. Qualitative primary data collection techniques will provide a better understanding of phenomena where it will explore and describe issues rather than testing a certain theory (Brewel, 2007). Yin (1989) emphasizes that proof for case studies comes from six sources namely Documents, archival records, interviews, direct observation, participant's observation, and physical artefacts. Qualitative methods offer extensive choices of data to be gathered and provides a better understanding of the current strategic situations of NAC.

On the other hand, secondary data is the source of information that is already available on various databases. Saunders et al (2012) has created three main subgroups that capture a full variety of secondary data, namely document-based, survey-based, and those compiled from multiple sources. Where documents consist of text which includes organisational databases, organisational communications, blogs and non-text consists of media account, radio voice, and recordings. Likewise, surveys consist of censuses which include government census, census of employment, continuous and regular surveys such as family spending, labour market, and organisation, and ad hoc surveys include government surveys, organisational surveys, and academic surveys. Similarly, multi-source consists of snapshot and longitudinal where

snapshot includes data compiled in, financial times, government publications, books, journals, big data sets and longitudinal includes data compiled in industry statistic and reports.

For the purpose of this research, the case study strategy is used involving both primary and secondary data that help to explore NAC's internal and external environmental factors as well as the challenges faced by the organisation. In order to collect the primary research data, in-depth semi-structured interviews are conducted. Prior to discussing the approach followed doing the interview process, the section below now details upon the sampling techniques followed during the research.

3.5.1. Sampling

A sample is a subset of the total population and it must be considered in all research studies (Saunders et al, 2012). It is occasionally possible to collect data from the entire population which is termed as 'census'; however, for most studies, it is impossible to collect data from the entire population due to restriction of time, money, and sometimes access. Different sampling methods enable a researcher to reduce the amount of data to be collected. Sampling methods are of two main types: probability and non-probability. Each category has a number of different techniques in order to select the most suitable sample in the context of the given research (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Wilson 2011; Bryman, 2012).

According to Ritchie et al (2003), Perry (1998), Stake (2000), and Eisenhardt (1989), qualitative research uses non-probability sampling method for the selecting the sample for the study. In business and management research, the probability sampling technique is not highly popular due to either the lack of clarity regarding the sampling frame or the probability sampling being inappropriate for answering the research objectives. Non-profitability sampling, on the other hand, is the alternative method that has a range of various sampling techniques including subjective judgement. Methodologists in the qualitative research have reached a general consensus concerning sampling for qualitative studies that selection for case studies should be undertaken based on purposive sampling as opposed to random sampling (Denzin and Lincoln, 2000). Similarly, in the support of purposive sampling, Eisenhardt (1989 p.537) argues that "random selection of cases is neither necessary nor even preferable".

3.5.1.1. Selected sampling techniques and justifications

The purposive sampling technique involves selecting a sample that is particularly informative, readily available, and can provide information that answers the research questions. It is vital for the researcher to use judgement to select cases that will best answer the research questions and meet the objectives. Purposive sampling is sometimes also known as judgemental sampling. The power and logic of selecting purposive sampling lie in selecting information-rich cases for an extensive and in-depth study (Patton 2002, p.230; Stake 2000, p.446). It is often used while working with small samples such as case study (Neuman, 2005).

The logic in which research strategies base for selecting purposive sampling depends upon the research questions and objectives. This study uses a theoretical sampling strategy for purposive sampling. Theoretical sampling works in hand in hand with purposive sampling as the former often leads to the latter (Silverman 2005; Bryman and Bell 2007; Glaser and Strauss 1967; Strauss and Corbin 1998). In theoretical sampling, the researcher has to have the idea of where to sample. The groups and categories in theoretical sampling will be selected on the basis of their relevance to one's research questions, one's theoretical positions, and explanation or account which one is developing. Theoretical sampling provides a more specific and clearer objective for the general concepts of purposive sampling. Therefore, purposive sampling serves as means and theoretical sampling determines the ultimate purpose of sampling.

This study uses purposive and theoretical sampling for identifying cases that were information-rich while conducting qualitative case studies. This study aims to study the phenomena in an organisation and seeks to uncover new constructs or add new insights to theoretical perspectives. Therefore, purposive sampling would ensure that key constituencies of relevance to the subject matter were covered. Moreover, this study also utilises elements of the snowball sampling technique for recruiting respondents that are most suitable for answering the research objectives. During the data collection process, respondents were requested to refer researchers to further respondents that are suitable for answering the questions of the researcher. This enabled the researcher to extract highly relevant and valuable information.

3.5.1.2. Sample size

Unlike quantitative research, there is no clear evidence regarding the required sample size for qualitative research. In qualitative inquiry, the logical relationship between sample selection technique and the purpose of the research is vital where generalization is made to theory rather than population (Saunders et al, 2012). However, many research textbooks recommend continuing collection of qualitative data such as conducting interviews until they reach the state of data saturation (Eisenhardt 1989, p.545; Saunders et al, 2012). Likewise, there is general agreement that a qualitative study should have 5 to 30 interviews that are expected to be undertaken (Creswell, 2013; Saunders et al, 2012). Similarly, Saunders (2012) has summarised limited guidance for the various type of study where 5 to 25 semi-structured or in-depth interviews sample size are expected. Nonetheless, the suggestion made by the researchers are indicative and a researcher must focus on the data saturation aspect over the number of interviews. Besides, the depth and length of each interview are also crucial as they determine the quality and amount of data collected.

In this research, the researcher gave very careful consideration to data saturation aspects and continued to collect further data until new insights were being discovered. Besides, the data was collected from various parties, which resulted in a further variation of the responses. The length and depth of interviews varied as individuals that are in the strategic decision-making positions were interviewed for a longer period in comparison to the respondents such as general employees, agents, and customers. For the purpose of this research, a total of 47 semi-structured interviews were conducted.

3.5.2. Semi-structured interviews

The interview is a powerful conversation between two or more people where the interviewer is required to established rapport as well as ask concise and unambiguous questions to which the interviewee are willing to respond and listen attentively (Perry, 1998; Fontana and Frey 2000; Patton 2002; Sekaran 2000; Denzin and Lincoln, 2000; Saunders et al., 2016). Interviews help researchers to ask purposeful questions, gather valid and reliable data, and listen to answers to explore more or redefine idea if research question and objectives are not fully formulated. Interviews may contain highly structured and standardised questions, or they may be informal or unstructured questions (Healey and Rawlinson, 1994). Different categories of

interviews include structured interviews, semi-structured interviews, and unstructured or in-depth interviews (Saunders et. al, 2012).

Semi-structured and in-depth interviews are used to gather qualitative data whereas structured, standardise interview are used to gather qualitative data. Semi-structured and in-depth interviews are used in exploratory studies and normally used for case study strategy (Saunders et. al, 2012). Semi-structured and in-depth interviews help researchers to provide vital background or contextual material for the study and they are highly useful in inductive approaches.

This study uses semi-structured interviews to collect qualitative research data. Semi-structured interviews consist of a list of questions and themes that need to be covered, unlike in-depth interviews where it is not required. Semi-structured interviews give freedom to the interviewer to amend questions, add questions, change the question, and ignore questions that have been already been addressed (Saunders et.al, 2012). For the purpose of this research, three sets of semi-structured an open-ended interview questions were developed. One set of questions were used to collect data from NAC employees whilst the others were used to collect data from customers and agents. The researcher used his judgement during the interview process to refine and amend interview questions as necessary.

The interview questions were derived from the previous empirical studies of Bitelmal (2010) on strategic challenges that airport are facing to gain competitive strength and of Yusoff (2008) who conducted a research on strategic management in the public sector of local authority in Malaysia. Reviewing the questions used by past researchers and contextualising them allowed the researcher to develop questions that can best answer the objectives of this research.

3.5.2.1. Selection of the respondents

Whilst recruiting the respondents for the research, careful consideration was given to the size of the sample. Though many researchers focus on data saturation for selecting the relevant sample size, Kvale (2007) argues that too many interviews can lead to the misinterpretation of data. Whilst determining the suitable number of respondents, it is important to give careful considerations to what is being studied (Mintzberg, 1979) and what is necessary for achieving the research objectives. Besides, it is also important to give considerations to various factors

such as the availability of time and resources (Lincoln and Guba 1985; Strauss and Corbin 1998; Patton 2002, Silverman 2005; Saunders et. al 2007). Although different types of research studies may consist of different numbers of interviews, Perry (1985) suggests 35 to 50 sample size for doctoral research collected from different hierarchy which he describes a role thumb that can assist research design.

In this research, a total of 47 respondents were interviewed. 27 of them were the employees of NAC (the CEO, 9 department directors, and 17 general employees). The remaining 20 respondents were external to the organisation. External respondents included one expert in the aviation industry, 7 ticketing agents, and 12 customers of the aviation sector in Nepal. Chapter 4 of this thesis includes more information regarding the interview process as well as the reasons for selecting particular respondents.

The interviews were tape-recorded using a digital application. Saunders et al. (2016) suggest recording interviews as a good practice mainly because in the events of confusions the recordings can be heard again. Furthermore, recording interviews can also help to reduce researcher bias. Prior to the interview, the respondents were informed about the research, assured anonymity their responses, and requested to sign a participant information sheet. The respondents were comfortable with interviews being held in Nepalese language and the researcher believed that conducting interviews in the Nepali language will help the interviewee to answer the questions more appropriately. The interviews were initiated with broad questions where the researcher remained highly flexible to establish rapport with the interviewees.

3.5.2.2. *Analysis of the research data*

An interpretive researcher must fully understand the collected qualitative data within the context of the research in order to be able to meaningfully analyse them. Constructing meaning from qualitative data can be challenging as these meanings are principally derived from words rather than numbers and words may have multiple meanings under different circumstances (Saunders et al., 2016). Therefore, the quality of qualitative study depends on the interaction between data collection and data analysis to allow meaningfully to explore and clarify with great care. The non-standard data are likely to be large in volume and complex in nature that needs to be confronted by the mass of paper or electronic files. These will need to explore, analyses, synthesis, and transform to address research objectives and answer research questions

(Hubner, 2007). As this research falls under the interpretivist continuum, a manual thematic analysis approach within content analysis will be used for analysing the research data. A decision is made to not to use NVivo in this research after considering time and resources implications associated with using it. Chapter 4.3.2 details upon the process that is followed doing the analysis of the research data.

3.6. Reliability and Validity

Reliability and validity are the central elements for ensuring the quality of a research study in natural science and quantitative research in social sciences. Reliability assessments are conducted to assess the replicability of findings (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016) whereas validity assessments are conducted to identify that measurement instrument are capable of measuring the research variables (Saunders et al., 2016). However, reliability is often considered as philosophical and technically inappropriate in relation to qualitative research based on interpretative assumptions where reality is regarded as being socially created and multi-layered.

There are three ways where a qualitative study can be compared in the concepts of reliability and validity to be able to demonstrate the quality and comparable status of a qualitative study. Firstly, if the research has a rigours description of the research design, methods, and context that others may replicate similar studies. However, it is always not necessarily intended to be replicated as it will reflect the socially constructed interpretations of participants in particular settings at a particular time conducted. Secondly, there are parallel versions formulated “dependability” for reliability, “credibility” for internal validity and “transferability” for external validity (Lincoln and Cuba, 1985). The dependability means recording all the changes to produce a reliable and dependable account of emerging research focus that may be understood and evaluated by others. Likewise, creditability means building trust and rapport with participants to collect sufficient data. It also includes checking data, analysis, and interpretation of data with participants. Similarly, transferability involves providing a full description of research questions, research design, context, findings, and interpretation where the reader will have the opportunity to evaluate transferability in another setting. Thirdly, to ensure and judge the quality of qualitative research (Cuba and Lincoln, 1989, 2005; Lincoln et al., 2011) formulated authentic criteria as an alternative to validity. Authentic criteria promote

fairness by representing all views of the respondents, raise awareness, generate learning, and bring about the change.

Validation is the process of authenticating research data, analysis, and interpretation to establish their credibility. There are two techniques namely triangulation and participant or member validation that will help to verify research data collected. Triangulation involves using more than one source of data or methods of data collection to verify the validity of research data, analysis, and interpretation (Saunders et al., 2016). For an interpretivist research, triangulation helps to add depth, breadth, complexity, and richness to the research (Denzin, 2011; Denzin and Lincoln, 2011). Participants validation or member validation are some of the techniques to verify data by allowing participants to review their responses. This can be done in various forms such as showing interviews transcript, stores account, research interpretation of participant's data as well as observations and other notes (Cayla and Arnold, 2013).

For ascertaining the validity of the research findings, multiple measures were deployed. In this research, research design, methods, and context are rigorously described. Besides, the researcher developed trust and rapport with all participants through communication from emails and social media before any data collection process started. All the participants were provided with the participant's information sheet and consent form which consisted the detailed information about the research. It provides information about why the research is being conducted, what will happen to the data, and provided information about their privacy and rights. The research data were validated by showing the interview transcripts to participants.

3.7. Ethical Considerations

In any research study, consideration of relevant ethical factors is essential for not only to comply with the requirements of the research project but also to ensure the reliability of the findings. Saunders et al. (2016) state that the reliability of the findings is significantly enhanced if respondents are assured confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. All key ethical principles were carefully followed during the completion of this research. Below, key ethical considerations made during the research study are presented.

Avoidance of harm: During the process of data collection, all considerations were made to ensure respondents were not harmed both mentally and physically. The respondents were not

asked questions that they may potentially find distressing. Besides, the anonymity of the respondents is also maintained so that any evidence given by the respondents cannot be used against them.

Informing respondents: All of the respondents were fully informed about the purpose of the research and implications of participating in the research. The rights of the respondents such as voluntary participation, right to withdraw, etc were fully communicated. No respondent was forced to participate in this study, and they were allowed to terminate the interview at any time should they feel uncomfortable in answering certain questions.

Respecting the dignity of the participants: All care was taken to ensure the dignity of all participants was respected and maintained during the process of data collection. The researcher used his interpersonal skills to build rapport with the respondents and make them feel comfortable.

Safety of the researcher: During the process of data collection, all measures were considered to ensure the safety of the researcher. The interviews were taken in secured locations within NAC and the researcher avoided asking questions that may potentially trigger anger in the respondents.

Security of the collected data: The collected raw data was stored securely in a password-protected computer and it was only available to the researcher. The collected data will only be used for analysis and will not be given to a third party under any circumstances. Upon completion of this research, the raw data will be securely destroyed. All the respondents were fully informed about the data management process prior to the interviews.

3.8. Limitations of the Research Design

The study is perfect. This study also has its limitations which may impact the findings of the research to an extent. Some of the key limitations of the research design of this study are stated below:

- **Lack of sufficient prior research in the area of study**

Although many studies are already conducted in the aviation industry, the number of studies that precisely focused on the strategic aspects is limited, therefore this area of study is still

considered as relatively new. Besides, previous studies conducted in NAC is extremely limited. These may have impacted the process of designing interview questions, possibly impacting the richness of data. It is possible that the results are may not have been able to address all strategic factors in this research.

- **Single method study**

This research followed the interpretive philosophy utilising interview for data collection. Qualitative research is sometimes criticised for the lack of generalisation and replicability of the findings. Given that a limited number of respondents were considered in the study, it is possible that findings are not replicable in the wider context. Besides, the use of a single method reduced the opportunities related to the triangulation of the findings.

- **Access to information**

The researcher was denied access to sensitive financial information such as the cost of purchasing aircraft, revenues, and the grants received by NAC. In the absence of this information, the researcher will not have a complete understanding of the organisation. This may lead to some of the strategic recommendations not being highly appropriate to the organisation.

3.9. Summary

This chapter critically reviewed different research philosophies, approach, methods, strategies, and data collection instruments in order to develop the most appropriate research design for the research project. Whilst determining the suitable tools for the research, the requirements of the research along with its objectives were carefully assessed. Based on the analysis of a wide range of tools and techniques, this study was designed as an exploratory study where it adopts epistemology with subjective continua with interpretivism philosophy via inductive approach using qualitative research design and single case study strategy. The case study strategy was used in the research to facilitate in-depth analysis of the phenomena. The primary source of the data collection was semi-structured interviews from the employees, agents, and customers of NAC as well as an expert in the Nepalese aviation industry.

After carefully considering the time and resource limitations as well as the requirements of the research, a non-convenience sampling method combined of purposive and snowball sampling techniques were selected in this chapter. This chapter also dealt with the reliability and validity, ethical aspects, and the possible limitations of the research design. The following chapter now deals with the analysis of the research data and the findings of the research.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

4.1. Introduction

This chapter systematically presents the process followed during the collection and analysis of the research data as well as the findings. Prior to collecting the main research data, a pilot study was conducted. The process followed during the pilot study is also discussed in this chapter. In order to effectively answer the research objectives, the findings of the research are presented under three key themes: strategic analysis of NAC, challenges faced by NAC, and the critical success factors of NAC. The figure below presents the structure of this chapter.

FIGURE 4-1: STRUCTURE OF CHAPTER FOUR

4.2. Pilot Study

Prior to collecting the main research data, a pilot study was conducted to ensure the interview questions designed for the research can actually collect data that can help to achieve the research objectives. The pilot study was also conducted to understand whether or not the interview process adopted by the researcher needed modification in order to extract the most relevant information from the participants.

As a part of the pilot study, a total of 3 participants were interviewed. As the study aimed to collect data from different parties such as employees of NAC, ticketing agents, and customers of NAC, one participant from each category was interviewed during the pilot study. Following pilot interviews, the researcher then reviewed the collected data and assessed them against the research objectives. Overall, the collected data met the requirements of the research and therefore, no major revision on the interview questions was made. However, the researcher noticed that some of the respondents had difficulties in understanding some academic terms such as strategic positioning. Therefore, the researcher briefly revised the interview questions and further simplified the terms that the interviewees faced difficulties in understanding.

4.3. Process of Main Data Collection and Analysis

4.3.1. Data Collection

After reviewing the findings of the pilot study and finalising the interview questions, the main research data was collected. A total of 47 respondents were interviewed and the length of interviews varied depending on the designation of the respondents. As the questions used for collecting data were semi-structured and open-ended, whenever the respondents were providing valuable information, the researcher was then able to prolong the interview and extract further details. As previously stated in the earlier chapters, this research aimed to conduct a strategic analysis of NAC from different perspectives. Therefore, different sets of interview questions were developed for different sets of respondents.

Firstly, employees of NAC were interviewed. The respondents included the CEO, 9 department directors, and 17 general employees. The interview with the CEO lasted approximately 90 minutes whilst the interview with the department directors lasted for around 45 minutes. The interviews with general employees were kept brief with each lasting from 15 to 20 minutes.

The interview with NAC employees focused mainly on identifying the strategic position of the company as well as the challenges faced by the company in recent years.

Secondly, an expert was interviewed to further understand the challenges faced by the company as well as the ways in which they can be addressed for enhancing the organisational performance. The expert was one of the previous CEOs of NAC and he also previously worked as an expert advisor for one of the top domestic airlines in Nepal. The interview lasted for approximately 70 minutes. Finally, 7 ticketing agents and 12 customers of NAC were interviewed for approximately 10 minutes each, primarily to understand the challenges faced by the organisation.

The collected research data was then transcribed and translated. The researcher is a native speaker of the Nepali language as well as a good user of the English language. In order to further ensure the translations were accurate and true reflections of the interviews, an additional bilingual peer who speaks both English and Nepali reviewed the transcripts and verified it. The data was then coded, and themes were generated for answering the research objectives. The section below now discusses the process followed during the qualitative data analysis.

4.3.2. Qualitative Data Analysis

An extensive review of the literature suggested that there is no standard approach for analysing the qualitative data. Miles and Huberman (1984, p.11) quote that there are few shared ground rules during the analytical process; however, a qualitative researcher has a high degree of flexibility during the process of analysis.

“We have few agreed-on canons for qualitative data analysis, in the sense of shared ground rules for drawing conclusions and verifying their sturdiness.”

The process of analysing qualitative data highly depends on how a study is commenced and whether it is inductive or deductive. Therefore, the researcher must remain vigilant during the process of data analysis and be mindful of axiological implications (Tesch, 1990; Coffey and Atkinson, 1996). Various researchers have developed and used specific analytical producers such as inductive-based producers or deductive-based producers to analyse qualitative data (Johnson, 2004; Corbin and Strauss, 2008; Yin, 2009; King, 2012). There is also a third approach to analyse qualitative data that does not follow a specific theoretical approach rather

it follows the general principle of analysing qualitative data. Below is the process in which data can be analysed using this approach.

- a. Comprehend a large and disparate amount of qualitative data.
- b. Incorporate related data drawn from different transcripts and notes.
- c. Identify themes and patterns from them for further exploration.
- d. Develop and test theories based on the themes and patterns identified.
- e. Draw and verify conclusions.

Talking all these things on board, this study will use a generic approach for the analysis of the qualitative data. There are various generic approaches outline by many researchers such as Dey (1993), Miles and Huberman (1994), and Robson (2011). Miles and Huberman (1994) outlined a generic approach to analyse qualitative data known as data display and analysis approach where the process consists of three concurrent sub-processes namely data reduction, data display, and drawing and verifying conclusions. The figure below presents an approach of qualitative data analysis as outlined by Miles and Huberman (1994).

Content redacted due to copyright restriction. Original figure can be found in Miles, M.B and Huberman, M. (1994) *Qualitative Data Analysis*; London: Sage Publications

Source: Miles and Huberman (1994)

As presented above, data reduction is the process of reducing and organising a large volume of data by the means of simplifying, summarising, focusing, and converting data from interviews

transcripts and documents. The main aim of this process is to transform data and summarise it. The vital part of data reduction is data coding and categorising data according to different themes and key areas. Data display, on the other hand, is the process of organising and matching reduced data into reasonable and understandable shapes. It is done with two main families of data display: metrics and networks. Metrics are generally tabular form that consists of row and columns and rows where data are entered in appropriate cells for further data analysis. Whereas, Networks is the collection of nodes or boxes that are linked with arrows that indicate the relationship where the boxes contain brief description or labels to indicate variables or key points from the data. The last step is the conclusion (drawing/verifying), that is also known as the interpretation phase where the analysed data entails giving meaning and making sense. (Creswell, 2003; Miles and Huberman, 1994)

4.3.2.1. Coding Research Data

Data coding is a useful tool during the qualitative analysis as it involves reviewing transcripts and giving labels to key themes or meanings that emerged from the data that can possibly help to answer the research questions. Coding systematically identifies the indicators of different perceptions, preferences, behaviour actions, understandings, or events from the people interviewed (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Bryman and Bell, 2007). While coding the research data of this study, the predetermined research questions were taken as principal guidelines and the core categories from emerging themes were established in which descriptive labels were assigned for all themes. Several core categories that provided concepts and constructs for answering research questions were identified. The table below presents the key themes noted during the coding process.

TABLE 4-1: QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS THEMES

S.N.	Themes
1	Factors impacting the external environment of NAC
2	Factors impacting the internal environment of NAC
3	Political challenges faced by NAC
4	Operational challenges faced by NAC
5	Critical success factors of NAC and the Nepalese aviation industry

Source: The Author

4.3.2.2. Labelling of the Respondents

As previously stated, this research consisted of 47 respondents. The respondent group was made of the CEO of NAC, department directors of NAC, general employees of NAC, customers, ticket agents, and an expert in the Nepalese aviation industry. In order to protect the anonymity of the responses, the unique position or any personal information that can be used to identify them or their responses are not disclosed in this thesis. The table below presents the way in which key responses of the respondents are quoted in this thesis for protecting the anonymity of their responses.

TABLE 4-2: RESPONDENTS LABELLING

S.N.	Respondents	Referred to as (in this thesis)
1	CEO	Senior Manager
2	Department Director	Senior Manager
3	Other Employees	Employee
4	Customer	Customer
5	Ticketing Agent	Ticketing Agent
6	Expert	Expert

Source: The Author

The section below now presents the findings of the analysis. The findings are depicted under three key themes: strategic analysis of NAC, challenges faced by NAC, and the critical success factors of NAC in order to best answer the research objectives.

4.4. Strategic Analysis of Nepal Airlines

Chapter 2 of this thesis highlighted and discussed different tools that can be used to conduct a strategic analysis of an organisation. The tools included PESTEL analysis, SWOT analysis, Value Chain Analysis, Porter's Five Forces Analysis, and so on. In order to conduct a strategic analysis of NAC, SWOT and PESTEL analyses were conducted. A decision was made not to conduct the Value Chain Analysis after carefully considering difficulties related to applying this tool in the service industry such as airports and airlines. Besides, the availability of the

financial data was extremely limited, preventing the researcher to conduct a detailed Value Chain Analysis. Moreover, time limitation was also one of the reasons for not selecting this analysis. The section below now presents the findings related to a PESTEL and SWOT analysis of NAC.

4.4.1. PESTEL Analysis of Nepal Airlines Corporation

PESTEL is a commonly used framework for analysing the external organisational environment. During a PESTEL analysis, six external factors, namely political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal factors and their influences on the organisation is reviewed. Below, the research findings related to each factor is depicted.

4.4.1.1. Political

The analysis of the qualitative data revealed that political factors within macro-environment impact the NAC' operations, regulations, and strategic direction. This is primarily because NAC is currently operating under Nepal Government. Political appointments and political influence on the decision-making processes were identified as two key political factors that influence the organisation.

- **A culture of political appointments**

NAC has been repeatedly subjected to political influence as many political parties throughout history made political appointments of people and treated NAC as a cash cow from where money could be generated for own gain, making NAC as a funding organisation for their parties. One of the respondents believes that the failure of the NAC is due to political appointments of the Executive Chairman, CEO, and even Directors.

As being a government organisation, there are political impacts. There have been situations where broad of Directors, CEO, and Executive chairman were appointed via through a political appointment process.

(Senior Manager)

One of the respondents, who is an employee of NAC, believes that the policies that government makes in regard to aviation, tourism, and buying and selling acts have impacts on the operations of NAC as it is a government-owned organisation. The respondent asserts that the influence of the government has been detrimental in recent years for the further development of NAC.

Government policies do have an impact on the operation of NAC. The political impact should have been positive however it has been negative in recent years.

(Employee)

NAC suffers greatly from the culture of political appointment of unskilled and inexperienced people in the higher managerial level where strategic decisions are made. Political appointment of relatives, friends, and families of political leaders has been a common practice for decades in NAC. The ruling government favours the employee supporting their political party and employees are prompted on the basis of their political affiliation rather than their capabilities. Besides that, employee unionism has negatively affected the growth of NAC. Most of the employees seem to have an affiliation with one of the major political parties and loyal towards the leader of the party rather than NAC. This has developed a culture where employees disobey their managers in the organisation. Below are some of the key responses of the respondents highlighting this.

Government Political appointment of unskilled and inexperienced people, making their people, relative chief of NAC, interfering even in the director level is a common practice within NAC.

(Senior Manager)

We have a culture affiliating with different political parties, whichever party comes to the government, they only favour employees that support their party.

(Employee)

- **Politically motivated decision-making processes**

Some of the respondents highlighted that the government department and ministers that are responsible for the making key decision of NAC are ignorant and treat NAC as Nepal Telecom, Nepal Electricity Authority, etc. However, the business environment in which NAC operates

is completely different. It appears that ministers and other government officials underestimate the importance of the national flag carrier in the economic growth of the country. For example:

Finance minister and assistance finance minister are ignorant, and they have not understood the importance of NAC and treat NAC as it same as Nepal telecom and Nepal Electricity Authority.

(Senior Manager)

There are political interferences in buying aircraft as well, and this is the main reason behind the growth of NAC being stagnated.

(Senior Manager)

It was observed that the decision-making process of the NAC is greatly affected by political influence. This is preventing the airline from developing strategies that are competitive and in line with the global aviation sector. Political factors have severely impacted the day-to-day operations and management of the organisation, eventually leading to organisational failure.

Based on the above evidence, it is interpreted that the impact of political factors on NAC is extremely high. Political interference not only have stagnated the growth of the organisation, but it also has been one of the key reasons behind the organisation losing the trust of the customers. The culture of political appointment has also led to increased corruption.

4.4.1.2. Economic

The analysis of the research data suggested that economic factors also highly influence NAC. The respondents suggested that the disposable income of Nepali people is gradually improving; therefore, many people can now afford to travel via air instead of the road. Besides the number of people going abroad for various purposes such as tourism, business, and leisure has significantly increased as well in recent decades.

- **Improving living standards of the Nepali People**

The respondents believe that steady flow of remittance, growth in tourism, people travelling abroad for various purpose, and the growth in trade within the country has contributed towards

the growth of the airline industry in Nepal. The airline industry is expected to grow more with the completion of the second international airport which is currently under construction, construction of several big hotels, the increase in air connectivity through the implementation of new/revised air agreement, and the government's Visit Nepal 2020 initiatives. The views shared by some of the respondents on economic impacts on NAC are given below:

The economic condition of the Nepalese people is improving and there is growth in the number of people travelling around in Nepal as well as aboard for tourism, business and leisure purpose.

(Senior Manager)

The remittance that is coming to our country and the people that are abroad for various purposes has increased the use of airlines in Nepal.

(Employee)

Besides, there has been a steady rise in regard to Nepali people going abroad for holidays. One of the respondents suggested that people travel abroad for religious, business, and health treatment purposes. This has eventually increased the demand for air travels, eventually increasing the demand for services being offered by NAC. Airlines industry in Nepal has also benefited for the lack of good road system, challenging geographical locations, and the lack of other forms of transportations.

The culture of people going abroad for holidays has increased.

(Ticketing Agent)

People are using airlines for various purposes such as religious, business, and health treatments.

(Customer)

The economic development of the country had contributed positively towards the development of the airline industry altogether and this has led to the emergence of several new domestic airlines. Similarly, numerous international Airlines such as Qatar Airways, Emirates, Thai Airways, and Air India have increased their number of flights to Nepal. It appears that, despite the sharp increase in air travel, NAC has not been able to benefit tremendously from it.

- **Air travels being perceived as daily necessities than luxuries by the public**

During the primary data collection process, the respondents mentioned changes in people's perception of air travel and affordability, contributing to an increase in air travel. Until the past decade, air travel was seen as luxurious travel. This perception is now quickly changing as more and more people are perceiving it as the essential mean of transportation. The increasing number of middle-class people are able to use airlines due to various factors like budget airlines, time-saving, and being able to travel in the places where other means of transportation are unavailable. Airlines also have become more accessible these days with cheaper fares, easy to book flights, and an increase in the number of flights.

More middle- class people are able to use the airline industry due to air travel being more affordable.

(Senior Manager)

If there is an option to travel with NAC or other airlines, I will choose to travel with NAC as it gives me feel of home as soon as I enter a NAC plane.

(Customer)

There are various cultural and religious places in Nepal where visiting them with air travel is more convenient and faster.

(Senior Manager)

The popularity of the airline industry has also increased due to people living abroad, travelling for education, work, and sports. As observed in the dataset, Nepali people are more likely to travel with NAC rather than travelling with other airlines as it gives the feeling of being home without being at home. NAC, being the national flag carrier, has a strong competitive advantage over other airlines among Nepalese customers.

- **Access to international lenders**

The respondents highlighted that NAC requires fleet expansion and doing so requires funding. Domestic borrowing could be costly with, in some cases, costing as much as 10% APR, whereas NAC might get external funding for less than 5% APR. This gives NAC an edge over domestic competitors as many of the domestic competitors may not be able to borrow at lower

rates. The respondents suggest that it is vital for NAC to explore external funding opportunities with lower rates so that they can expand the fleet and gain an edge over the domestic competitors.

Airlines industry is a fragile industry with very thin profit margin and expecting a big profit margin in the airline industry is being unreasonable. Therefore, it is crucial that NAC focuses on increasing the volume of services.

(Senior Manager)

The interest rate of domestic funding is high, which more is 10 % whereas external funding might come under 5%.

(Senior Manager)

Therefore, in order to achieve a strategic advantage of the current environmental circumstances, the higher management of NAC should focus on exploring options of increasing the fleet and thus, increasing the range of services available.

Based on the analysis of the research data, it is concluded that the Nepalese aviation market is rapidly growing due to the growth in peoples living standards. Air travel is now increasingly being seen as an everyday necessity rather than a luxury. These changing circumstances are favourable to NAC, and if effectively materialised, they can transform the organisation entirely. Therefore, the impacts of economic factors are identified as high.

4.4.1.3. Social

The analysis of the research data indicated that social factors have an influence on the operations of NAC. The respondents suggested that an increase in tourism for various purpose like visiting religious places, holiday, globalization, and employment has significantly contributed to the growth of air transportation in Nepal.

- **Growth in Tourism from inside Nepal and abroad**

The respondents suggested that tourism has grown within the country and from abroad due to the culture of people travelling for holiday is getting popular and people around the globe as

well as inside Nepal are aware for various tourist destinations through media. Tourism has become a much more diverse customer market due to the increasing income of the middle-class population and decreasing costs of air transport.

The culture of people going for a holiday within Nepal and abroad has increased and that has contributed to the growth of the tourism sector.

(Ticketing Agent)

People are using airlines for various purposes such as religious, business, and health treatments. People from abroad come to Nepal to visit various religious places and middle-class income is increasing and the cost of air transport is decreasing; therefore, there is an increasing use of air transport.

(Customer)

Nepal is the land of beautiful mountains, lakes with many historical and religious importance. These have contributed to the growth of national and international tourism.

(Senior Manager)

- **Globalization and people travelling abroad for various purposes**

The respondents share the view that globalization and people travelling abroad and within Nepal has increased the growth of air passenger in NAC. Globalization has resulted in the cross-border expansion of the businesses that has resulted in an increase in people travelling as well as seeking employment abroad.

The trend of people travelling abroad has increased due to people travelling abroad for higher education, employment, and settlement. It has increased the number of passengers that travel via air.

(Employee)

The cost of air transportation is decreasing and it now has become like other means of transportation rather than a luxury, so more people are using it as it saves time as well.

(Ticketing Agent)

Therefore, the culture of holidaymaking, increase in tourism, people travelling abroad for higher education, employment, settlement and health purpose has increased the number of people travelling via air transport, ultimately favourably impacting the aviation industry.

4.4.1.4. Technological

NAC, despite being the national flag carrier of Nepal for over 61 years, has a record of very little technological advancement. Based on the analysis of the research data, it was identified that the company lacks modern equipment. However, on the bright side, it was observed that NAC has launched an electronic ticketing system, allowing customers to book their tickets online.

- **The lack of modern aircraft and ground handling equipment due to unavailability of Funding**

The main asset of any airline company is its aircraft. NAC, despite being in the business for over six decades, merely has a handful of aircraft with most of them very old and unreliable. After 27 years, the organisation finally bought a few more aircraft recently, but they were poorly built Chinese aircraft, unreliable and required frequent maintenance. Besides, the organisation was unable to fly those aircraft for the majority of the time as the airline did not have skilled pilots to fly them.

NAC also provides ground handling services in coordination with the Tribhuvan International Airport (TIA). The respondents suggested that the quality of ground handling services is really poor as the equipment used by NAC are outdated and sometimes cannot ensure the total safety of employees as well as customers. Besides, due to the lack of modern and efficient equipment, employees are having to conduct many tasks manually, eventually delaying the service delivery as well as putting themselves at risks. For example:

The lack of technical equipment that is vital for aircraft and customer health and safety is one of the major challenges of NAC.

(Senior Manager)

Employees are forced to do the job that was supposed to be done by machines.

(Employee)

This lack of necessary equipment has prevented the organisation from materialising its full potential. NAC was recently recognised as an IATA ground handler; however, due to the lack of necessary resources, the organisation only handles few airlines.

As NAC was recently recognised as an IATA ground handling certificate member it has raised the level of NAC ground handling services. It has positive impacts on our operations as we are more likely to get more ground handling contracts from new airlines. Airlines previously used to audit and verify our ground handling services independently. However, after IATA certification, we never have such kind of hassles.

(Employee)

Therefore, the lack of modern equipment is identified as one of the technological factors impacting not only the operations but also the future growth potentials of NAC. The impact of the technological factors on the organisation was identified as very high as aviation industry relies heavily on the use of new and sophisticated technologies. NAC has made very little investment for improving the necessary equipment: both physical and virtual in the past 27 years. The respondents suggested that it is essential for the organisation to acquire the latest technologies in order to make services more efficient. However, acquiring such equipment requires the financial support of the government as NAC is a government organisation. Based on the analysis of the data, it was witnessed that most of the past governments focused on extracting money from the organisation rather than investing in its growth. Thus, the lack of technological development due to a lack of funding was identified as a technological barrier of the company.

4.4.1.5. Environmental

The analysis of the research data identified the impacts of various environmental factors on the operations of NAC.

- **Hub airport located at a challenging geographical location**

The hub airport of NAC is far below the international standard and it is considered as one of the risky airports in the world in terms of the risk of crashing during both landing and takeoff. Previously, there have been several accidents involving TIA, resulting in loss of life of many passengers. The airport is surrounded by mountains and there are limited ways of landing. The margin for error is extremely low as a small inconsistency can lead to fatal accidents. Due to the landscape of the airport, NAC often struggles with finding pilots that are capable of flying to and from TIA.

The airports of Nepal are located in such extreme geographical locations if I ask a pilot where do you find easy landing in an entirely new airport or Lukla. They will say the forth.

(Senior Manager)

Nepal aviation industry is been blacklisted by European commission due to safety concerns.

(Senior Manager)

The runways of some rural airports are so short that aircraft have to be forcefully stopped.

(Employee)

- **Less concerned Nepalese public regarding environmental impacts of air travel**

Air travel is now increasingly being criticised for being one of the primary reasons for increasing air pollution and global warming. Airline companies are required to meet environmental standards. NAC, however, has not come under scrutiny for its environmental impacts, primarily due to environmental issues are still not the priority for developing countries like Nepal. Nonetheless, if NAC is to fly in countries with higher requirements for environmental protections (i.e., European Union aviation safety standards), the aircraft must meet the required criteria. The respondents suggested that the pressure to reduce the impacts of the aviation industry on the environment is low.

The awareness regarding the environmental impact of airlines is almost non-existent among the people of Nepal.

(Customers)

There are various other issues that the government needs to tackle before any actions are taken in the context of environmental pollution by the airline industry.

(Senior Manager)

Nepal is a country that is still naturally rich with various sources like forest, lakes, rivers, mountains; therefore, people have not thought critically about the impact of the airline industry in the environment.

(Expert)

4.4.1.6. Legal

NAC it's facing various legal challenges, one of the key challenges, as observed in the dataset, is Nepal government procurement act which the airline must follow while making any purchase.

- **Nepal government procurement act being unclear and ineffective**

The act was criticised by the respondents for making the decision process lengthy and sometimes unviable for purchasing necessary equipment.

The process of buying an aircraft is a bit of hassle; otherwise, we would not have been limited to only four big aircraft.

(Senior Manager)

There is no clear procedure to buy aircraft and that is the problem. Even though we follow the same procedure we might be caught in corruption controversies.

(Senior Manager)

Yes, we do have issues in purchasing aircraft like we have to follow government public procurement act and it is bit technical and we have one type of requirement. Like if I

want one type of aircraft, we cannot ask we need this aircraft these type of problem we face.

(Employee)

Based on the analysis of the research data, it was identified that the aircraft purchasing process can take up to five years as the organisation must undergo a lengthy time-consuming process in order to meet the legal requirements. Besides the current legal requirements for purchasing new aircraft are not clearly defined, this has resulted in the management of the organisation being accused of corruption on multiple occasions. The problem was not limited only to purchasing of aircraft, the organisation also has to follow a similar process whilst purchasing ground handling equipment. This resulted in a significant loss of time during the buying process, eventually impacting the organisation's competitive status.

4.4.2. SWOT Analysis

The analysis of the research data revealed various strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with NAC. Below, some of the key findings are presented.

4.4.2.1. Strengths

- **The national flag carrier and a government organisation**

Nepali people have positive sentiments towards Nepal Airlines due to the organisation being the national flag carrier. People are willing to travel with NAC rather than other airlines both nationally and internationally. Due to this, being a government organisation, the government has the obligation to fulfil the financial requirements of the organisation. This is one of the key strengths as if a supportive and responsible government comes into power, the organisation can get a significant financial boost that can transform NAC entirely in a short time.

As the national flag carrier that is established for more than 60 years and it has an emotional connection with customers, Nepalese people trust NAC.

(Customer)

If NAC was a private company, it would have been bankrupted by now.

(Expert)

The organisation has a long history as its been in operation for over six decades. Besides, it has been receiving support from the government time to time which has kept the company afloat. If the company is led by the right management and a government that genuinely favours the growth of the organisation comes in power, NAC can leverage its government ownership as well as the trust of the public and turn the company into a successful and profitable organisation. Therefore, being a national flag carrier as well as operating under the government of Nepal is considered as one of the key strengths of the organisation.

- **Involvement in both domestic and international markets**

NAC currently flies to seven international destination and many rural domestic airports where other airlines normally do not fly to. The current strategy of NAC in the domestic market is service-focused, where the company mainly aims to provide services to Nepalese people rather than making profits. Whereas, the company's international flights are related to its market growth strategy.

We fly in some of the most remote areas where other airlines do not. We do this only to serve our people, not to make profits.

(Senior Manager)

Our ticket prices in the domestic sector have always been lowest you can get in the market as it is all about service. In terms of international flights, it is about expansion, so we do offer competitive prices to compete with competitors.

(Employee)

As the respondents highlighted, the fare company offers is the cheapest in the domestic market. This has helped the company to build a reputation of a company that provides tickets at affordable prices. Besides, NAC offers competitive fares internationally as well. This is identified as one of the strengths of the organisation as it is accustomed to flying in challenging destinations as well as established into offering competitive fares. These can give great leverages when developing and implementing competitive strategies.

- **Introduction of the electronic tickets booking system**

The discussion with respondents also revealed some of the encouraging facts and development regarding NAC. The organisation has incorporated electronic ticket booking system since July 2017 allowing thousands of passengers to book their tickets online. NAC has an online booking system where all the major debit and credit cards payments are taken in collaborations with a bank in Thailand. Previously, there was a problem of making payment through credit card while purchasing tickets from NAC but after the introduction of payment gateway – a payment system for online ticketing, purchasing tickets through credit card has been possible.

We launched our online booking in July 2017.

(Senior Manager)

In order to facilitate online booking, we introduced different software like MRO and Arms.

(Employee)

There was a problem with accepting credit cards as there was no merchant bank in Nepal, so we worked in collaboration with a bank based in Thailand to resolve this.

(Senior Manager)

Although it was launched late, NAC has finally launched an electronic ticket booking system in order to meet the market demands. This has given the organisation some competitive edge both nationally and internationally, hence it is considered as one of the strengths of the organisation.

4.4.2.2. Weaknesses

- **Poor management of debt**

The analysis of the research data identified a managerial weakness in terms of management of the organisational debt. The respondents suggested that although the organisation can access lower-cost debts, they are heavily reliant on funding through the domestic market where the interest rate can be as high as 10% annually. If the organisation strategically approaches

international lenders, the interest rate can be reduced down to as less as 5% annually. The higher interest rate has led to a large monthly repayment, eventually reducing the profit and financial capabilities of the organisation.

The loan we took from the internal organisation has a higher interest in the market which is above 10% however we could get the same loan from an external organisation for less than 5%.

(Senior Manager)

NAC should explore loans from both internal and external organisations to get a competitive interest rate.

(Senior Manager)

The loan interest we pay for such a big amount is extremely high.

(Senior Manager)

Some of the respondents also suggested that such high repayment can put the organisation into an extremely challenging situation in the events of unfavourable market movements such as financial depression. Therefore, the current practises involving poor management of debt is identified as one of the key weaknesses of the organisation.

- **Poor intra-organisational coordination**

As observed in the research data, there is a lack of coordination, cooperation, and a sense of togetherness between NAC and TIA. The coordination is lacking from both sides. Other international airlines are given an advantage over NAC even though TIA being the hub airport of NAC.

Other international airlines are given more priority over NAC in all aspects of airport facilities.

(Employee)

NAC should have been given almost priority in its own hub but that is not the case.

(Senior Manager)

Such lack of coordination with the hub airport is one of the key weaknesses of NAC as this not only leads to impacting the day to day operations of the organisation but also results in poor customer services as well as lack of customer trusts.

- **Poor organisational culture leading to brain drain**

The findings of the data analysis suggested two main factors, namely political party affiliation and unionism as main reasons for power struggle within NAC. The culture of party affiliation and unionism has been the main obstacle for coordination between employees. The employees feel that they are more associated with the party rather than the organisation. The culture of employees affiliating with different political parties is very prominent within the organisation primarily because the organisation is highly affected by various political factors such as political appointment and political influence in employee promotion and transfer processes. It appears that employees feel it is impossible to progress within the organisation without being associated with an influential political party. This has led to extreme unionism, eventually reducing the coordination between employees.

There is a sense in the employee where they feel that they are affiliated with the political parties rather than the organisation.

(Employee)

The unionism of political parties in the organisation has a negative impact on employee's coordination and cooperation.

(Senior Manager)

The cooperation and coordination between different department are not great and the people affiliated with some parties are more likely to be favoured.

(Employee)

The skills, knowledge, experiences, hard work, and honesty do not count in this organisation, all that counts are affiliation with political parties.

(Employee)

Due to extreme political influence, the employees are not valued based on their merits and capabilities rather they are valued based on what political figure they know. This has led to a situation of brain drain as capable and talented employees are seeking career growth opportunities elsewhere. This has severely affected the growth potential of the organisation; thus, it is identified as one of the key weaknesses of the organisation.

- **Poor Infrastructures – single international airport leading to traffic congestion**

Due to TIA being the only international airport of Nepal, NAC's operational costs have increased. The issue of traffic congestion in TIA is usual as planes normally have to be on hold for 1 to 2 hours on a regular basis for landing space. This has increased the operating costs of airlines flying to TIA including NAC. This has also affected the punctuality of services, resulting in loss of consumer trust in the airline. The reasons behind such delays were identified as maintenance, no parking slots, no sufficient x-ray machines, and no available belts.

Traffic congestion is one of the many main problems NAC is facing. Aircrafts being on hold increases the fuel cost and causes timing issues. Fuel cost is one of the major expenditures of airline companies.

(Senior Manager)

Traffic congestion has caused delays of our flights on multiple occasions.

(Senior Manager)

Being a small international airport, there are parking slot issues, untimely maintenance issues, and limited baggage belts.

(Employee)

We do not have all the required facilities in the airport such as sufficient x-ray machines and conveyor belts.

(Employee)

Due to the poor availability of necessary infrastructures, it will be challenging for the organisation to deliver services in a large volume, provide excellent services to customers, and

to maintain the consistency of the services. These weaknesses, therefore, pose strategic challenges for NAC in order to develop growth strategies.

- **Nepalese aviation industry being blacklisted by the European Union**

In December 2013, the Nepalese aviation industry was blacklisted by the European Union citing safety reasons. This resulted in all Nepalese airlines being restricted to enter European airspace. This tarnished the reputation of NAC as well as of the aviation industry in Nepal. Customers lost confidence in Nepalese airlines companies and NAC lost access to its lucrative destinations. The European Union ban has an impact on route expansion plans of NAC.

NAC has been banned from flying in the European skies due to Nepal Aviation safety concerns.

(Expert)

The perception of the customers towards safety and security has changed since the European Union introduced a ban.

(Senior Manager)

The ban by the European Union is affecting the entire aviation industry in Nepal. Yet, the government of Nepal appears to be sleepwalking and making no attempts on removing the ban by meeting the safety requirements of the European Union. One of the respondents suggested that if the government make some necessary changes, they can work towards getting the ban removed.

The Government knows that if it gets civil aviation authority and airport authority working as two different entities than half of the work to get rid of the ban is done.

(Expert)

Growth of an airline company, particularly in the current time, requires coordination with various sectors. Given the market is extremely competitive, an aviation company loses much of its competitive edge if questions related to safety arise. Therefore, the ban by the European Union is considered as one of the key weaknesses of NAC.

4.4.2.3. Opportunities

- **Market expansion in both national and international markets**

NAC already operates in 25 domestic and 7 international destinations. As of 2018, the market share of NAC was 2.78% in the domestic market and 11.3% international market (Prasain, 2019). NAC is an established organisation with a long history of operating in various countries across the globe. The respondents suggested that merely by increasing the fleet size and making the operations more efficient, the organisation can significantly expand its market both domestically and internationally. Besides, most of the domestic airlines do not serve in destinations that are challenging or not highly profitable.

The main factor is market, NAC has a great market and now it needs sufficient equipment. So, if there are large markets and the necessary equipment, there is a high possibility of sustainability.

(Senior Manager)

With the expansion of the fleet, NAC can tap the previously untapped market and increase its domestic markets exponentially. The increasing economic condition of Nepal and the increasing disposable income of people contribute favourably towards the fleet expansion strategy of NAC. Therefore, opportunities to expand market both domestically and internationally is identified as one of the key opportunities for the organisation

- **Existing air agreements with 38 different countries**

The respondents highlighted that NAC currently has agreements with 38 different countries, allowing them to resume services in any of those countries without having to undergo further agreements. This provides a great opportunity for the organisation to expand the market on those countries and to identify highly profitable routes. As a large number of Nepalese people are living abroad, NAC can target countries with high Nepalese diaspora. Besides, Nepal is well known for its touristic attractions as well. This also allows the organisation to identify countries from where they are highly likely to have tourists. Therefore, the current air agreement with 38 different countries is identified as one of the opportunities of the organisation which can be utilised to expand the market.

NAC has air agreement with 38 different countries and we can fly there immediately with the fulfilment of all the requirement.

(Senior Manager)

NAC has no issue with the market expansion as it has air agreement with 38 different countries

(Senior Manager)

- **The increasing trend of Nepalese travelling both within the country and abroad for various purposes**

There has been a growth in the people travelling domestically as well as internationally. Nepalese people, these days, travel within the country for various purpose like business, religious, and healthcare. Air travel is increasingly being seen as everyday travel as opposed to being seen as a luxury - which used to be the case a few decades ago. People of Nepal also travel around the world for various purpose like work, education, and holidays and there has been a growth in numbers year by year. Furthermore, the number of tourists coming to Nepal is increasing year by year as the country had recently seen some peace and stability.

The economic wellbeing of Nepali people has improved and the people travelling for leisure, business, education and health are growing.

(Senior Manager)

Due to the company being the national flag carrier of Nepal, the Nepalese people have some sort of emotional attachment with the company.

It is remarkable that NAC has survived 61 years in aviation and has developed emotional connections with people of Nepal.

(Expert)

Such attachment is identified as one of the great opportunities of the company as given that the number of Nepalese people travelling both internally and abroad has increased, this emotional attachment can give leverage to NAC over its competitors - which can eventually be used for market expansion.

4.4.2.4. Threats

- **Instability of the government**

Given that NAC is a government corporation, the changes in the ruling government significantly impacts NAC. With a new government coming to power, there is always a strong likelihood that the top management of the NAC will be changed too. This creates an environment of uncertainty as the organisation cannot implement its long-term visions. Due to political rivalry, it has been observed on multiple occasions that the new managers give priorities towards fulfilling their political prophecies rather than making the organisation successful. Besides, as the decisions of NAC must go through the approval of the government, the constant change in government makes the decision-making process lengthy, ultimately affecting the competitiveness of the organisation. As Nepal has barely witnessed a stable government since the arrival of the democratic governance system, and this has severely affected the performance and growth of NAC, the instability of the government is identified as one of the key threats of the company.

As soon as there are changes in the government, there will be changes happening in NAC as the Executive Chairman, CEO or directors are changed.

(Senior Manager)

The government of Nepal is unstable and as soon as there is a change in government, the business plan of NAC are always put on hold.

(Employee)

The instability of government has negatively impacted the revival strategy of NAC, the decision-making processes are lengthy.

(Senior Manager)

- **Growth of competitors in both domestic and international markets**

Private airline companies in Nepal have a stronghold of the market share in both the domestic and the international market. Other international airlines that operate from Nepal have a strong international presence with a large economic scale and strong brand image. Airlines like Qatar, Emirates, Air India, and Turkish airways are few of the many big companies operating in the

international market connecting Nepal. Similarly, in the domestic market, there are companies that have a huge fleet with modern aircraft that flies in almost all of the profitable destinations. As the number of people travelling through air is increasing, the competitors of NAC are increasing too. As the competition is increasing, the prices are gradually coming down, eventually affecting the only competitive edge NAC has against its competitors.

The big airline companies like Qatar, Emirates, Turkish, and Air India operate in the international market

(Senior Manager)

NAC's domestic and international market share is very little where I think it 3 per cent in domestic and 12 per cent in international market share.

(Senior Manager)

4.5. Key Strategic Challenges faced by NAC

The third objective of this research was developed to assess the challenges faced by NAC across various organisational aspects. In order to identify the challenges faced by the organisation, the CEO of the company, directors, customers, agents, and expert were interviewed. The analysis of the research data identified various challenges faced by the organisation which are presented and discussed below. As identified from the analysis, key challenges faced by NAC fall under two main categories: political and operational.

4.5.1. Political Challenges faced by NAC

4.5.1.1. Increased corruption due to the political appointment system

NAC has always been marred by political appointments of employees in every level of the organisation. The respondents believe that political connections play more important roles in the promotion of employees rather than their merit, skills, and experiences. The appointment of the executive chairman is always political. The culture of nepotism and discrimination is highly prevalent in NAC where relatives, family, and supporters of political parties get employments and promotions. NAC is made as a cash cow by political parties where supporters

could be recruited and collected funds from. The responses below show that the culture of political appointment is highly prevalent in the organisation and the organisation is being exploited by political parties.

People are able to get the position they desire through political connection rather than their experience and merit.

(Employee)

Political appointment of relatives, family, friends and political parties' supporters is nothing new in NAC.

(Senior Manager)

After the 1990s, NAC is being treated as a cash cow of political parties.

(Expert)

Nearly all of the respondents suggested that political appointment not only has limited the growth potential of the organisation but also has been the root reason of corruption. The culture of political appointment has severely impacted the organisation as it is now facing the shortage of workforce that is motivated and qualified. Some of the respondents suggested that this has led to the right people not being in the right place as well as employees not being knowledgeable enough for the industry.

We should get skilled employees rather than quantity and NAC does not have the right people in the right place.

(Employee)

There is a lack of experiences and knowledgeable employees required for the growth of NAC.

(Employee)

Therefore, the culture of political appointment is identified as one of the key challenges faced by the organisation.

4.5.1.2. *Employees' political affiliation and extreme unionism leading to the lack of collaboration across departments*

Under the current circumstances, given that the organisation is facing extreme political influence, it now appears that career progression within the organisation is almost impossible if employees are not members of political parties. This had led to a situation where nearly all of the employees are associated with different political parties. Besides, extreme unionism can also be witnessed within the company, eventually reducing the power of directors and managers for implementing new changes. This has also led to issues such as the lack of cooperation, coordination, and communication across departments. An employee working in the accounting department shared his view as follows:

The political interference and involvement are present in buying aircraft, recruiting employees, and allocating pilots to fly both domestic and international destinations.

(Senior Manager)

Respondents that work in the human resources and commercial department also shared the view.

It feels like employees working in this airline have a perception of working for the government rather than the organisation.

(Employee)

There is a lack of cooperation, coordination, and communication across the employees because of affiliation with certain political parties and union, feeling of working for different governments.

(Employee)

The employees that support the ruling government are often treated more favourably.

(Senior Manager)

As seen above, many employees working in NAC have a perception of working for the government of Nepal rather than NAC. An employee working in NAC feels that employees that support the ruling government get favourable treatments. The culture of political appointment has been spreading within the organisation as a disease that is eating the

organisation inside out. In the extremely competitive industry such as aviation, unless all of the employees work towards the organisational goals collaboratively, an airline such as NAC cannot sustain. Therefore, employees' political affiliation and extreme unionism are identified as strategic challenges that NAC is facing.

4.5.1.3. Instability of the government

NAC has paid a heavy price due to the instability of the government. Whenever a change in government takes place, they tend to interfere NAC and appoint their preferred person as the executive chairman of the company. They also make changes in terms of organisational plans and goals, and in often cases, they abandon ongoing developments. This sort of interference has prevented NAC from growing and becoming competitive in the industry. The government also interferes operational activities such as purchasing new aircraft. The respondents highlighted that, on multiple occasions, NAC was forced to cancel the ongoing aircraft purchase process, eventually causing to lose millions of dollars already paid as a deposit. Some of the key responses of the respondents regarding this are listed below.

As soon as the government changes, the change happens in our organisation where the executive chairman is changed, directors are reshuffled, and business plans are kept on hold.

(Employee)

Political interference in the process of buying aircraft is one of many reasons NAC growth is stagnated.

(Expert)

As the government changes, there is always a problem with the purchase we make. There were times where we had to cancel the deposit that was made for aircraft purchase due to changes in government.

(Senior Manager)

Due to the unstable government, many times in the history of the organisation, we had two executive chairmen at the same time. One with power and another one without –

which ultimately destroyed the culture of the organisation as employees were divided and supported different chairmen.

(Employee)

The political situation of Nepal has been unstable for a long time and changes in government happen frequently. The cost of frequent government changes on NAC is extremely high as the organisation is unable to plan, develop organisational strategies, and execute them in an effective manner. Besides, the constant change in leadership of the organisation has put the organisation into chaos. Therefore, instability of the government is identified as another challenge faced by NAC.

4.5.1.4. Outdated government public procurement act for airlines

NAC must follow government procurement act to buy aircraft where it needs to undergo a tender process and buy the cheapest aircraft in the market. Some of the key responses from the employee that are directly involved in the process of purchasing aircraft are stated below:

We have a top down approach in our organisation with command and control. There is a framework which we receive from the Board of Directors and Chairman about purchasing of aircraft and the type of aircraft that are needed and we work in according to that.

(Employee)

We have issues in purchasing aircraft as we have to follow government public procurement act and it is bit technical. If we have one type of requirement like if we want one type of aircraft, we cannot ask that we need certain types of aircraft.

(Employee)

I do not think the current process is effective. It takes more than 2 years to purchase an aircraft following the current process and within that time frame, other private airlines will bring multiple aircraft. It is not about the problem with the organisation, but it is like how the government works and we have to follow every rule. We have to comply

with each and every ministry requirement due to being a government organisation of Nepal.

(Employee)

All of the respondents suggested that NAC has an outdated procurement act which slows the process of buying aircraft as it takes multiple years just to finalise the process of buying. This has affected the competitiveness of the airline both in the domestic market as well as in the international market. Therefore, the current procurement act is identified as one of the key challenges being faced by NAC.

4.5.2. Operational Challenges

After analysing the qualitative data, numerous operational challenges were also identified. The challenges included from lack of fleet to lack of effective recruitment processes. Below, some of the key operational challenges are presented.

4.5.2.1. *The lack of sufficient fleet, spare parts, and ground handling equipment*

NAC has only 7 functional aircraft, which is not sufficient for covering a wide range of national international destinations. One of the department directors of the company suggested that the lack of fleet is causing a tremendous challenge to the corporation and it is vital that the fleet size is increased in order for the organisation to become more sustainable.

The main factor is the market. Airlines is been guided by market and needs sufficient aircraft so if there is a good market and aircraft, there is a high possibility of sustainability. If one of them is missing, then the operating cost will be high for airlines, risking the future of the business.

(Senior Manager)

The corporation is also facing a tremendous challenge in terms of repairing the aircraft when a malfunction occurs. Aircraft breakdown occurs on a regular basis as most of the aircraft are either old or of poor quality. One of the respondents suggests that Chinese aircrafts currently being used by Nepali airlines are not reliable, eventually leading to last-minute cancellations and thus loss of consumer trust.

We have a problem with Chinese aircraft in our domestic sector as we are not punctual and reliable, and we do not have new aircraft for the domestic sector.

(Employee)

Besides, NAC also lacks sophisticated technical equipment required for supporting airport management as well as maintaining health and safety standards of consumers.

There is a lack of technical equipment that is vital for aircraft and customer health and safety.

(Senior Manager)

People are forced to do jobs that are supposed to be done by machines.

(Employee)

It appears that top managers are aware of the necessity of sophisticated machines for day to day activities. However, they blame the lengthy buying processes for lack of such equipment. For example:

Buying sophisticated equipment that is required for aircraft and health and safety of customers is a lengthy process being government organisation.

(Senior Manager)

Based on the above evidence, the lack of sufficient fleet and other machinery was identified as one of the key challenges the organisation is currently facing.

4.5.2.2. *The lack of effective research and development practices*

Similar to the majority of government organisations in Nepal, NAC also lacks an effective practice of research and development for developing new business strategies and assessing their effectiveness. This lack of effective research and development practice has prevented the organisation from innovating as well as identifying ways in which service standards can be further improved. Some of the respondents that are currently working in the field of planning

highlighted lack of expertise, experience, and knowledge leading to them not being able to produce effective business plans.

We are the planning department, but we do not have any software, system and guidelines in place. We are doing all of our works on the basis of information search from the internet, past research from NAC, etc.

(Employee)

If we talk about departments, there is a gap. For example, there is no one in my department who has knowledge of fleet planning and I am new one as well. We do lack expert, experienced, and knowledgeable employees in our department, there is no one to guide us and we do research in our own way.

(Employee)

Director in our department keeps changing, which causes a problem as some of them do not have enough knowledge in our field.

(Employee)

Nepal airline lacks a good research team that is responsible for the business plan of the airline. Although the airline appears to have some form of a research team, it was clearly visible that the research team did not have necessary tools for conducting research, nor they have required experience and expertise in the area for being able to produce business strategies that are effective. It was observed that the research team rely on outdated information that is available on the internet for developing business plans.

It appeared to the researcher as if the team was placed there just for the sake of formality, not to make an actual difference. The business planning department conducts research on fleet expansion, market expansion, purchasing, and phasing of aircraft and equipment. This research identified that one of the key reasons behind NAC being unable to expand his fleet and develop markets both domestically and internationally was due to the organisation not investing enough in the research and development process by hiring the right people and the right tools. Therefore, the lack of effective research and development practises was identified as one of the key challenges faced by NAC.

4.5.2.3. *The lack of coordination with Tribhuvan International airport*

The analysis of the qualitative data revealed that there is an extensive communication gap between Nepal airline and Tribhuvan International Airport (TIA) - the home airport of NAC. It was identified that there is a lack of co-operation, coordination, and knowledge sharing from both sides. NAC is the national flag carrier and Tribhuvan International Airport is the main hub of NAC. Both organisations operate under the Nepal government. The respondents suggested that international and other domestic airlines get treated more favourably than NAC. As observed in the dataset, employees working in the passenger handling department and the commercial department highlight the lack of coordination between these two organisations as one of the key challenges faced by NAC.

Other international airlines are given more priority over NAC in all aspects of airport facilities.

(Employee)

NAC should have been given high priority in its own hub airport but that is unfortunately not the case.

(Senior Manager)

There have been few cases where other international flights were given permission to take off even though airports were closed for maintenance; however, NAC had to cancel a flight for having departing time 5 minutes later than the closing time of the airport.

(Senior Manager)

During the interview, the researcher also observed that the reason behind TIA giving a little attention to NAC may have been due to the lack of punctuality and reliability of NAC itself. Besides, NAC only accounts for a very little percentage of the total revenue of TIA. Nonetheless, it is important that airlines and the hub airport coordinate effectively in order to enhance the quality of services as well as to improve the organisational performance. Therefore, the lack of coordination between NAC and TIA is identified as one of the key strategic challenges being faced by NAC.

4.5.2.4. *The lengthy and ineffective employee recruitment process*

Being a government company, NAC has a lengthy recruitment process. The recruitment of employee for NAC is conducted by another government organisation called “Lok Sewa” (Civil Service), who conducts exam for the candidate of NAC. Candidates are then called for interviews in NAC once they pass the written exam. People recruited through Lok Sewa tend to have no technical skills. A recruitment manager of the company believes that hiring through Lok Sewa is an inappropriate recruitment process for NAC. For example:

The recruitment process is wrong in NAC where employees are hired from Lok Sewa, from there you will not get employee as airlines industry needs as NAC is a technical company and we require technical people too, rather we get unskilled people.

(Employee)

Similarly, a senior manager responsible for passenger handling department also agrees with the view of the above-mentioned recruitment manager. As he states, the passenger handling department of NAC requires new employees in short notice, which is often difficult due to the lengthy recruitment process.

The recruitment process is not easy, fast, and convenient in NAC as it is a lengthy process. The passenger handling department requires employee as soon as there is an increment in the handling of international airlines. However, the lengthy recruitment process prevents us from recruiting new staff immediately, eventually leading to situations where we are severely understaffed.

(Senior Manager)

Staff recruitment through Lok Sewa is identified as an ineffective process for Nepali airlines as the possibility for recruiting experts through Lok Sewa is slim as many experts do not go through that particular recruitment process, hence unable to fill the vacancy available at the organisation. In order for the organisation to recruit the right people, sometimes they have to headhunt and recruit them directly, which is often prevented by the recruitment system that is currently in place. One of the respondents highlighted the severe shortage of experts within the organisation.

The work we undertake is research for fleet expansion, market expansion, and making business plans for our organisation but we do not have any expert to guide us.

(Employee)

Therefore, given the evidence above, the lengthy and ineffective recruitment process was identified as one of the key challenges NAC is currently facing.

4.6. Critical success factors of NAC

The fourth research objective was developed to identify the critical success factors for NAC. In order to answer this objective, views of all interviewees such as the expert, CEO, directors, employees, ticketing agents, and customers were carefully analysed. Respondents were requested to share their views on how NAC can improve its business performance and become a sustainable organisation. For answering this research objective, the views of staffs at the senior managerial level and the views of expert were carefully considered. Besides, interesting insights of other respondents were also considered. An analysis of the research data revealed that NAC could improve its business process and thus enhance the overall performance in various ways; however, it requires some major changes both within and beyond the organisation. Some of the critical success factors highlighted by the respondents are listed and described below.

4.6.1. Effective fleet management

- **Increasing fleet size**

Airlines industry is highly competitive with some key global players covering a large scale of the global market whilst providing affordable fares and excellent services. In order for an airline to remain competitive, they must provide high quality and punctual services at affordable prices. Doing so requires producing services in high volumes. For a corporation like NAC, with the currently available fleet, it is not possible to ensure high-quality services, large numbers of destinations, and punctuality of services. One of the directors of NAC asserts that having sufficient equipment such as aircraft is crucial for the success of any airline, primarily

because an effective balance of market demand and the available number of aircraft leads to lower operating costs, which is the crucial factor for the success of an airline. For example,

The main factor is market, NAC has a great market and now it needs sufficient equipment. So, if there are markets and equipment, then there is a high possibility of sustainability. If one of them is missing, then the operating cost will be high for airlines then there is a risk of going out of business. The supporting activity like human resource, economic aspects, and competitive market are all secondary.

(Senior Manager)

One of the senior managers of the company argues that due to NAC not having a sufficient number of aircraft, competitors have their monopoly in terms of pricing. This has led to air travel being extremely expensive, eventually adding new challenges for further growth of the airline industry.

We cannot fly to Singapore is due to the lack of aircraft. If the national flag carrier flies to those destinations, the monopoly of other airlines breaks down and the fares can be brought down.

(Senior Manager)

Respondents argue that without having new aircraft, increasing production capacity will be impossible. And without increasing the production capacity, the corporation will be unable to profit regardless of implementing any expert opinions and suggestions. For example:

One of the main challenges of NAC is to increase production capacity which can only be done by increasing the number of fleets.

(Employee)

We can talk about all the strategy, bring any experts of aviation in the world but if there is a lack of sufficient fleet then nothing will work. People need to understand that the basic need of NAC is not fulfilled until we have sufficient aircraft to operate.

(Senior Manager)

Despite being in operation for over 61 years and being the national flag carrier of a country, the organisation is still unable to fund for new aircraft.

- **Securing funding for fleet expansion**

A respondent who is currently working in the commercial department of the company (as stated below) suggests that the company is struggling financially and therefore unable to purchase new aircraft to meet the requirements of the market. It appears that lenders do not trust NAC as the company has a bad track record in terms of maintaining organisational profitability.

We are in the same situation as we were when we were established, we do not have funds to buy aircraft. When we reach out to the lenders, they state that we have not made any progress financially. Otherwise, we would have funds to buy aircraft.

(Employee)

The analysis of the research data suggested that one of the primary steps for moving forward towards the success of NAC is through increased production capacity. However, NAC is not in the financial position where it can fund itself for the purchase of new aircraft. It has to rely on the lenders, and currently, it is being funded from internal organisation of Nepal paying higher interest rates. Nonetheless, given the financial history of the organisation, NAC is not highly trusted by international lenders that offer lower interest rates. Some of the respondents suggested that the lower interest rate can be attained if the government of Nepal becomes the guarantor of the debt. For example:

We have to explore funding options from external lenders as we currently have internal funding with an interest rate of around 10%. If we get external funding, we might get it for less than 5%.

(Senior Manager)

Nepal government has to be the guarantor for the debt required to buy the aircraft for the company to be trusted by the lenders.

(Senior Manager)

- **Enhancing safety and reliability**

Currently, the airline has a reputation of being unreliable and in some cases unsafe too. The organisation serves only a handful of domestic locations and often flights are cancelled with short notice, resulting in the loss of consumer trust. One of the respondents from the commercial department suggested that the organisation should focus on making services reliable so that people can fly with confidence.

The first thing we should do is make customers feel that NAC is a reliable airline where people can fly with confidence.

(Senior Manager)

Customers and ticketing agents also shared the view of the above NAC employee.

Even though I love to travel with the national flag carrier, I personally do not trust NAC as they are not punctual and reliable. Rather, I choose to travel with other private airlines.

(Customer)

NAC does not fly to most of the destination that why we must travel with other airlines.

(Customer)

Customers have a perception that Chinese aircraft are not safe for travel and they are not reliable either.

(Ticketing Agent)

Some more respondents highlight the concern related to the reliability and safety of the services being offered by NAC being the main reason for them not choosing the organisation. For example:

I do not have in faith in NAC that its flight will depart on time, there will be delays cancellations and that is the reason I do not trust NAC.

(Customer)

We sell tickets for private airlines as well as NAC, but we always have to be worried about the cancellation of flights of NAC.

(Ticketing Agent)

Due to NAC not being able to serve many domestic locations, there is a monopoly of private companies, leading to high fares. Besides, the mere few locations being served by NAC are also not very popular due to the lack of trust of customers on the airlines. In order to win back the customer trust, NAC must focus on ensuring the reliability of services, serve a higher number of destinations, and gradually gain the trust of the consumers. In order to do so, the airline must invest in new aircraft and manage them effectively. Thus, based on the findings of the research, one of the primary strategies of the company should be looking for suitable sources of funding for increasing fleet size. Doing so can eventually increase the production capacity of the organisation, leading to improved overall performance. Therefore, effective fleet management is identified as one of the critical success factors for NAC.

4.6.2. Establishing great organisational cultures for attracting talents

- **Ending the culture of political appointment**

The analysis of the research data suggested that the culture political appointment has been a major problem for NAC as more often than not, employees without any necessary expertise, skills, and experience are recruited. In NAC, the Executive Chairman, CEO, Directors, and even general employee are politically appointed without considering their experiences, skills, and knowledge of the airline industry. The respondents suggested that such appointment of inexperienced and unskilled staffs has resulted in organisational failure. For example:

By being a government organisation, there is definitely political impact, there is been context where broad of Directors, CEO and Executive chairman are appointed through political processes.

(Senior Manager)

Political appointment of unskilled and unexperienced people, making their people, relative chief of NAC, interfering even in director levels are common practices within NAC.

(Employee)

Some of the senior managers of the company also agree with the above views.

NAC has always marred in controversy after controversy that is all due to political interference and involvement in everything – from appointing CEO to buying aircraft and leasing them.

(Expert)

The political appointment of Executive Chairmen in NAC has always created chaos as many times NAC had two Executive Chairmen same time: one with power and one without. This created division within the organisation as both chairmen usually supported different political parties.

(Employee)

Due to the unstable government in Nepal, an additional executive chairman was appointed when NAC already had one. This created chaos in the organisation with leaders not being able to implement their business plans. Although the review of the literature indicated that political interference could have some useful outcomes, this was not observed in the case of NAC. The organisation is found to be losing a competitive edge against its competitors as the interest of politicians is more prominent in the organisation than the organisational interests.

- **Controlling the practices of political unionism**

In order to minimise the political influence on the organisation, after critically analysing the research data, it appeared to the researcher that banning employees' affiliation with political parties and ending the culture of unionism could play a significantly positive role in terms of enhancing the organisational performance. This conclusion was drawn based on the responses below

Employees working in NAC have the perception of working for government rather than NAC.

(Employee)

There is a lack of coordination, cooperation and communication due to employee affiliation toward political parties and unison.

(Senior Manager)

Employees here are more loyal towards political parties, politician rather than towards NAC.

(Employee)

The ruling political parties always favour employees that are associated with them.

(Senior Manager)

Due to unison in NAC, there have been cases where pilots do not fly airlines on time, engineers do not carry on work on time, etc.

(Employee)

The culture of political affiliations and unionism have severely affected the organisation as it has been the result of a lack of cooperation and coordination of employees. Due to their affiliation with a certain political party, employees sometimes feel more responsible for their political party rather than the organisation that pays their salaries. Due to the culture of recruiting employee through the political process, people that have certain political beliefs are prioritised over those that have essential knowledge and skills.

Some of the respondents suggested that whilst ending the culture of political appointment, NAC also should focus on operating similarly as a commercial airline. The airline industry is extremely competitive and merely operating as a government organisation, it will be extremely difficult for the company to generate profit and remain sustainable. One of the respondents highlighted that whilst the company was working as a commercial airline prior to 1990, it was performing really well.

When Nepal airline was operating like commercial airlines before 1990, it was a successful company. But after 1990, when it started running like a public enterprise of government, it became the hub of corruption, nepotism, and cronyism.

(Expert)

Even though we are a government organisation, if we run like other government organisation, we cannot be sustainable. A company like us has to make profits to become sustainable.

(Senior Manager)

Therefore, based on the findings of the analysis, it is identified that NAC must focus on recruiting people in a competency-based basis and have the right people in the right place. The only way of achieving this is by implementing a fair recruitment process and ending the culture of political appointment. Doing so will equip the organisation with necessary and skilled human resource, which is vital for an organisation like NAC for sustaining in the current competitive market.

4.6.3. Minimal external interference in the decision-making process

- **Changing Nepal government's current public procurement act**

As a government organisation, NAC must follow public procurement act before making any purchases. The earlier section of this chapter highlighted that due to the bureaucracy required by public procurement act, making purchases such as the process of purchasing new aircraft is very lengthy and, in some cases, it takes over multiple years just to finalise the purchase of an aircraft. The current public procurement act of Nepal government is outdated and irrelevant to a competitive marketplace such as the airline industry. The act requires that the airline must purchase through a bidding process and buy the cheapest aircraft available in the market. This prevents the organisation from purchasing aircraft that meets their requirements. Two respondents that work in senior management positions of the commercial department discuss the difficulties associated with purchasing new aircraft.

We do have an issue in purchasing aircraft as we have to follow government public procurement act and it is a bit complex. Majority of the time, we cannot purchase aircraft according to our requirements.

(Senior Manager)

There is a tendering process in our organisation. As we have Airbus aircraft in our fleet, we would want to buy more Airbus when we purchase new aircraft; however, we cannot guarantee this as everything happens through tendering basis. There has been

concern raised during the purchase procedure of the aircraft, but no real change is yet made.

(Senior Manager)

The complexities caused by the public procurement act was visible in nearly all of the interviews with top-level executives of NAC. One of the respondents, who is also a member of the board of directors of the company, suggested that the current public procurement act is one of the key reasons for the failure of NAC as it prevents the organisation from purchasing new aircraft that can generate profits in the long run.

There is a legal problem with the purchase of new aircraft as NAC has to go through a tender process where it has to buy the cheapest aircraft, this often results in buying aircraft that are old and require extra maintenance.

(Employee)

Given the requirements of the current public procurement act, NAC cannot buy aircraft without going through the tendering process even though there are new and cheaper aircrafts available. The process of purchasing an aircraft is long and has to comply with every ministry requirement. The fleet of NAC is small, yet it has aircraft from 4 different manufactures. This is causing problems with supplier, spare parts, engineer, and pilots as the company needs four different sets of pilots, engineers, and parts as one specialist generally tends to have knowledge about one particular aircraft only. This was observed in the responses of some of the senior managers of the company.

NAC cannot request the government to buy certain types of aircraft as we have to follow the government public procurement acts where we have to go through the tendering process. Due to that and interference of politicians, we have aircraft from 4 different companies. Can you believe an airline company with just 13 fleets has aircraft from 4 different companies? Due to this, there are problems with pilots, engineers who were trained with a certain aircrafts manufacture, and the suppliers who only provide parts for a specific brand.

(Senior Manager)

As we are government origination, we must follow every rule and comply with every ministry requirement. It takes more than 2 years for an aircraft to arrive, which is a long time, especially for us as our production is critically low.

(Senior Manager)

As stated above, respondents believe that the current government procurement act is inadequate and preventing the growth of the organisation. Therefore, minimal external interference is identified as one of the critical success factors for NAC.

4.6.4. Effective planning and development

- **Recruiting expert researchers**

During the interview, it was identified that employees that work within the planning (research and development) department of the organisation were not equipped with necessary skill and experience in order to be able to produce or recommend competitive business strategies. The employees received very little training and they had no experts to supervise or guide them. Besides, they also lacked the tools that are necessary for conducting research. One of the employees working in the planning department stated that they have no access to reliable databases so that they have to rely on the publicly available information on the internet for developing new strategies. For example:

We have to conduct research looking on the previous research done in NAC and research available on the internet. There is a lack of experienced, skilled, and knowledgeable employees in business planning neither we have anyone to guide us during our research.

(Employee)

From the analysis of the research data, it was observed that the airline management has given very little to no importance to training and development of staffs, which one of the crucial tasks for further development of the organisation. Employees working at the organisation felt as if they were neglected by the senior management. One of the respondents currently working at a senior manager level highlighted that although they are responsible for very important organisational activities such as sector expansion and aircraft purchasing, they had not received

any formal activities on how to conduct such activities. The only training respondent received was IATA, which is not sufficient to execute such an important role.

I have only received IATA training and have not received any other training since I am here which is surprising as well as frustrating. I am making various business plans such as sector expansion and aircraft purchase without receiving any training.

(Employee)

Given that NAC's business planning and business development strategies are developed by the planning department, when employees are not effectively trained or have no access to adequate informational resources, it is likely that they cannot develop strategies that are effective. Not providing adequate training and guidance to the employees can also demotivate them, causing further destruction to the organisation. Therefore, NAC must focus on training their employees to an adequate level whilst ensuring that employees involved in planning and development processes. They should also have access to high-quality data and information so that they can make relevant and effective decisions. Besides, the respondents also suggested that the airlines should recruit research experts who can train employees on conducting research effectively. Thus, effective planning and development practices is identified as one of the key factors essential for the success of an airline company like NAC.

4.6.5. Management of people

- **Employee development programmes**

The analysis of the research data revealed that NAC has a very poor culture of employee development and motivation. Most of the respondents stated that they have not received any training apart from the induction training which they received at the time of joining the organisation. The respondents believe that this has limited their personal and professional growth and eventually prevented them from performing at a high level. For example:

I have not received any training since my arrival here two years ago. All I got was an induction class. I believe I can perform better with better training and development programme.

(Employee)

Providing training to employees and further developing them is essential not only to ensure employees perform at their best level but also to ascertain employees are constantly motivated. Trained employees tend to be more confident and this can bring the practice of professionalism within the organisation. When employees are trained to the highest level, they not only tend to be motivated to perform the job, but they are also more likely to remain within the organisation as they are receiving benefits of professional and career growth.

- **Effective rewards and recognition systems**

Some of the respondents stated that the organisation does not have any reward and recognition system in place to encourage well-performing employees.

The reward system in our organisation is non-existent as good performing employees are never rewarded.

(Senior manager)

Motivation comes from the reward that can be financial or non-financial, but I do not think we have that kind of reward system.

(Employee)

After the analysis of the data, it appeared to the researcher that the lack of reward and recognition practices, the lack of career prospects, and the absence of training and development programmes are impacting the organisation directly as the company is unable to attract skilled human resources such as pilots and engineers. Besides, one of the respondents suggested that employees move on to different roles at different organisations after gaining some experience from NAC as they are not incentivised to remain. For example:

We do not have sufficient skilled manpower. Therefore, NAC has to explore the ways to recruit and retain them.

(Employee)

There is a shortage of pilots and engineers in NAC. Many new pilots leave once they gain experience from NAC.

(Senior Manager)

- **Recruiting the right people with the necessary knowledge**

The respondents also highlighted that NAC does not have sufficient skilled manpower such as pilots and engineers. Therefore, they suggested that the company should focus on recruiting experts of the aviation industry and providing them great into incentives to remain within the organisation for a long time. Recruiting experts could be really helpful in areas such as purchasing new aircraft or developing new business plans as the current management of NAC as well as the relevant government members have very little experience on purchasing new aircraft or developing global competitive strategies.

The Government of Nepal is the guardian of NAC and our business plan goes to the government for approval. However, the ministers and people in the government of Nepal do not have experiences of buying and operating aircraft. There is a lack of coordination and which is why NAC did not purchase aircraft for the past 28 years.

(Senior Manager)

Therefore, based on the analysis of the research data, it was identified that NAC must focus on recruiting the necessary skilled human resource, have advanced training and development programmes for their development, and introduce attractive reward and recognition schemes in order to retain them in the long term. Hence, investing in the development of employees is identified as one of the critical success factors for NAC.

4.6.6. Robust internal management

Nearly all of the respondents, in one way or another, highlighted some managerial inefficiencies of the organisation. These inefficiencies included slow decision-making processes, lack of coordination with the government as well as the Civil Aviation Industry, poor internal management, lack of coordination with foreign countries, and so on.

- **Making decision-making processes faster**

Some of the respondents suggested that lengthy processes need to be followed during the decision-making process. Any purposed change must be agreed by the ministry as well as the management of the company. Besides, the decisions must be approved by the board of directors as well which consumes a significant amount of time. For example:

The decision here is not made by a single person as we are a government organisation. The decision is made after an agreement between the ministry and the board of NAC. We send proposal from here, then the management has to approve, following by the board and various ministries. It is a long process.

(Employee)

As the aviation industry is constantly transforming with new changes being brought in every single day, such a slow decision-making process cannot assure the competitiveness of the organisation. The organisation should be able to make most of the decisions following a fast and effective process. It is important that the management of the organisation recognises this and initiates talks with the government in order to make the necessary changes in the legislation.

- **Phasing out the unprofitable aircrafts**

Some of the respondents suggested that the management should focus on phasing out the aircraft that are not profitable to the organisation. NAC has Chinese aircraft in the domestic market, and they incur a lot of operational and maintenance costs. The respondents suggested that such unreliable and costly aircraft should be phased out to reduce the loss of the organisation. For example:

We have problems with the Chinese aircraft in our domestic sector as they break down very frequently. We do not have new aircraft in the domestic sector therefore the old aircraft always increase the operational costs. We have less market share in the domestic market than new private airlines such as Yeti and Buddha.

(Employee)

I am always worried about Chinese aircraft NAC has purchased as there is always news of its safety issues and people normally do not trust the quality of Chinese aircraft.

(Senior Manager)

Echoing similar view one of the key respondents working in the commercial department responded:

We needed new aircraft but purchasing Chinese aircraft was a lightly taken and immature decision as no sufficient research was done prior to buying the aircraft. This resulted in a significant amount of loss to the airline.

(Employee)

The above evidence suggests that the management conduct little research whilst making significant decisions. This has cost the company a large amount of money. A better management practice could have prevented this loss.

- **Decisiveness of the managers**

The respondents also highlighted that internal management cannot take firm decisions, which is necessary for the growth of the organisation. It is essential that the managers can take firm actions against destructive forces both within and outside the organisation.

The internal management has to be strong where it will not shy away from those that are resisting the change.

(Employee)

No airlines can be successful without good internal management, especially when an organisation is struggling.

(Senior Manager)

There has to be strong leadership that can resist the external forces that are against the new changes.

(Employee)

Therefore, based on the analysis of the research data, it was identified that the current management practises within the organisation are not as effective as they have led to huge losses for the organisation. Besides, it was also noticed that senior management cannot make firm decisions and implement them. Therefore, changing the current management practices was suggested as one of the key areas of improvement for NAC in order to enhance its

organisational performance. Thus, robust internal management is identified as one of the critical success factors for NAC.

4.7. Conclusions

This chapter aimed to present the findings of this research and interpret them. The earlier sections of the chapter dealt with the collection and analysis of research data whilst the latter sections dealt with the presentation of the findings. The research findings were based on the data collected from a total of 47 respondents. Respondents included the CEO of NAC, Department directors of NAC, general employees of NAC, customers in the Nepalese aviation industry, ticketing agents of NAC, and an expert in the Nepalese aviation industry. The duration and the depth of interviews varied based on the requirements of the the research. The collected research data was transcribed, coded, and themes were generated by using the thematic analysis approach. During the analysis, three key themes, namely strategic analysis of NAC, strategic challenges faced by NAC, and the critical success factors of NAC emerged.

This study revealed various political and operational challenges faced by NAC. Political challenges include increased corruption due to the culture of political appointment, employees' political affiliation and extreme unionism leading to the lack of collaboration across departments, instability of the government, and the outdated government public procurement act for airlines whilst operational challenges include the lack of sufficient fleet, spare equipment, and ground handling equipment, the lack of effective research and development practices, the lack of coordination with TIA, and a lengthy and ineffective employee recruitment process. This research also identified six key critical success factors for NAC, namely effective fleet management, establishing great organisational cultures, ensuring minimal external interference in the decision making process, effective planning and development, effective management of people, and a robust internal management. The next chapter now discusses the research finding by locating them into the broader context.

5. Discussion of the Findings

5.1. Introduction

This study is designed to identify the challenges faced by NAC as well as to make strategic recommendations for enhancing organisational performance and sustainability. Five distinctive research objectives were developed in Chapter One in order to systematically achieve the research aim. The first objective dealt with the theoretical aspects of the research, whilst the second, third, and fourth objectives dealt with identifying the current strategic position of NAC, strategic challenges faced by NAC, and the critical success factors of NAC. The final objective focuses on making strategic recommendations to NAC based on the findings of this research. In order to achieve the research objectives, an inductive interpretive approach was followed by using the semi-structured interview as the data collection instrument. The research data was analysed using a thematic analysis approach.

The analysis of the research data, as presented in the earlier chapter, identified various strategic challenges faced by NAC as well as the critical success factors of the organisation. Besides, the analysis also revealed various internal and external environmental factors of NAC that are affecting the organisation. This chapter of the thesis summarises, discusses, and evaluates the findings of the research by locating them in the broader contexts and highlighting their contributions as well as their practical implications to the stakeholders. In this chapter, the research findings are discussed in the context of research objectives in order to systematically answer the main research question. Below, a strategic analysis of NAC, strategic challenges faced by NAC, and the critical success factors of NAC summarised, discussed, and evaluated. The figure below presents the structure of this chapter.

FIGURE 5-1: STRUCTURE OF CHAPTER FIVE

5.2. Strategic Analysis of Nepal Airlines Corporation

5.2.1. Summary of the Findings

The second research objective was designed to identify both internal and external environmental factors of NAC. To achieve this objective, semi-structured and open-ended interviews were conducted with the CEO, directors, and management staffs of NAC. PESTLE and SWOT analysis were conducted to identify the environmental factors in a systematic manner. The findings of the analysis, as presented in chapter 4.4, identified several political, economic, social, technological, legal, and ecological factors of NAC along with its various strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats.

As identified, political factors such a culture of political appointment and politically motivated decision-making processes impact the organisation negatively whilst economic factors such as improving the living standard of Nepali people, air travel becoming more accessible to the larger segment of the population, and the organisation having access to international lenders were identified as factors that impact the organisation positively. On the other hand, the limited availability of technological resources was determined as a technological factor that is posing strategical challenges to the organisation. Nepal government procurement act also posed legal challenges to the organisation by impacting is competitive powers.

Similarly, a SWOT analysis revealed various strengths such as the organisation being the national flag carrier of Nepal, operating in both domestic and international markets, and having an electronic ticketing system. Besides, organisational weaknesses such as poor management of debt, poor intra-organisational coordination, poor organisational culture leading to brain drain, and poor infrastructures were identified along with organisation opportunities such as possibilities of market expansion, and the growing domestic market with Nepalese peoples' increasing spending habits. Finally, an unstable government and the increasing number of competitors were identified as organisational threats.

5.2.2. Discussions of the findings

5.2.2.1. *External Environment of Nepal Airlines Corporation*

The findings of this research highlighted extreme political influence and corruption being the key reason behind NAC's decline. The political condition of Nepal is unstable despite the fact Nepal has experienced significant changes since the declaration of a republic country in 2008

(Gill, 2019). The liberal norms have not been institutionalised in Nepal, therefore, as one entity comes in that has more power, they are going to impose restrictions (Gill, 2019). NAC has heavily suffered from lack of transparency, corruption, political interference where it has come down to fleet of two operational planes and five international destinations in 2014 from 21 international destinations and fleet of 19 planes in the 1980s (Econ-ity, 2015).

The decline of NAC started along with the introduction of multiparty democracy where prime ministers made NAC money-making machine for themselves and their party (People's Review, 2016). The extreme political interference, influence, and ineffective decision making from the government have negatively impacted the profitability and reputation of NAC. For instance, Covid-19 crisis management committee (CCMC) cancelled all reparation flight including NAC that had flown to pick people from Dubai had to return empty because of government decision while it was en route despite public health source confirms air transportation had less risk due to strict rule on having PCR negative test 72 hours prior to departure (Baskota, 2020).

Previous studies suggested that political intervention that may enhance or hinder the performance of an organisation (Heracleous et al., 2009). Political factors have a momentous impact on the operating business environment of airlines industry (Barrett, 2006; Doganis, 2001; Taneja, 2010; Shepherd, 2012) and some particular market are regulated by the political atmosphere (Pratap, 2016). According to Doganis (2001) due to political interference state airlines tend to be characterised by elements of over politicisations, substantial losses, lack of clear development strategy, bureaucratic management and overstaffing. Similarly, Mananavire (2016) agrees that political interference has a significant impact on the performance of the airline industry. The findings of this study also suggest that political influence on a company within a competitive industry such as airline is harmful as they affect the overall competitiveness of the organisation.

Similarly, this research identified that economic factors highly influence NAC. Economic factors are known to have an influence on airlines industry and vice versa (IATA 2016; Pratap 2016). Economic factors in the region are directly related to the amount of the demand the organisation can expect to face and how well the organisation can expect to do during a specific time period (Grant, 2002). According to Davis (2013), the airline industry is impacted by changes in the world economy as it is not immune to economic pressures like unemployment, inflation, interest rate, disposable income, and has to adjust time to time as per changing economic conditions (Demydyuk 2011; Cederholm 2014; McCann 2015).

The economy of Nepal is growing rapidly with reaching 7.1 percentage of GDP growth in FY2019. This was due to the growth in the service sector, growth in agriculture, higher remittance inflow, growth in tourism, growth in retail trade, growth in real estate, growth in transport and restaurant services (Nepal Development update, 2019). In 2019, due to expanding economy and the increasing income of the Nepali people, the annual domestic passenger traffic increased by 11.96 per cent to 3.18 million; however, NAC experienced a drop of 6.23 per cent from the previous year (Prasain, 2020). The findings of this research also suggest that NAC has been unable to use the growing market favourably, primarily due to the lack of sufficient fleet and effective management.

The research findings suggested that middle-class people are particularly attracted to air transportation. This is due to the airfares are getting cheaper and air transportation is perceived as a necessity rather than extravagance (Prasain, 2020). NAC has a loan with an interest rate of 10.5 per cent fixed per annum that has been secured from two government organisation namely Citizen Investment Trust (CIT) and Employee provident fund (EPF) to buy two wide-body Airbus (The Kathmandu Post, 2017); however, the findings of this research suggest that should the government became guarantor and explore international investors, the cost of the loan can be halved. The purchase of two wide-body and two narrow-body aircraft has increased the losses of NAC where equity and loan are very high and the cumulative loss has soared (Poudel, 2019); the findings of this research suggest that this is due to the lack of research prior to making investments.

Additionally, airline companies create social value as any other business, thus social factors have effects on the attitude of consumers towards air transport (Pratap, 2016; Chandrappa 2014; Heracleous et al., 2009). The culture of going on holidays has increase around the world where more and more people are using airlines to travel and tourism has become more diverse and a large customer market (Shankman, 2014). The findings of this research indicated that rising numbers of Nepalese people travelling abroad for employment, higher education, tourism and religious purpose have contributed to the use of growth of air transportation domestically. The tourism boom in Nepal has contributed to the growth of 27 foreign airlines companies (CAPA, 2018). Similarly, Nepal successfully attracted more than 1 million tourists in 2017 which helped in the growth of the airline industry (Biju, 2018). Despite Numerous opportunities for growth, NAC appears to be unable to materialise such opportunities as the

trust of the Nepalese people on the organisation is declining year by year due to its poor services and management.

Technological factors, on the other hand, were also identified to significantly influence the operations of NAC. Technology, in the aviation industry, means speed, convenience, safety and the importance of technology could be understood from substantial use of technology in the aviation industry (Porter and Kramer, 2011). The finding of this research identified that technological development in NAC is very minimal and it is severely impacting the overall performance of the organisation. The role of technology is crucial in the airline industry whether it is on passenger safety, modern aircraft, air traffics, online payments and online booking system (Truxal, 2013). Technology enables airlines prompt access to customers to book tickets online, online check-in system saving the cost of airlines companies (Hartman and Boscoianu, 2015). Technology has the ability to reach a large number of customers (Porter and Kramer, 2015) that provides competitive advantages in this highly turbulent industry (Davies, 2013). It also helps airlines in the wide dissemination of advertisement (Georgieva, 2016) however airlines company that is statures with technology struggles for a competitive advantage over its competitors.

The respondents suggested that the use of low-quality equipment has affected the organisation's reputation as well as profitability. A previous study by Parsain (2020) also concluded that Chinese aircraft and old twin otter that are used in the domestic market has damaged the reputation, punctuality, reliability and has increased the operating cost and insurance of NAC. Due to the lack of modern and sufficient aircraft, the quality of services offered by NAC is poor, contributing to huge losses where NAC have decided to ground all the Chinese aircraft. This research also identified that NAC does not have adequate equipment for ground handling. Previous empirical studies conducted in NAC have found lack aircraft as a key challenge of NAC (i.e., Bastola 2017; Kumar 2016; Gyanwali and Walsh 2020); however, they do not mention the lack of equipment in ground handling department despite being ground handling the major source of revenue. Therefore, the findings of this research add new insights to the body of knowledge.

Previous studies identified that legal factors significantly impact the performance of the airline industry (Roche 2011; Mulder 2011) as air transport is regulated by several laws and regulations (Georgieva, 2016). This study also identified that legal factor such as the procurement act of Nepal government is significantly affecting the performance and

competitiveness of NAC. Legal factors also have an impact on wages, corporate social responsibility, are the few examples that affect the strategies and activities of the organisation (Arnold and Reynolds, 2003). There are various organisations that monitor, advocate, and regulate the aviation industry. These include instance International Civil Aviation organisation (ICAO), Civil Aeronautics Board, and International Air transportation association (IATA). Although various regulatory legislations are designed to enhance the safety and performance, in the case of NAC, the public procurement act of Nepal government is rather counterproductive as it prevents NAC from making faster decisions. Poudel (2019) suggests that NAC needs to run as an autonomous firm without having to follow public procurement act for enhancing its performance.

Finally, environmental factors also affect the aviation industry. This is because the aviation industry contributes to climate change and global dimming due to heat, noise, and gases produced from aircraft (Forsyth, 2011). The carbon footprint of the aviation industry contributes approximately 6% of greenhouse gas emissions to the atmosphere (Reay, 2004). Such environmental factors are driving changes in the airline industry. The rapid growth in the airline industry in recent years have contributed to the increase in pollution despite emission reduction and more fuel-efficient aircrafts production (Anderson and Bows, 2008). The growing number of airlines companies has increased the environmental pollutions in Nepal as well (Karki, 2017). However, the findings of this research suggested that, in the particular case of NAC, such environmental factors currently have a little impact as Nepalese people are not highly aware of the ecological impact of the aviation industry.

5.2.2.2. Internal Environment of Nepal Airlines Corporation

The analysis of three so state identified a few strengths of NEA that can be used for developing competitive strategies that can help the organisation to enhance its sustainability. One of the findings indicated that the organisation being the national flag carrier of Nepal it is a strength as the government of Nepal is also responsible towards the organisation, hence it is in a better position to finance itself during difficult times. A previous empirical study conducted in NAC also suggested that NAC has strong financial backing from the government, and it is a strong brand itself representing a national flag carrier (Yadav, 2016). Besides, NAC has been operating for the past 61 years in the both domestic and international market and has

experienced business units. This can be extremely useful in the events of market expansion. Additionally, this research also identified that NAC has a functional online booking system, which can be highly useful when the organisation is developing international markets.

The findings of this research, as presented in the previous chapter, highlighted various weaknesses NAC. These include the lack of sufficient aircraft, the lack of coordination and cooperation among the employee of NAC, poor managerial cultures, and etc. A previous study by Yadav (2016) identified that NAC lacks long term planning, which is resulted in poor handling resources. Due to the lack of visionary leaders, the airline has made substantial losses. For instance, NAC purchased Chinese aircraft that were rejected by Dhaka and has grounded all of the six Chinese aircraft due to high maintenance cost, high insurance cost, lack of pilots, lack of safety, and not being reliable (Prasain, 2020). The purchase of the Chinese aircraft shows the lack of experience, skill, and knowledge of people at key decisions making positions. The respondents also highlighted the single international airport in Nepal as a weakness of NAC. TIA, which is in middle of the city, has increasing air traffic where flights are compelled to wait more than an hour for landing permission (Karki, 2017), increasing the operational costs and impacting the punctuality of services.

This study has also identified various opportunities for NAC such as market expansion in both international and domestic sectors. This is because the disposable income of the Nepalese people is rising as the economy is growing. Besides, there is a consistent growth in both domestic and international tourism and opportunities to form alliances with other international airlines companies (Yadav, 2016). The domestic market is now highly controlled by private airlines (Himalayan Times, 2016) as they have capitalised on the weakness of the NAC. With an expansion of the fleet, NAC can once again gain the lost market as it is still connected emotionally with the Nepalese customers.

Finally, this research suggested various possible threats to NAC such as instability of the government and intensifying market competition. As the organisation is extremely influenced by politics, the change in government is an extremely uncertain period for NAC. As a new government enters, they tend to shuffle the senior managers of the organisation and abandon previous development strategies. A previous study on NAC by Yadav (2016) also identified various threats such as unstable government, increasing interest rates, not being able to balance books with increasing operational costs, growing competitions, and lower profitability (Yadav,

2016). The findings of this research support the existing findings by making them stronger and thus, making a contribution to the body of knowledge.

5.2.3. Evaluations of the findings

In this research, semi-structured interviews were conducted for achieving the research objectives. Respondents included the CEO, directors, and management employees of NAC. In-depth interviews with senior managers of NAC helped to identify various interesting insights, some of them not previously reported in the literature. The findings have broadened the horizons of the body of knowledge by making the unknown known. However, in order to assess the environmental factors, this study did not collect data from the employees of TIA and government officials – parties that make critical decisions of NAC. Therefore, it is possible that the exact strategic position may not have been identified due to not evaluating the perceptions of all concerned parties.

Moreover, the strategical analytical tools used to achieve this objective were PESTLE and SWOT. However, if the researcher had full accesses to collect financial data and other critical information, using other strategical analytical tools like resource base view, value chain analysis, and business models would have provided more accurate information about the strategic position of NAC. A decision was made to conduct only SWOT and PESTLE analysis after carefully considering the time and access implications.

5.3. Strategic Challenges Faced by Nepal Airlines Corporation

5.3.1. Summary of the findings

The third research objective was designed to assess the strategic challenges faced by NAC across various organisational aspects. To achieve this objective, semi-structured interviews were conducted with board members of NAC, directors from different departments, employees of NAC, customers of NAC, agents of NAC, and an expert in the Nepalese aviation industry. The earlier chapter of this thesis presented the challenges faced by NAC into two categories: political and operational.

The research findings, as presented in chapter 4.2, suggest four key political challenges faced by NAC. These include increased corruption due to the culture of political appointment, employees' political affiliation and extreme unionism leading to the lack of collaboration

across departments, instability of the government, and the outdated government public procurement act for airlines. Similarly, this research also identified four key operational challenges of NAC, namely the lack of sufficient fleet, spare equipment, and ground handling equipment, the lack of effective research and development practices, the lack of coordination with TIA, and a lengthy and ineffective employee recruitment process. The figure below presents the challenges faced by NAC.

FIGURE 5-2: STRATEGIC CHALLENGES FACED BY NEPAL AIRLINES CORPORATION

Source: The Author

5.3.2. Discussions of the Findings

5.3.2.1. Political Challenges

One of the key political challenges of NAC, as identified in chapter 4.5, is the instability of the government leading to frequent changes in executive chairman and directors. Unstable government has been a reason behind frequent changes in business plans and organisational growth strategies are often abandoned or put on hold. This was identified to have a severe negative impact on NAC's growth and its organisational performance.

Bastola (2017) conducted research in the Nepalese aviation industry and identified that political stability in NAC can bring growth in the aviation industry whilst improving the and the quality of life. Similarly, Mhlange and Steyn (2017) conducted research on the impact of macro environment on the operations of southern African airlines by reviewing the cases of six different southern African airlines namely Com Air, South African Airways, FlySafair, Air Botswana, Air Namibia, and Air Zimbabwe. Mhlange and Steyn (2017) identified that political interference and political influence has destabilized the growth of the southern African airlines (both private and government-owned), negatively impacting the performance of airlines and fostering corruption. The study also identified that government-owned airlines lack clear development strategies, are overstaffed, make substance losses, and have bureaucratic managements that leads to lack of operational efficiency (Mhlange and Steyn, 2017). Besides, it was also identified that government interference in government-owned airlines has negatively affected the implementation of the airlines' turnaround plans. The findings of this research are consistent with the findings of Mhlange and Steyn (2017) as they suggest that political interference has negatively impacted the growth of NAC.

Bazza and Deneji (2013) also examined the organisational performance under unstable political environment. It identified that political instability affects organisational performance as when the government is in charge of an organisation, it has no control over its own organisation. Furthermore, Abayomi and Ayobami (2012) also agree that political instability is one of the factors that negatively affect the performance of an organisation. Therefore, the findings of this research make a contribution to the body of knowledge by further supporting previous literature.

Similarly, chapter 4.5 also identified political appointment of executive chairman, directors and even employee in NAC has stagnated its organisational growth, becoming the root of corruption. A study of Mhlange and Steyn (2017) on state-owned airlines in Southern Africa found that political appointment led to the recruitment of inefficient CEOs, many CEOs remained only for a short period of time, forced to purse political agenda, cased the loss of funds, and caused instability at board and management level of the organisation. All of these factors lead airlines being ineffective in their operation and operating on loss. Similarly, Chlumecky (2018) conducted a study on Thai Airways about its political appointees, nepotism, corruption, and bad management. The study found that the political appointment of an individual with prior experience in airlines industry leads to corruption. In the case of NAC,

Poudel (2019) states that there is too much interference by the state and political parties with nepotism playing a key role in the appointment process. Poudel (2019) also argues that unskilled employees at the decision-making level are the main reason for NAC facing losses.

However, the political appointment does not necessarily always increase corruption neither always has a negative impact on the organisation. For example, In 2018-2019 fiscal year, Qatar Airways launched 11 new destinations, recorded growth in its passenger revenue by 14.3 per cent, with capability growth in available seats kilometre by 13.5 per cent, cargo revenue by 16.8 per cent, and cargo capacity in available tonne-kilometres by 11.8 per cent comparing to the previous fiscal year (Smith, 2019). In regard to Qatar Airways, the CEO is appointed by the head of states as well (Jones, 2011). A report suggests the corruption index of Nepal and as 113 in 2019 among 180 countries whereas the corruption index of Qatar was 62 for the same period. Therefore, the political appointment does not always lead to corruption rather it is about the integrity of the appointees. Corruption is a complex and multi-faceted phenomenon that is fomented and evolved through various factors and weak governance is considered a fundamental leading cause of corruption (Department for International Development, 2015). Perhaps, the system of proper governance and monitoring of government organisation, better accountability, and introduction of rigid reward and punishment systems might reduce the corruption in NAC.

The research findings presented in chapter 4.5 highlighted that employee's political affiliation and extreme unionism in NAC have negative effects on the coordination and communication among departments and employees. This study also identified that leaders are facing difficulties to implement new change or new strategy in origination as political affliction and extreme unionism has led to resistance to change. Wit and Meyer (2014) agrees that unionism does not lead to adeptness as these are based on mutual incompetence and supporting within the group. Similarly, Verluyten (2010) also agrees that unionism in some cases leads to stagnation.

Gyanwali and Walsh (2019) conducted research on the factors influencing the organisational performance of NAC using mixed methods where primary data was collected from fifteen government officials and NAC executive. The research found that the polarization of political alignment in staff union is causing poor coordination within the departments NAC and irresponsibility among some employees. Strong and stable political-free unionism in an organisation is essential for proper organisation relationship where it can play an important

role in ensuring effective communication between worker and management (Nambiar and PK, 2014). However, the politicization of unionism and political affiliation of the employee becomes the cause of continuous disturbance to the affable relation within organisation relationship and organisation will become a battlefield of political parties for their own gain (Nambiar and PK, 2014). This will ultimately kill the coordination, communication and efficiency of the organisation.

Additionally, this research also identified that the government public procurement act (PPA) is ineffective and outdated which slows down the process of buying aircraft as it not only takes multiple years to approve the purchase of aircraft but also does not allow to buy specific aircraft required by the airline. The current PPA requires NAC to undergo a bidding process to purchase any aircraft. According to the PPA 2063, NAC could use four different methods, namely quality and cost method, quality method, fixed budget method, and least cost method for the bidding process. However, NAC does not have the right to choose a specific type of the aircraft, which results into – as identified in this research – having aircraft from four manufacture despite having a fleet of only 13 aircraft. Operating single type of aircraft from the same manufacture helps to reduce the stockpile of spare parts, reduce spare parts costs, reduce downtime for maintenance, and reduce the cost of training pilots and technician for various types of aircraft (Boon, 2019). However, a disadvantage of having a single type of aircraft from one manufacturer is if the aircraft has to be grounded for safety reasons it affects the entire fleet: for example, Boeing 737 max grounding (Boon, 2019).

Moreover, the procurement act requires the involvement of government officials and board members in the purchasing process of aircraft despite they not having knowledge in the type of aircraft that is required by NAC (Prasain, 2020). Due to the lack of necessary knowledge in the decision-making process whilst purchasing aircraft, NAC has bought Chinese aircraft that caused substantial losses to the organisation. In 2012, six Chinese aircraft were first acquired by NAC after 28 years; however, the planes were not fit for the Nepalese sky (Prasain, 2020). NAC now have retired all of six Chinese made aircraft due to sub-standard performance, high operating cost, and to prevent mounting losses in future mainly insurance and operating cost (Ch-aviation, 2020). Qatar Airways, despite having a fleet of 207 passenger planes, only uses two manufacture Airbus and Boeing where airlines orders aircraft through manufacture as per the requirement of airlines without the intervention of the government despite being government organisation (Qatar airways, 2020). This proves that the excessive political and

government intervention in NAC is unnecessary and counterproductive, eventually causing the organisation to fail. The findings of this research, as discussed above, are consistent with the existing literature.

5.3.2.2. Operational Challenges

The research also identified various operational challenges of NAC. One of the key operational challenges identified in this research is the lack of fleet, timely availability of spare parts and lack of ground handling equipment. NAC does not have sufficient aircraft to compete in both the domestic and international market (Gyanwali and Walsh, 2019). NAC requires advanced and sophisticated technology and a sufficient number of modern aircraft to maintain service safety, reliability, and punctuality that are essential elements to maintain customers trust and loyalty (Gyanwali and Walsh, 2019). Due to the lack of sufficient fleet of NAC, the domestic market is dominated by private airlines such as Buddha Airlines, Yeti Airlines, Summit Airlines, etc (Skyline, 2017). During 2018, the domestic market share of private airlines was 97.22% (Prasain, 2019). Similarly, the international market is also dominated by private airlines or other international airlines with a market share of 89.67% (Prasain, 2019).

There is also the lack of timely availability of spare parts required for the maintenance of the aircraft as it is not possible to stock all the spare parts required for four different manufacture aircraft (Rai, 2019). NAC ground handling service in Tribhuvan international airport generates NPR 3 billion on annual revenue that is one-third of its total receipts (Prasain, 2017). Yet the NAC ground handling department lacks technical equipment that is essential for the aircraft and health and safety of the customers. Due to the lack of equipment, employees working in the ground handling department are forced to work manually for the jobs that are usually done by machines.

Similarly, the research findings presented in chapter 4.5 also highlighted that NAC lacks effective research and development practices for the development of new business plans and business strategies. The purchase of the Chinese aircraft that were not beneficial for NAC growth is the prime example of NAC lacking effective research and development practices. Due to lack of effective research and business plan, NAC has been unable to utilize two wide-body and two narrow-body aircraft into their full capacity (Sunuwar, 2019; Ojha, 2019). NAC does currently have a business planning department; however, it does not have the necessary tools for conducting research neither have required knowledge, skills, and experience to

conduct research. The business planning team have to rely on outdated research while preparing business plans. As the competitive advantages of the airline industry do not sustain for a long period, conducting business plan with outdated information will only lead to the failure of business plan and business strategy.

An organisation that implements effective research and development practices offers tremendous advantages to them. Research and development practices question the business process and productivity, encourage organisation flexibility, and enable to integrate new concepts and process allowing organisations to become more agile to the environmental changes (Freel, 2000). The research and development practices of an organisation have to be effective for various factors like regulation changes in the market, distributive technology and innovation, shareholder expectations, and various integration (Nu Angle, 2014).

Additionally, this research identified the employee recruitment process of NAC is lengthy and ineffective. The recruitment process is carried out by other government organisation on behalf of NAC where they conduct the exam for candidates. This increases the probability of people being recruit with no relevant skills. Due to generalisation in the selection of the candidates, NAC is unable to get the experts required in some of its department like business planning. The recruitment process and outsourcing process are not quick and efficient that impacts department like ground handling where more manpower is required as soon as the ground handling contract increases. Due to poor recruitment process, NAC is unable to hire experts in an organisation where they are required by specific division like business planning.

5.3.3. Evaluations of the Findings

In order to identify the strategic challenges faced by NAC, interviews were conducted with various internal and external organisational parties. The views of NAC employees including the CEO, department directors, and general employees along with the views of an expert in the Nepalese aviation industry, ticketing agents, and customers were incorporated to identify the strategic challenges. Prior to considering the findings of the research, although this research was done in a very comprehensive manner, it is important to note that the perceptions of certain external bodies such as government officials and the officials at the hub airport were not included. Given that they are some of the significant stakeholders of NAC, it is possible that the challenges identified in this research may not provide the full picture.

Additionally, a large proportion of research data was collected from the employees of the organisation. This may lead to certain respondent-bias related implications as it is possible that the employees of NAC may not have disclosed their own weaknesses during the interview process. Besides, given that this research was conducted particularly in NAC, the findings may not be widely generalizable to different airline companies.

5.4. Critical Success Factors of Nepal Airlines Corporation

5.4.1. Summary of the Findings

The fourth research objective was developed to identify the critical success factors for NAC. The findings of this objective were presented in chapter 4.6 of this thesis. In order to identify the critical success factors of NAC, the views of all research participants were carefully analysed using a thematic analysis approach. The identified critical success factors of NAC include (1) effective fleet management by increasing fleet size, securing extra funding, enhancing safety and reliability, (2) establishing great organisational cultures for attracting talents by ending the culture of political appointment, controlling the practices of political unionism, (3) ensuring minimal external interference in the decision making process by changing Nepal governments current public procurement act, (4) effective planning and development by recruiting expert researchers, (5) effective management of people by introducing employee development programmes, introducing effective rewards and recognition systems, recruiting right people with the necessary knowledge, and (6) making the internal management robust by making the decision-making process faster, cost management by phasing out the unprofitable aircraft, and enhancing the decisiveness of the managers by allocating them more power. The figure below presents the critical success factors identified for NAC.

FIGURE 5-3: CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS OF NEPAL AIRLINES CORPORATION

Source: The Author

5.4.2. Discussion of the Findings

The analysis of the research data suggested that effective fleet management is crucial for the long-term success of NAC. The respondents suggested that this can be done by increasing the current fleet size by securing extra funding. Doing so can help the organisation to enhance the safety and reliability of its services, eventually being able to win back the customer trust and increase organisational profitability. Respondents suggested that increasing fleet size can eventually increase the production capacity of the organisation leading to improved overall performance. Previous empirical research found that airlines like JetBlue and Kenya Airways Limited have invested heavily on their fleet size as it is one of the critical success factors of organisation (Abudho et al., 2013). Aircraft are the major assets of airlines companies where their utilization per day explains how well major assets are used (McCabe, 2006). There are various factors that can indicate how well individual airlines are used; i.e., the proportion of seats that are sold and actually filled at the time of departure (McCabe, 2006).

In the context of NAC, it has a small number of aircraft due to the lack of ownership feeling from the government (Gyanwali and Walsh, 2020). Furthermore, NAC does not have the required funds to purchase aircraft, thus has to rely on government and lenders. However, the

main issue with the fleet of NAC is not only lack of sufficient aircraft, but it is also their effective use (Prasain, 2019). NAC has not been able to fly the minimum amount of the hours in the sky that is required to make any profit from two wide-body, two narrow-body aircraft (The Kathmandu Post, 2020). These factors have contributed to the reduced market share in both domestic (2.78%) and international (11.3%) markets (Prasain, 2019). NAC is facing a severe financial challenge with the debt reaching a critical level of NPR 37 billion and annual interest repayment of NPR 3.66 billion (The Kathmandu Post, 2017). The recent pandemic forced NAC to seek government bailout of NPR 20 billion (The Kathmandu Post, 2020).

Despite being the national flag carrier, NAC has insignificant domestic market share. Based on the analysis conducted above, NAC should focus on fleet expansion in the domestic market rather than in the international market. When the national flag carrier has a weak presence in the domestic market, it will be extremely difficult to expand in the international market. Nepalese customers, under the current circumstances, do not trust NAC, doubting their punctuality and reliability. The international market connecting Nepal is served by some of the world biggest airlines companies and it will not be easy to compete with them, mainly because of their competitive strength of fleet size, financial powers, and strategic alliances. Besides, the costs involved in expanding fleet internationally will put NAC in serious debt problems.

This research also identified that the current organisational culture of NAC demotivates employees and cannot attract talents. Therefore, establishing a great organisation culture for attracting new talented human resource is identified as one of the critical success factors of NAC. Previous studies suggested that excellent corporate culture motivate employees and cultivate the attitude that steered towards teamwork with employee commitment and cost-consciousness translated into operational excellence and growth in profitability (Dess et al., 2008; Daramaju et al., 2007; Bunz and Maes, 1998). Similarly, Chatman (1989) also suggested that organizational culture plays an important role in attracting and retaining employees in an organisation.

Silverthorne (2004) studied the impact of organisational culture on job satisfaction in Taiwan. The study found that organisation with bureaucratic organisational cultures resulted in the lowest level of organisational commitment and the lowest level of job satisfaction, indicating organisational commitment and job satisfaction is higher in an innovative or supportive culture. On the other hand, Khanna et al. (2015), Chien and Hung (2020) identified that connection-based appointment reduces the firm performance and profitability. The recruitment process of

NAC it usually through the political appointment and the culture of connection-based appointment is highly prominent within the organisation. This culture needs to be changed if the organisation is to see some real transformation.

Furthermore, the culture of unionism is also highly prominent within NAC. The strong presence of political unions has created a culture of disobeying within the organisation. CAPA (2018) identified unionism in a low margin industry like the airline industry has a negative impact on organisation interest as they are there to serve the interest of their members. Wit and Meyer (2014) agrees that unionism does not lead to adeptness as these are based on mutual incompetence and supporting within the group. Similarly, Verluyten (2010) also agrees that unionism in some cases leads to stagnation. Likewise, Gyanwali and Walsh (2019) found that due to the polarization of political alignment in staff union, poor coordination within the departments of NAC exists. Such cultures of political unionism and connection-based appointment system not only prevent the organisation from growing but also hinder the career progressions of talented employees. Therefore, developing an organisational culture that promotes the recruitment and retention of the right talent was identified as one of the critical success factors for NAC.

This research also identified a high level of external interference in the decision-making process. This interference is mainly caused due to the requirements of the current public procurement act of Nepal. The procurement act requires NAC to involve government officials and board members in the purchasing process of aircraft despite they neither having knowledge in the type of aircraft that is required by NAC nor any experience in the airline industry (Prasain, 2020). Although the literature evidence related to the impact of the procurement act on NAC is limited, it was highly prioritised by the respondents of this research for hindering the organisational growth of NAC. This issue was previously raised to the government and a task force that was formed by the Minister for Culture, Tourism, and Civil Aviation to look into the issue plaguing national flag carrier. The task force recommended that NAC should operate as an autonomous organisation without having to follow public procurement act and divesting 49% of its share to the public or foreign investor in order to be profitable Poudel, 2019). Nevertheless, the findings of this research have raised an important insight into the literature, making contributions to the body of knowledge.

Additionally, this research identified effective planning and development as one of the critical success factors for NAC. As observed in the dataset, the respondent's working in the planning

and development department had no product experience nor they received essential training and coaching. Olumuyiwa et al. (2012) suggested that effective planning determines the success or failure of an organisation as it impacts the organisation's productivity. Similarly, Ufartiene (2014) asserts that planning related to organisation development and employee development help to expand and sustain business in a competitive market. Organisations that implement effective research and development practices are more productive, agile, and receptive to new changes (Freel, 2000). Therefore, it is essential that NAC invests on appropriate training and development practices by recruiting the right people in order to sustain in the current competitive marketplace. This finding of the research is consistent with the findings of the previous studies.

Moreover, this research also identified that effective management of people is critical for the success of NAC. This can be done by introducing employee development programmes, introducing effective rewards and recognition systems, and recruiting the right people with the necessary knowledge. The respondents also highlighted that the organisation has no training and development plans for employees as well as no reward and recognition schemes to motivate well-performing employees. According to Fernald et al. (1999), training could be used as tools to enhance the performance of employees and to prevent problems rather than spending management time in correcting the problems caused by untrained employees. Lancaster and Milia (2014) indicated that organisational support as a significant factor affecting employees' ability and opportunity to learn new leadership skills. Training and reward practices in an organisation environment lead to effective people management (Renwick, 2003).

Meyer et al. (2004) also indicated that employees perceive strong normative commitment if they feel valued by rewarding jobs and recognition schemes that perceive as moral obligations to stay with the employer and perform par excellence. Similarly, Saunderson (2004) agrees that need for recognition is felt by a considerable portion of the workforce regardless of profession or status. Rewards and recognition schemes are significant for employee engagement for developing organisation commitment (Saks, 2006; Albrecht, 2010). More researchers such as Bakker et al. (2004), Schaufeli et al. (2006), and Rai et al. (2018) also identified reward and recognition programmes to positively influence the employee engagement, eventually enhancing both in-role performance and extra-role performance.

Finally, effective internal management was identified as another critical success factor of NAC. The respondents highlighted that the senior managers are not decisive, the decision-making processes slow and ineffective, and the organisation is poorly managed, leading to increased losses. According to Aramovich and Blankenship (2020), effective leaders have high decisiveness and participation in the organisation. Mallari and Joseph (2016) and Winters et al (2019) suggest that effective management requires a manager to understand and improve decision making as it is central to management activities within any organisation that should be met with strong professional expectations and high ethical demands.

5.4.3. Evaluations of the Findings

As discussed above, the critical success factors in this research are similar to those of previous studies. In fact, the critical success factor of NAC is not significantly different than any organisation that operates in a competitive environment. Given that the above findings are based on primary research the involved interviewing senior managers of NAC as well that an expert in the aviation industry with several decades of experience, careful considerations of those can significantly transform NAC. This research not only highlights various critical success factors, but it also provides clear instruction on how each organisational aspect should be treated and managed. However, similar to previous findings of this research, the findings related to the critical success factors of NAC also may not be fully comprehensive as key stakeholders such as Nepal government officials and officials from TIA were not interviewed.

5.5. Conclusions

The findings of this research were summerized, discussed, and evaluated in this chapter of the thesis. Initially, findings were summarised in the context of research objectives and they were then discussed in the broader context to assess how they support or contradict the prior evidence available in the literature in order to draw knowledge claims. Although very little evidence that are precisely related to NAC was identified, the findings of the research generally supported the notion of the literature. Finally, the findings were evaluated by highlighting their strengths and weaknesses. During the evaluation, suggestions were also made to the future researchers by highlighting how a research extending the findings of this thesis can be done in an effective manner to further enhance the validity and reliability of the findings.

The research finding related to the strategic analysis of NAC provide various new insights that were not previously discussed in the literature. These findings not only make contributions to

the body of knowledge but also guide future researchers as well as practitioners. Similarly, this research identified various challenges faced by NAC, a careful examination of them during the development of new business strategies can help the management of NAC to clearly understand the organisational challenges and develop strategies that are more practical and appropriate. Finally, the critical success factors identified in this study clearly state the approaches that are required for making NAC a successful organisation. The findings are unique as no similar study was conducted previously. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no such comprehensive study was previously conducted in NAC and this is the first attempt made to incorporate the views of NAC's both internal and external stakeholders. Therefore, the findings of this study make significant original contributions to the body of knowledge well as the practise.

6. Conclusions, Contributions, and Recommendations

6.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to demonstrate how each research objectives were achieved by summarising the research findings as well as the research methods related to each of them. In this chapter, each research objective of the research is revisited, the methodological approach used for achieving each of them is described and evaluated, and the findings related to each objective is outlined. Besides, in this chapter, the contribution, as well as the significance of each research finding, is presented and discussed. Additionally, recommendations are made to the stakeholders of NAC for enhancing the overall performance of the organisation based on the findings of the research. Finally, this chapter also deals with further studies and the possible limitations of the research findings. The figure below presents the structure of this chapter.

FIGURE 6-1: STRUCTURE OF CHAPTER SIX

6.2. Summary of the Research

This study was designed to analyse the strategic challenges faced by NAC for recommending strategies for enhancing long term organisational performance. In order to do so, a strategic review of NAC was conducted by carefully considering both internal and external factors. Besides, this study also assessed the key challenges faced by NAC as well as the critical success factors of the organisation.

In order to systematically achieve the research aim, five distinctive research objectives were formulated in chapter one of this thesis. The first objective was developed to have an in-depth understanding of the relevant literature as well as the research context. In order to achieve this objective, various theories related to strategic analysis, strategy formulation, strategy implementation were critically reviewed. Besides, an extensive literature review was also connected in the context of NAC as well as the critical success factors of the aviation industry. The second, third, and fourth objectives of this study were designed to identify the findings that are explicitly related to NAC. For example, the second objective of the research was established to understand the current strategic position of NAC, the third objective was formed to understand the challenges faced by NAC across various organisational aspects whilst the fourth objective was established to identify the critical success factors of NAC. Finally, the last and fifth objective of the study was designed to make strategic recommendations for enhancing the overall performance of NAC based on the findings of this research.

In order to have a greater grasp of the research area, an extensive literature review was conducted in chapter 2 of this thesis. The review included relevant theoretical models as well as prior studies in the area organisational strategy and aviation. The theoretical literature review explored various strategy theories, elements of strategy, different level of strategy formulation, and strategy implementation whilst the empirical literature review dealt with and current scenario of the global aviation industry, NAC and challenges faced by it, previous studies on the aviation industry, common challenges faced by the aviation industry, and common critical success factors of organisations in the aviation industry.

The second chapter of this thesis reviewed various strategic analytical tools such as SWOT, PESTLE, Resource Base View, and Value Chain Analysis. After careful analysis of the various

tools for strategic analysis of an organisation, SWOT and PESTLE were considered in this research for analysing the organisational environment of NAC. During the review of the literature, it was noticed that the number of studies conducted in NAC is extremely limited. Although some minor studies were done focusing on a small segment of the organisation, no comprehensive empirical study was previously done to identify the challenges faced by NAC as well as its critical success factors, leaving a knowledge gap in the literature.

In order to achieve the research objectives and thus to fill the knowledge gap, this the study was designed as a subjective-interpretive study. The reason behind selecting an interpretive philosophy was not only due to the nature of the research question but also due to the research area not being highly established – where the use of the quantitative method is considered unsuitable and counterproductive. Inductive reasoning was used for theory creation in this study as there was no existing theory to test neither any existing theory to improve. The research phenomena were further explored in depth as the data was collected. This study adopted qualitative method for data collection as it was deemed more useful in better understanding the current situation of NAC, its strategic position, and current situations of the airline market in Nepal from the perspectives of various respondents. The selection of the research method was further justified as many similar previous studies were conducted from an interpretive perspective.

For collecting the research data, this study used the non-probability sampling method where purposive and snowball sampling techniques were used to recruit respondents. The qualitative primary data was collected through semi-structured interviews from employees of various department of NAC, including directors and CEO, general employees of NAC, customers of the Nepalese aviation industry, and an expert in the Nepalese aviation industry. In order to collect the relevant research data, three sets of interview questions were designed, and the length of each interview varied depending on the designation of the respondents. After carefully considering the requirements of the research objectives as well as data saturation, a total of 47 interviews were conducted.

Prior to the interviews, the researcher focused on building trusts and rapport with participants by communicating with them through emails and social media before the data collection process started. All participants were provided with the participant's information sheet and consent form which consisted of all details regarding the research. The participant's

information sheet included information related to why the research is being conducted, what will happen to the data, as well as the information related to their rights and privacy. The research data was validated by showing the interview transcript to participants and requesting them to confirm that the transcript is the true reflection of their views. In order to enhance the reliability and validity of the findings, a pilot study was conducted by interviewing three respondents. The interview questions were slightly modified after the pilot study to make them more understandable by the respondents. Once the research data was collected, it was coded, and themes were developed by following the thematic analysis approach within the content analysis.

This research identified various political and operational challenges faced by NAC. Political challenges include increased corruption due to the culture of political appointment, employees' political affiliation and extreme unionism leading to the lack of collaboration across departments, instability of the government, and the outdated government public procurement act for airlines whilst operational challenges include the lack of sufficient fleet, spare equipment, and ground handling equipment, the lack of effective research and development practices, the lack of coordination with TIA, and a lengthy and ineffective employee recruitment process. This research also identified five key critical success factors for NAC, namely effective fleet management, establishing great organisational cultures, ensuring minimal external interference in the decision making process, effective planning and development, effective management of people, and a robust internal management.

6.3. Achieving Research Objectives

In order to systematically answer the research question, five research objectives were designed in chapter one of this thesis. Below, the process in which each objective was achieved is discussed.

6.3.1. Review of the Relevant Literature

The first research objective *“To critically review the literature related to strategic analysis, challenges faced by the aviation industry, and the critical success factors of an airline company”* was designed to have a broader understanding of the subject as well as to identify

and demonstrate the knowledge gap. Whilst analysing literature related to strategic management, various strategy theories such as SWOT, PESTLE, Five Forces, Resource-based View, Value Chain Analysis, and Business Model were critically analysed. Besides, different levels of strategy formulation and various strategy implementation process were also analysed. Additionally, in order to have a broader understanding of the research context, the challenges faced by the aviation industry was also reviewed. Furthermore, a detailed review of NAC was also conducted by reviewing both internal and external environmental factors.

In order to conduct an extensive review of the past literature, various sources such as Journal databases, books, reliable websites, and company reports were accessed. A careful revision of the existing literature suggested that there is a knowledge gap concerning the challenges faced by NAC as well as the critical success factors of NAC. In the second chapter of this thesis, the researcher also carefully analysed similar past studies in order to have clarity on the data collection process. A careful revision of past similar studies helped the researcher to design interview questions that can best answer the research objectives. Given that the researcher was able to design comprehensive interview questions as well as to demonstrate the knowledge gap, it is considered that the first research objective was successfully achieved.

6.3.2. Strategic Analysis of Nepal Airlines Corporation

The second research objective “*To conduct a strategic analysis of Nepal Airlines Corporation for identifying both internal and external environmental factors that their impacts on the organisation*” was designed to analyse the strategic position of NAC and the environmental factors that impact the organisation both positively and negatively. In order to achieve this objective, semi-structured and open-ended questions were formed where interviews were conducted with the CEO, directors of various department, and with the employees of NAC. This research identified various internal and external organisational factors such as the culture of political appointments, increasing popularity of air travel, the lack of fleet, poor debt management practises, and poor rewards and recognition system for recruiting and retaining talented employees. The findings related to this objective are presented in detail in chapter 4.5 of this thesis.

Based on the research findings, it is concluded that NAC has different strategic approaches for domestic and international markets. In the domestic market, NAC uses cost leadership strategy whereas, in the international market, it uses focus strategy focusing on a niche market to gain market share. The in-depth strategic analysis suggested that the organisation can succeed by effectively utilising the current resources available to it. NAC must remain open to innovative ideas that can enhance service standards and overall performance of the organisation and focus on attracting three vital resources: investment, aircraft, and human capital. This can make NAC more productive and competitive. The strategic analysis conducted in this research suggested that there are no problems with the objectives of the organisation in both domestic and international markets. However, NAC lacks strategies to achieve its objectives. For instance, the objective of NAC is to increase market share, market expansion, and fleet expansion and regain the leading position in both domestic and international markets, but it lacks rigid planning and development practices that can result in effective business strategies.

The finding related to the second research objective, as discussed in chapter 5.2, offer several new insights to the literature. As observed during the literature review, no comprehensive prior study was conducted for identifying both internal and external environmental factors of NAC using a primary data collection method. This research made an extensive attempt in identifying the environmental factors that are affecting the operations of NEA. Most of the discoveries of this research are new and make significant contributions to the body of knowledge. The findings of this research are based on primary data collected precisely for this research; therefore, they are original. This objective of the research, therefore, was also successfully achieved.

6.3.3. Strategic Challenges Faced by Nepal Airlines Corporation

The third objective of this study “*To identify the strategic challenges faced by Nepal Airlines Corporation*” was designed to identify the strategic challenges faced by NAC across various organisational aspects. The review of the literature suggested that no comprehensive prior study focused on identifying the challenges faced by NAC by conducting primary data from NAC’s top-level executives. In order to answer the research objective, semi-structured and in-depth interviews were conducted with an expert in the Nepalese aviation industry, the CEO of

NAC, directors and employees of NAC, customers, and ticketing agents. A thematic analysis of the qualitative data identified various political and operational challenges faced by NAC.

The political challenges of NAC include the political appointment of employees leading to corruption, employees' affiliation with political parties and extreme unionism leading to lack of collaboration across departments, instability of the government, and the outdated government public procurement act. Similarly, operational challenges faced by NAC include the lack of sufficient fleet, spare parts, and ground handling equipment, the lack of effective research and development practices, the lack of coordination with TIA, and the lengthy and ineffective employee recruitment process. These findings add new insights to the literature by making significant original contributions to the body of knowledge as well as bridging the knowledge gap that previously existed. Therefore, this objective of the research was also fully achieved.

6.3.4. Critical Success Factors of Nepal Airlines Corporation

The fourth objective of this study *“To reveal the critical success factors of Nepal Airlines Corporation based on the views of various organisational stakeholders”* was designed to understand the factors that contribute towards the success of NAC by enhancing the overall organisation performance across various organisational aspects. In order to identify the critical success factors, comments of all participant groups were carefully scrutinised. Besides, the contextual suitability of each critical success factor was also assessed by giving careful considerations to the strengths and weaknesses of the organisation. A thematic analysis of the research data revealed six key categories of critical success factors.

The identified critical success factors of NAC include (1) effective fleet management by increasing fleet size, securing extra funding, enhancing safety and reliability, (2) establishing great organisational cultures for attracting talents by ending the culture of political appointment, controlling the practices of political unionism, (3) ensuring minimal external interference in the decision making process by changing Nepal governments current public procurement act, (4) effective planning and development by recruiting expert researchers, (5) effective management of people by introducing employee development programmes, introducing effective rewards and recognition systems, recruiting right people with the

necessary knowledge, and (6) making the internal management robust by making the decision-making process faster, phasing out the unprofitable aircraft, and enhancing the decisiveness of the managers by allocating them more power.

The findings of this research not only outline the critical success factors for NAC, but they go further beyond by highlighting how each of the factors can be addressed for making a real change within the organisation. Given that no such comprehensive study was conducted before in the context of NAC by using a primary data collection approach, the findings of this research make significant original contributions to the body of knowledge as well as the professional practice by adding new insights to the literature. The research objective, therefore, was fully achieved.

6.3.5. Strategies for enhancing the performance of Nepal Airlines Corporation

The fifth objective of this study “*To make strategic recommendations for enhancing the overall performance of Nepal Airlines Corporation based on the research findings*” was designed to provide strategic recommendations to NAC after giving careful considerations to the strategic position of NAC, challenges faced by NAC, and critical success factors of NAC. Whilst making the recommendations, the researcher also focuses on the transforming landscape of the aviation industry, the competitive position of NAC, and the possible changes in both external and internal environments. In order to draw the strategic recommendations, careful consideration of the perceptions of all respondents was made. A foregoing section of this chapter (chapter 6.5) deals with the recommendations of this research in detail.

6.4. Original Contributions of the Research

The contributions made by the findings of this research are detailed below in three key categories: theoretical, methodological, and practical.

6.4.1. Theoretical Contributions

This study makes two key theoretical contributions as presented below:

6.4.1.1. *Identification of strategic challenges faced by Nepal Airlines Corporation*

After an extensive literature review, a knowledge gap was identified in chapter 2 of this thesis regarding no prior study conducting strategic analysis on NAC using a primary data collection approach and identifying the strategic challenges faced by NAC. Among a handful of research conducted on NAC and the Nepalese aviation industry, Yadav (2016) Conducted a strategic analysis of NAC using only SWOT analytical tool. Yadav (2016) paid no attention to macroeconomic variables that impact the organisation. Similarly, Joshi et al. (2015) also studied NAC to understand its present scenario; however, the analysis would superficial and no strategical analytical tool was used. Moreover, Gyanwali and Walsh (2020) researched factors influencing NAC performance, but it was done without using any strategical tools.

This study conducted comprehensive primary research by using PESTLE and SWOT as strategical analytical tools to analyse the internal and external environment of NAC. This research identified that NAC is facing severe political and operational challenges. As identified, political challenges include increased in corruption due to political appointment system, employees' political affiliation and extreme unionism leading to the lack of collaboration across departments, instability of the government, and outdated government public procurement act. Similarly, the key operational challenges included the lack of sufficient fleet, spare parts and ground handling equipment, lack of effective research and development, lack of coordination with TIA, and lengthy and ineffective employee recruitment process. These findings make significant theoretical contributions to the body of knowledge by extending its boundaries.

6.4.1.2. *Identification of the critical success factors of Nepal Airlines Corporation*

Although there were several studies conducted globally in different aviation industries for identifying the critical success factors of an airline company, an extensive literature review

conducted in this thesis indicated that no such priority study was conducted in the precise context of NAC. For example, Abudho et al. (2013) conducted a study to identify key success factors in airlines and overcoming challenges. Similarly, Bissessor (1996) conducted a study to identify the critical success factors of strategic air alliance. Although there are few empirical studies conducted in NAC to identify the factors that enhance organisational performance (i.e., Joshi et al., 2015; Gyanwali and Walsh, 2020), to the best of the researcher's knowledge, no study was precisely conducted to identify the critical success factors.

This study explicitly studied the critical success factors of NAC by interviewing senior managers, general employees, customers, ticketing agents, and an expert. This research identified six critical success factors, namely effective fleet management, establishing great organisational cultures for attracting talents, ensuring minimal external interference in the decision-making process, effective planning and development, effective management of people, and robust internal management. These findings make significant contributions to the literature by adding new insights. Besides, these findings are original as they are based on the data collected precisely for the purpose of this research.

6.4.2. Methodological Contributions

6.4.2.1. *Incorporation of the views of multiple sets of respondents*

In this research, prior to selecting the appropriate method for achieving the research objectives, a comprehensive review of the literature was conducted regarding the methods used by prior studies for conducting similar studies. Bitelmal (2010) conducted three semi-structured interviews with heads of various department to understand the strategic challenges faced by Dubai Airport whilst Yusoff (2008) conducted interpretivist study of strategic management in the public sector in local authority in Malaysia using case study consisting of 45 semi-structured interviews involving CEOs, head of departments/divisions, and middle manager.

In the precise context of NAC, Gyanwali and Walsh (2020) conducted mixed-method research on factors influencing NAC performance where primary data were obtained from in-depth interviews with fifteen governments and NAC executives and secondary data were collected from NAC publications, Nepal Government, and International Air Transport Association

(IATA). Similarly, Joshi et al. (2015) conducted research on the analysis of the present scenario of NAC by only using secondary data. Furthermore, Yadav (2016) conducted a case study research on NAC using secondary data as the source of information. Unlike previous studies, this study involved primary data collection and incorporated the perceptions of various stakeholders such as CEO, Directors, employees, expert, customers, and ticketing agents. The approach in which research objectives were answering this research is far more comprehensive than any similar previous studies in a similar context. Therefore, this study makes a methodological contribution by incorporating the views of different parties during the data collection process.

6.4.3. Practical Contributions

The findings of this study make six key contributions to professional practice:

6.4.3.1. *Fleet expansion for taking advantage of the growing market*

As identified and presented in chapter 4.5.2.1, NAC does not have sufficient fleet to maintain reliability, punctuality, and consistency of the services. Despite being an airlines company with a history of over six decades, NAC has weak domestic and international market share. The Chinese aircraft that have been used by NAC in the domestic market are perceived as not reliable and safe, eventually damaging the brand reputation and the loss of customer trust. This research identified that expanding fleet can enhance the sustainability and profitability of NAC. With the improving living standard of Nepalese people, the demand for air travel is increasing too. Therefore, this research identified that NAC should focus on fleet expansion and serving more domestic market to win back customer trusts. This finding makes a contribution to professional practice by providing ways of enhancing the performance of NAC.

6.4.3.2. *Investing in research and development practices for developing relevant and robust business plans*

As identified and discussed in the previous chapters, there is a lack of effective research and development practice in NAC for assessing and developing business strategies. The importance

of research and development is not understood by the management of NAC and the lack of effective research and development practices has prevented NAC from being an innovative organisation, ultimately impacting the organisational performance adversely. NAC does not have the required level of experience, skilled and knowledgeable researcher in the organisation to produce an effective business plan. NAC lacks the guidance of experts, tools required to conduct research and rely on outdated information to make critical organisational decisions. As discussed in chapter 5.4, organisations that implement effective research and development practices are more flexible, agile, and receptive to new changes. Therefore, NAC must focus on strengthening its research and development department by investing in it further. This finding provides a systematic way of developing sustainable business strategies, eventually making a contribution to professional practice.

6.4.3.3. *Introducing new employee training and development programmes*

The findings in chapter 4.6.5 indicated that the culture of training and development programme is non-existent in NAC. Employees in NAC have only received minimal training and the lack of effective training and development culture in NAC has stagnated professional and personal growth of employee, eventually preventing them from performing at a high level. Providing training to employees and further developing them is essential not only to ensure employees perform at their best level but also to ascertain employees are constantly motivated. Trained employees tend to be more confident and this can bring the practice of professionalism within the organisation. When employees are trained to the highest level, they not only tend to be motivated to perform the job, but they are also more likely to remain within the organisation as they are receiving benefits of professional and career growth. Therefore, the findings of this research highlight the importance of training and development programmes for NAC, making a significant contribution to professional practice.

6.4.3.4. *Introducing a merit-based employee promotion system and attractive reward and recognition schemes*

The findings of this research suggested that extreme unionism and political interference has severely affected the employee promotion system. The employees are currently promoted

based on their political connections, not on their merits. This has led to the organisation losing talented employees and not being able to recruit people that can actually add value to the organisation. Besides, the organisation also lacks reward and recognition schemes to encourage and motivate well-performing employees. Chapter 5.4 of this thesis discussed that employees perceive strong normative commitment if they feel valued by rewarding jobs and recognition schemes that perceive as a moral obligation to stay with the employer and perform par excellence. Therefore, it is essential for NAC to introduce a fair promotion system that values the merit have employees as well as introduce reward and recognition systems that aspire employees to perform better. This finding of this research makes a contribution to the professional practice by highlighting an approach in which NAC managers can retain and recruit best employees that are critical for the success of the organisation.

6.4.3.5. *Making internal management more robust to sustain in the competitive marketplace*

The findings of this research, as presented in chapter 4.6.6, highlighted several managerial inefficiencies such as slow decision making, lack of coordination with other government, private, and international organisations, and poor internal management. The respondents highlighted that internal management cannot take firm decision and actions against destructive forces within and outside of the organisation. The findings of this research suggest that leaders must be decisive in order to be able to implement changes. NAC should change its current management practices that are essential for robust internal management. Effective internal management requires leaders or managers to understand and improve decision making as it is central management actions. This finding of the research highlights the importance of robust management in gaining and sustaining competitive advantage, ultimately making a contribution to professional practice.

6.5. Recommendations

This research makes several recommendations to both NAC and the government of Nepal. Below, recommendations to both parties are presented based on the research findings.

6.5.1. Recommendations to Nepal Airlines Corporation

The aviation industry is extremely competitive, and it is growing more and more competitive every year with the emergence of new entrants. With increasing innovation in the industry, new entrants are entering the market with more modern and equipment such as new and latest aircraft that have lower operational costs. The findings of this research indicated that, although there is a growing market for NAC, the organisation has not been able to materialise it. In order to do so, it must expand its fleet as the current fleet is not sufficient to compete in both the domestic and international market. However, it is also vital for NAC to work on proper utilization of the currently available aircraft and making them more efficient. NAC has to be careful with the debts it accumulates with fleet expansion. This research also identified opportunities related to lowering the interest rates by working alongside the government of Nepal and securing load interest debts from foreign investors.

It is vital for NAC to capture its lost domestic market share to win the trust of customers in the domestic market before it competes in the international market with the biggest airline companies in the world. NAC should for now focus on fleet expansion only in the domestic market whilst effectively utilising the aircraft that are currently serving the international market. It is recommended to NAC to request a government bailout and invest in fleet expansion in the domestic sector. Growing fleet in the domestic market will help to turn around the organisation as Nepalese people, particularly when flying domestically, prefer NAC over other private airlines.

Additionally, NAC should make its employee aware of the urgency of the change required to save NAC. It needs to invest and work to establish effective research and development practices that will help to create robust business plans. NAC cannot survive nor grow without proper market growth strategies. The process in which employees are recruited, trained and managed is really ineffective within NAC. Therefore, the organisation must focus on recruiting the right talent, encouraging them to perform their best, and introducing attractive reward and recognition schemes to retain them for the long term. Besides, the organisation leadership also must take the necessary steps for controlling and managing the level of employees' political unionism in order to be able to implement new changes and strategies more effectively.

6.5.2. Recommendations to the government of Nepal

The current procurement act requires the involvement of the government officials and board members NAC in the purchasing process of aircraft whether or not the officials or board members have necessary knowledge and expertise in the area. The approach taken by government officials in their decision-making processes is rather interventional and motivated with their political agenda. The procurement act does not allow to buy certain aircraft that NAC requires rather has to follow the tender procedure to purchase an aircraft and equipment. The current government procurement act is inadequate, time-consuming, and does not have certain guideline follow for Airlines Company which land in controversy. Therefore, NAC should be allowed to run as an autonomous firm without having to follow the public procurement act.

Nepal government should also end the culture of political appointment in NAC and allow NAC to appoint its Executive Chairman on their meritocracy basis rather than political connections. The government should discourage or ban the political unionism in NAC as it is affecting coordination and collaborations among employees. Furthermore, NAC employees perceive that they work for the government rather than NAC due to strong political involvement and interference. Nepal government should monitor the progress of NAC however it should not control it as overprotection results in inefficiency. Besides, the Nepal government should work along with the Civil Aviation Authority of Nepal (CAAN) to remove the European Union ban as it is tarnishing the image of NAC and hopes to expand to international lubricative destinations. Finally, the employee recruitment process should be controlled by NAC so that they can recruit employees as per the requirement of the job. This will allow NAC to recruit the right individuals that match with the required experience, skills, and knowledge.

6.6. Limitations of the Research

Like any other study, this study also has its limitations which may impact the validity of the findings of the research to an extent. The area of the study is considered relatively new due to a limited number of studies being carried on the strategic aspects of airlines and an extremely limited number of studies conducted precisely in NAC. Therefore, it might have impacted the process of designing interview questions, possibly impacting the richness of data. It is possible

that, during the interview process, the researcher may not have been able to address all strategic factors in this research.

This research followed the interpretive philosophy using semi-structured interviews for primary data collection. Qualitative research is sometimes criticised for the lack of generalisation and replicability of the findings. Given that a limited number of respondents were considered in the study and the respondents from Tribhuvan International Airport and Nepal government were not included, it might be possible the findings do not provide a comprehensive picture of NAC. Besides, the use of a single method reduced the opportunities related to the triangulation of the findings. The researcher was denied access to sensitive financial information such as the cost of purchasing aircraft, revenues, and the grants received from the government of Nepal. In the absence of this information, the researcher may not have had a complete understanding of the organisation in order to be able to form competitive strategies that are most suitable for the organisation.

6.7. Further Research

As aforementioned, the number of studies conducted in NAC is extremely limited. Only a handful of studies were conducted before with most of them being either incomprehensive or based on secondary data. Below, some of the studies that could potentially extend this research are listed.

a. A New study incorporating five forces, value chain analysis, and the resource-based view

The extensive literature review in chapter 2 discussed various strategic analytical tools for conducting the analysis of both internal and external business environments. After considering all objectives and lack of sufficient information, only PESTLE and SWOT strategic analytical tools were used in this research. However, further studies could be carried out by also using other strategic analytical tools such as porter's five forces, value chain analysis, and resource-based view. This could provide a more accurate picture of NAC's strategic position

b. A new study consisting of multiple cases

This study used a single case; however, choosing multiple cases may have helped to contrast and compare different operational factors. This could help to further strengthen the findings and the findings could be more generalizable in the wider context.

c. Use of mixed-method for understanding the perceptions of customers

This study only used a qualitative research design. However, a further study could be carried using multiple methods where both qualitative and quantitative techniques could be used for data collections. A quantitative data collection method can be used to gather perceptions of the customers regarding NAC by deploring questionnaires. Doing so will allow future researchers to collect a large scale of data and more reliable findings.

d. Impacts of Covid-19 and the challenges faced by NAC

The research data of this study was collected prior to the emergence of COVID-19. Given that many industries including aviation is highly impacted by COVIA-19, a research on the strategic challenges faced by NAC on the post COVID-19 era could identify meaningful findings that could be more relevant to the current business environment.

6.8. Conclusions

This chapter of the thesis dealt with highlighting the contributions of the research along with recommendations to the future researchers. In order to draw contributions, this chapter revisited the research objectives, highlighted how each of them what achieved, and stated the findings related to each of them. Similarly, this chapter also highlighted theoretical, methodological, and practical contributions of the findings. Furthermore, recommendations were made to the management of NAC and the government of Nepal on the basis of the findings of the research. Additionally, this chapter also dealt with the possible limitations of the research that may have impacted the reliability and validity of research findings.

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8. Appendices

Appendix A: Ethics Approval

04/02/2019

Dear Bijay Karki,

Your application 6448: Strategic challenges of Nepal Airlines and recommendation of change management framework for long term profitability , submission 5027, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

Appendix B: Participant Consent Form

Research Consent Form

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

Title of the Study: *Strategic challenges of Nepal Airlines and recommendation of change management framework for long term profitability*

<i>The participant should complete the whole of this sheet</i>		
<i>Please tick the appropriate box</i>		
	YES	NO
Have you read and understood Research Participant Information Sheet?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Have you had an opportunity to ask questions and discuss this study?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Have you received satisfactory answers to all your questions?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Do you understand that you will not be referred to by name in any report Concerning the study?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Do you understand that your participation is voluntary and are free to withdraw from the study:		
• At any time?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• Without having to give a reason for withdrawing?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
• (where relevant, adapt if necessary) without affecting your Future care?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(Where relevant) I agree to my interview being recorded.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(Where relevant) I agree to the use of non-attributable direct quotes when the study is written up or published.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Do you agree to take part in this study?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Signature of Research Participant:	Date:	
Name in capitals:		
Signature of Researcher:	Date:	
Name in Capitals: BIJAY KARKI		
Email address: [REDACTED]	Personal details withheld.	

Appendix C: Interview Questions

Topic: Strategic challenges of Nepal Airlines and recommendation of change management framework for long term profitability

Interviewee Background

Would you mind telling me your name? (Names will be kept anonymous and would be represented in alphabetical or numerical order)

What is your position and how long have you been in this airlines and position for?

What are your responsibility and duties in this airlines company?

The Airlines Aim and Objectives (Question for Executive chairman and Managing Director)

1. What are goals for Nepal Airlines and where will you see Nepal Airlines 10 years from now?

2. If any, how is Nepal Airlines going to achieve its goals?

The Nepal Airlines Resources (Questions for Board and Management Department)

3. Who is responsible for making decisions concerning investing, expanding, and improving services at your airlines? How has all decision being going since your arrival?

4. How often does the Executive chairman or Managing Director meet with department managers to discuss issues concerning the Airlines business?

5. How often do employee attend training and development programmes?

6. To what extent do you think that the experience and knowledge of your employees has contributed to the growth level of Nepal Airlines?

7. What are the challenges faced by Nepal Airlines of only having one international Airport to what extent do you think that the geographical location of your airport has contributed to its growth level?

8. Do you think that the Airline's physical resources have enhanced its operation performance? If yes how and If No what are the step taken to enhance operational performance?

Nepal Airlines Strategies (Board and Management Department)

9. How do different units or department of Nepal Airlines cooperate and coordinate with each other?

10. How would you describe the business model of Nepal Airlines and how stable is it?

11. What is Nepal airlines strategic directions? How could Nepal Airlines change its strategic direction?

12. Has Nepal Airlines adopted any cost control strategies in order to offer its airline's customers the lowest price possible and does it have any differentiation strategy offering different and unique services to cater specific type of customer? If yes since when?

13. Does your Airlines focus on a particular group of customers or specific geographical area?

14. Has your Airlines diversified its business by investing in unrelated areas such as hotels and properties or in services such as roads or buses in order to expand geographically by enlarging the airport catchments area? If yes then since, when?
15. Has Nepal Airlines invest or partner in local travel agencies and tour operators as a marketing scheme to attract more passengers to use Nepal Airlines? How Nepal Tourism Board has help to enhance the reputation of Nepal airlines and has it lead to growth of customers?
16. What is the purpose of Alliance in your view? Has your Airlines established any strategic alliances and cooperation with any other Airlines companies?
17. Who do you buy your aircrafts from? How has been the purchase of the aircrafts been in recent years? Any issues, if yes what are they?
18. What is your opinion on the effectiveness of purchasing and acquiring other existing Airlines in order to gain greater market share?
19. Does the relation between Nepal Airlines and its airport customers involve any collaborative approach on issues such as traffic projections, capacity requirements and future investment projects? (If yes what are the projects on line?)
20. Does your airlines use market research and analysis to develop air services and routes (If yes could you mention the recent ones)? Does Nepal Airlines provided any special promotion or discount programmes such as lower charges to potential new routes or public service discount?
21. What are the strategic response of Nepal airlines is for its competitors? What are the strategic plans to get Nepal airlines out of the no flying band list from Europe?

Nepal Airlines Brand (Questions for Management)

22. Do you think that Nepal airlines brand name and reputation have attracted more passengers nationally and internationally?
23. To what extent do you think that Nepal Airlines is focusing on providing better quality of service to its customers?
24. What is your opinion on the overall effectiveness of the airlines marketing scheme? For example, advertising, promoting and passenger loyalty schemes.

The Competitive Environment (Questions for Management)

25. Which of the existing national and international airlines are the competitors of Nepal airlines and do you see a risk of potential new airlines entering market? What distinguishes from its competitors?
26. Do you think home based airport (Tribhuvan international airport) has help Nepal airlines to operate efficiently? How the relationship between Nepal airlines and its supplier is companies those that provide services such as aircraft ground handling, immigration and catering?
27. Do you think that substitute services such as roads are affecting the operational performance of Nepal Airlines?
28. How would you describe growth Of Nepal Airlines? What are the elements you believe hindering the progress of Nepal airlines?

The General Environment (Question for Board and Management Department)

29. To what extent do you think that the economic condition of the Nepal has contributed to establishing Nepal Airline's market position?
30. Do you think that social and cultural factors have contributed to air travel demand in Nepal?
31. Are concerns over issues such as global warming, pollution and noise affecting the growth level of your airlines?
32. Is Nepal airlines subject to any legislation and restrictions that may interfere with its planning, operation and business?
33. Do you think that technological factors have had a major influence on Nepal Airline's operational performance?
34. Do you think that political and economic forces have had an influence on the growth level of Nepal Airlines?

35. Do you believe that strategic change in Nepal Airlines possible? What kind of resistance would you think in change process would occur?
36. To finish, what would you describe as the main factors behind a successful airlines company?
37. Would you like to add any other information?

Questions for customers and the Agents of Nepal Airlines

Customers:

1. Have you heard about Nepal Airlines? If yes, how often do you use them?
2. What do you think about customer service, service, and time keeping about Nepal Airlines?
3. What elements do you think are hindering the progress Nepal Airlines and have you seen any improvement in last 5 years?
4. What improvements can Nepal Airlines do to become a more competitive Airline?
5. Would you like to see Nepal airlines more globally?

Agents:

1. Are Nepal airlines ticket prices as competitive as its competitors?
2. How to you describe booking process of Nepal airlines and what are the demands of Nepal airlines is like?
3. Do you think Nepal Airlines flies in most popular destination?
4. Do you have communication problem with Nepal Airlines?
5. How can Nepal airlines be more competitive?

Appendix D: Employee Interview Questions

Topic: Strategic challenges of Nepal Airlines and recommendation of change management framework for long term profitability

Employee Interview Questions

Interview Background

Would you mind telling me your name please?

What is your position and how long you have been in this airlines for?

What are your key responsibility and duties in this airlines?

Questions

1. How often do you attend training and development programmes?
2. To what extent do you think that your experiences and knowledge of your employee has contributed to the growth of Nepal Airlines?
3. How often do you meet your department director to discuss any issues concerning the airlines business? Is the accessible to meet the Executive chairman?
4. How do the different departments of Nepal Airlines cooperate and communicate? How accessible is it to communicate with other department?
5. Since the time you have been here has there any transformational change taken place? If yes how it went or If no is there any changes taking place?
6. How do you describe the pay package, reward system and the benefits that you get from Nepal airlines?
7. How do you describe the brand Name and Reputation of Nepal Airlines?
8. How do you describe growth of Nepal Airlines? What are the elements you believe are hindering the progress of Nepal Airlines?
9. Do you think that political and economic forces have had an influence on the growth level of Nepal airlines?
10. Is there any major Technological factors that have a major influence on Nepal Airlines operational performance?
11. What would you describe as the main factors behind a successful airlines company? What might resist those changes?

Thank You very much for your cooperation

Appendix E: Letter from the Director of Studies

To Whom It May Concern

21/02/2019

This is to confirm that Mr Bijay Karki is my DBA student who is working on a research programme regarding the Nepal Airlines. As part of work for his thesis Bijay will need to travel to Nepal to collect data on the subject. I appreciate any cooperation with his project.

Thank you very much

Dr Hosein Piranfar

Director of Studies

London Campus

UWS, 235 Southwark Bridge Road

SE1 6NP

Personal details
withheld.

Appendix F: Data Collection Approval by the Director of Studies

Notification of Change of Circumstances (Non-EU/EEA Students)

This form should be used to notify any changes of circumstances affecting Non-EU International Students. This will include any period away from UWS, whether this is for study, research or writing up of dissertation/thesis or holiday out with set UWS holiday periods. The completed form should be returned to Registry.

1. Reason for Student's period away from UWS:
DATA COLLECTION
2. Date when period away from UWS is due to commence:
12/03/2019
3. Expected Date of return to UWS:
10/04/2019

This form should be returned to Registry

For Office Use	
Do Home Office need to be informed (Y/N)	
Date Home Office notified of changes	

Personal details withheld.

Appendix G: Data Collection Approval Letter from NAC in Nepali Language

Personal details withheld.

Appendix H: Request for Data Collection

Respected Sir,

My name is Bijay Karki. I am currently pursuing my PhD (Doctorate in Business Administration - DBA) from University of The West of Scotland, London. I am currently working on research of Nepal Airlines and its topic is Strategic challenges of Nepal Airlines and recommendation of change management framework for long-term profitability. The aim of this study is to identify the strategic challenges faced by Nepal Airlines, analysis business model and then recommend strategic change management framework for long term profitability.

I have chosen Nepal Airlines as there has not been any research done in strategic challenges faced by Nepal Airlines. Strategic planning in the context of Nepal Airlines is still frail and anonymous in the sense that there is lack of documented proof of its practise in organisation. While doing so researcher will be conducting semi-structured interview with higher hierarchy people from various department as qualitative data collection process. The collection of the data will be only related with strategy, Business Model and change management. There will not be any data collection in which the participant will be uncomfortable and goes beyond Nepal Airlines rules and regulation. Participants can withdraw from study anytime without any notice.

The data collected from Nepal Airlines will not be used for any other purpose. All the participant will be given a copy of participant information sheet and consent form which encloses all the information regarding research. All the participant's identity will be strictly confidential where no name or any information will be disclosed. This research has been submitted to Ethical Review committee of University where it has rigorously asses all ethical issues and have approved for data collection process. Ethical committee has code of conduct under University rules and regulation where it requires the researcher to keep all the data collected confidential.

With this application, I have attached a copy of Biometric card (residence permit), a copy of my Student Identity Card, a copy of UK Driving Licence , a copy of support letter from Director of Studies, Ethical Approval Letter, Participant information sheet and Consent form.

I would request you to kindly grant the permission to collect data from Nepal Airlines various Departments. Your kind co-operation will only help to fulfil and achieve the aims and objectives of my research.

Thanking you.

Yours sincerely

Personal details
withheld.

Appendix I: Sample interview transcript of a Senior Manager

1. How long have you been working in this airlines in this position?

I have been working in Nepal airlines for 14 years, *(The rest of response is deleted to protect the confidentiality of the respondent)*

2. What are your responsibility and duties in Nepal airlines?

The respond has been deleted for confidentiality of respondents.

3. Who is responsible for investing, expanding any services of Nepal airlines?

This all falls under Corporate Department and route expansion and market expansion falls under commercial department anything that are related with services will come under engineering department. We called it as cameo, we Nepal airlines have ground handling department as well which handles the ground handling services in Tribhuwan International airport. We have all have diversified responsibility.

4. Since your arrival 14 years ago has there been any investment in Nepal airlines?

Yes, there has been investment since my arrival in Nepal airlines. For example, when I came in Nepal airlines we had only 2 Boeing 757 and in latter stage we had 2 airbus and similarly in domestic sector we bought in 6 Chinese aircrafts. Recently, we bought 2 airbus 330. These investment injection has been made in Nepal airlines.

5. If we have to be exact how long ago this was all investment happened?

It happened around 10 years ago where there was boom in investment.

6. How often do you meet with CEO or Executive Chairman regarding all the issues and planning of Nepal airlines?

Board meeting will happen whenever it is required however executive committee meeting will involve CEO, Executive Chairman and Directors of every departments will sit and we do them every after 15 days. Another one is sector or department wise they have their in every week, safety committee meeting that happens every week and flight review committee that happens every day which reviews flight per day. These are the major meetings that happens.

7. How does the meeting which analysis the strategic issues of Nepal airlines works?

There are two there types of strategic analysis in Nepal airlines one if fare analysis which is done in commercial department as and when required. Another one is schedule meetings are

done when the prepared schedule has to be change for various reasons like no availability of flights.

8. How effective is the recruitment policy of Nepal airlines and are you getting the required level of help and support from airlines?

Yes, I am getting the required level of help, support from Nepal airlines in the requirement policy. I can give you the example of the recent example where we had 34 vacancy but received around 1000 applications. The requirement policy of the Nepal airlines involves Lok sawab ayago where it conducts the written examination as per syllabus design by Nepal airlines, qualification and criteria asked from Nepal airlines. So, due this reasons there will not be any bias decisions, unfair in recruitment process.

So, we have been getting talented people and there is no problem in recruitment policy. However, due the business we are in the technical manpower we need that are not available in Nepal are having difficulty in recruiting them. Till now, we are bring different foreign experts like bring Chinese for Chinese aircrafts. That is why in this department sometimes we do not get the types of the people we need. It is due to not having qualified manpower in Nepal and it is sometimes hard to find the technical manpower around the globe as well.

9. How often does your employee attend training and development program?

There are three types of training one is mandatory (like licence for pilots without these training their licences will not be valid) and these types of training are done whenever required and another type of training is general training those training are provided to administration employee leadership training, stress management training and fire fighter training are provided to them and they are regularly done to them.

10. What are the advantages and disadvantages of having one and only international airport in Nepal in the context of Nepal airlines? What are the difficulty NAC facing with having one international? Airport?

The main problem NAC is facing now is the traffic congestion where airlines has to been in hold in airport. Airlines so due to that there timing issues, increase in fuel cost, there are not slots available, it is small airport that why there is baggage issue where it doesn't come out on time and ultimately, people blame NAC for that . So these are the difficulty NAC has been facing.

11. So, it means that NAC is responsible for handling in the airport?

Yes, NAC is responsible for handling of the luggage in airports.

12. So, what is the exact reason of facing such difficulty? Is it because of being small airport, not having enough facility?

There are combination of two to three things like there is only one x-ray machine for the luggage as all the luggage has to be x-ray, like there are three belts and if 4 airlines arrived together than one has to been on hold.

13. How has geographical location impact on NAC?

We have to look this thing differently and have three divided categories namely stall a, stall b and stall c. Yes it has hinder the growth of NAC in terms of producing skill manpower, it does have impact on the performance of airlines industry as well.

14. How has the NAC physical resources help NAC to enhance the performance of NAC?

NAC doesn't have sufficient physical resources that could enhance the performance of airlines industry.

15. What are the plans that NAC will take in future to overcome such shortage of physical resources?

We have made 10 years plan in which we have disclose the increase of aircraft every year and the purchase of the aircraft NAC will make. We have plan to add two more aircraft in truck routes domestic markets and then purchase 5 to 6 stall aircraft like twin otter and with same business plan we have plan to add 4 narrow body like 320. It was made as 10 years business plan with same business plan we bought 2 320 aircraft before and 330 was bought on same business plan. However, those strategy is review every year.

16. How do different departments of NAC cooperate and coordinate with each other?

It is very easy to communicate with each of the department we use various source like email, phone. We do not have any issues with the communication in NAC.

17. How would you describe the business model of NAC and how stable is it?

If you look on the past of NAC were on operating profit airlines and always were but due to within NAC is stable. We have two different wing as service market domestic and international where we have concept of providing service in domestic market and expanding market in international market.

18. What is the strategic directions of NAC and how can NAC change its strategic direction?

By looking at current strategy, we are planning to buy 2 more narrow body in five years' time as the current aircraft will not be able to match the goal NAC wants to achieve. Similarly, adding 5 to 6 more domestic airlines.

19. Has NAC adopted any cost control strategies and goes it have any differentiation strategy offering different and unique services to cater specific type of customer? If yes since when?

Yes, NAC does have cost control strategist in domestic market where it does want to provide service and fly to those rural destination where other airlines does not to fly. The market in which we are fly internationally are all Nepalese market and for those customers as being Nepal national flag carrier they are emotionally attached and feel like they are on board on their own home.

Whereas, if they fly with other airlines they only feel they have come home once they landed to airport of Nepal. So, there is feeling that Nepal airlines is one of our and this opportunity Nepal airlines has been grabbing. We do have competitive pricing comparing to all our international competitors. In future, there is aim of bring tourist from our flying destination to visit Nepal 2020 working alongside with tourism of Nepal.

20. Does airlines focus on a particular group of customer or specific geographical area?

Yes, it does focus on particular customer before selecting any specific geographical are. First of all we look Nepalese diaspora living abroad and the population they have because it is not possible to run airlines on support of tourists coming Nepal. So, the first thing we do before selecting any destination is to look on the number of Nepali people living there.

21. Has NAC diversified its business by investing in unrelated areas such as hotels and properties or in services such as roads or buses in order to expand geographically or increase revenue streams?

There is not any direct investment however the buildings, lands and all the property of NAC has been utilised fully. Like they have been rented.

22. Has NAC invest or partner in local travel agencies and tour operators as a marketing scheme to attract more passengers to use NAC? How Nepal tourism board has help to enhance the reputation of Nepal airlines and has it lead to growth of the customer?

There will be some sorts of partnership while you are Airlines Company like in any sort of business campaign. In context to tourism Nepal as it promotes Nepal and so does the NAC. So, with other there will be partnership as and when required. Yes, Nepal tourism has helped in the growth of NAC

23. What is the purpose of alliance in your view? Has NAC established any strategic alliances and cooperation with any other airlines company?

Nepal is small airlines company however there were alliance in Europe in past. However, in our neighbour countries there are giant airlines that are commencing their services.so ,there is kind of trend that gain airlines company keep the higher profit range and lower profit range are given to NAC. So, NAC does not have any established alliance with any other company. We do have networking though like a customer can purchase ticket from us travelling to London and travel up to the destination. For example, we fly like Hamad airport and then they fly with Qatar airways to London.

24. Who do you buy your aircraft from? How has been purchase of the aircraft been in recent years? Any issues, if yes what are they?

There is tender process in our organisation however as having airbus aircraft in our fleet there is high chance of going for airbus again however it is not guaranteed as everything happens through tender basis. There has been concern raise during the purchase procure of aircraft and it is being look in details but has not been concluded that what has not happen. There are issues always when purchasing anything in NAC however the solution also comes time and again. There always has been so sort of accusation without being any one guilty. If there is any one doing wrong thing and not following the guidelines of purchasing aircraft then on they should serve for their actions however just because of someone accusation the news come out in media which then creates frustration among employee , demotivates employee.

25. Does the relationship between NAC and its airport customers involve any collaboration approach on issues such as traffic projections, capacity requirements and future investment projects? (If yes what are the projects on line)

There has always been communication with TIA and they are the coordinator of airport itself and we do work under them in the airport. There are been regular meeting with TIA regarding this. However, I am not exactly sure about any collaboration approach.

26. Does your airlines use market research and analysis to develop air services and routes (if yes could you please mention the recent ones)? Does NAC provided any special promotion or discount programmes such as lower charges to potential new routes or any public service discounts?

Yes, we market research before expanding and developing air services and routes. We do regularly promotion on new routes for example while promoting our new route Bangkok we offer 1 free tickets for every 4th one purchase.

27. What are the strategic response of NAC for its competitors? What are the strategic plan to get NAC out of the no flying band list from Europe?

The one and most important thing, we have to understand is NAC has been not put on blacklist rather European commission has blacklisted whole Nepal civil aviation and NAC and all those Nepali airlines fall under them. As NAC does international destination that is why NAC has suffer due to Nepal civil aviation blacklisted. So, if NAC is to come out from being black listed then whole Nepal civil aviation authority has to come out from that list. However, there are provision like certain aircraft can be exempted from them and NAC is working on them. We are now working on various safety aspects recently.

28. Do you think that political and economic forces have/had an influence on the growth level of NAC?

There are positive influence from political forces as NAC is fully owned by government. Like for example, when purchasing an aircraft Nepal governments makes decision through cabinet level and provides NAC with new aircraft. So all the new purchase of new aircraft has been possible through the positive attitude from government as well as from NAC. There has not been much hinder from government forces. The economic aspects of Nepali people has been growing and there is the growth in the people travel in and around Nepal as well as abroad for tourism, business and leisure purpose.

29. Do you believe that strategic change in NAC is possible? What kind of resistance would you think in change process would occur?

The business plan which we set out for 10 years as per same business plan we have received 4 new aircraft. We will revise the business plan time and again and Nepal government is provide all the help that is required for this business plan.

30. What are the human resources strategy is place to hire right employee and what are your policy to retain those employees?

There are two recruitment categories in NAC one permanent employee which 99% has retention rate and two contract employee which are hire until our permanent employee are not ready for the job assign and mostly they are hired for technical field. The employee who are hire for contract basis remains until there contract expires and some of them stays with us as permanent employee.so there is not really problem with retention of employee.

31. What do you describe the main factor behind a successful airlines company?

The main factor is market, airlines is been guided by market and needs sufficient equipment. So, if there is sufficient market and equipment there is high possibility of sustainability. If one them are missing then the operating cost will be high for airlines then there is risk of going out of business. Then to support those there are roles to play human resources, economic aspects and competitive market are all secondary.

32. What impact does NAC have as TIA itself is not ready for higher number of traffic and loads on runway?

If the country does not have sufficient infrastructure then it will have impact all round. Similarly, TIA does not have sufficient infrastructure which it has impact on all the airlines. If there was another international airport then it will benefit all the airlines industry.